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Fluid-Structure Interaction with the open-source software preCICE

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Abstract

The partitioned approach to Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) simulation offers notable advantages over the monolithic approach, particularly in terms of development time, flexibility, and modularity. However, setting up such simulations can be challenging, especially in black-box coupling scenarios where limited information is provided by the solvers to the coupling library. This work aims to assess the characteristics and performance of the coupling procedures implemented in preCICE, focusing on its integration into the in-house CFD solver FASTEST-3D and the open-source structural solver CalculiX. Data mapping methods will be evaluated using the ASTE testing environment, with particular attention given to RBF-based approaches. Another key objective is to understand the coupling schemes available in preCICE, with an emphasis on quasi-Newton methods. The influence of different coupling configurations with regards to various mapping techniques and coupling scheme combinations will be investigated using standard numerical benchmarks such as the flexible lid-driven cavity problem and the Hron/Turek FSI3 benchmark. These studies will enable a comprehensive performance evaluation on a modern computing cluster, focusing on runtime, scalability, and accuracy. Ultimately, this work aims to advance the understanding of partitioned coupling strategies for FSI problems and to identify best practices for achieving robust and efficient simulations using preCICE.

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Nomenclature

The abbreviations and notations used in this report are explained below with their units. If a notation does not appear in this section, it is explained in the context of the report.

Abbreviation

ASTE	Artificial Solver Testing Environment
HPC	High-Performance Computing
ALE	Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CSD	Computational Structure Dynamics
DNS	Direct Numerical Simulation
LES	Large-Eddy Simulation
FSI	Fluid-Structure Interaction
IQN	Interface Quasi-NEWTON
MPI	Message-Passing Interface
CV	Control Volume
GPGPU	General-Purpose Graphics Processing Unit
RBF	Radial Basis Function
XML	Extensible Markup Language
API	Application Programming Interface
iff.	if and only if

Notation

$\llbracket n, m \rrbracket \equiv \{n, n + 1, \dots, m\}$	Closed interval of consecutive integers between n and m
$\mathfrak{M}_{n,m}(E)$	Set of matrices of size $n \times m$ with coefficients in E
$\mathfrak{M}_n(E)$	Set of square matrices of size $n \times n$ with coefficients in E

Introduction

Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) refers to scenarios, in which a solid body undergoes deformation due to the motion of a surrounding fluid, while the fluid flow is simultaneously influenced by the movement of the structure. FSI phenomena are encountered in a wide range of engineering and scientific applications. The following paragraphs provide representative examples, though the list is not intended to be exhaustive.

One of the most classical use cases of FSI is aeroelasticity, which studies the stability of a given structure exposed to air flow. This is especially critical for aircraft design, as aeroelasticity can lead to various phenomena such as flutter [31, 60, 108], control reversal [110], or buffeting [22] across different flight regimes. In the context of civil engineering, the structural dynamics of lightweight, flexible structures, such as tents [29, 30, 72, 73, 109] or airships [68], are also influenced by aeroelastic effects, which can lead to significant design challenges due to significant wind-induced loads. Skyscrapers and bridges are not immune to such effects [24, 36, 84], as they are exposed to varying wind conditions and gusts. A classical and famous example highlighting the importance of wind-structure interactions in civil engineering is the Tacoma Narrows Bridge (see **Fig. 1**). This bridge was known to oscillate vertically in wind conditions as low as 5 to 7 km/h. Only four months after its opening, the bridge collapsed after its initial vertical oscillation transitioned into a pure torsional mode.

Given the significant impact of such phenomena on the design and safety of the products affected by them, the study of the dynamical response of structures to fluid-induced loads is mandated by various regulatory frameworks. In the aeronautical sector, the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) has established criteria and standards addressing these effects, as illustrated in regulations such as CS-23 and CS-25 [26, 27]. Similarly, the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) in the United States enforces comparable requirements, notably through Part 23 and Part 25 of the Federal Aviation Regulations [1, 2].

Comparable regulatory frameworks also exist in the civil engineering domain. For example, in

Figure 1 – The Tacoma Bridge incident, a famous case for the influence of aeroelasticity in civil engineering design. *Source: Kristen Moore, University of Michigan.*

Europe, [Eurocode 1](#)¹ and its associated standards provide detailed guidelines for the design of structures subjected to various actions, including wind-induced loads.

A less straightforward application of FSI can be found in modeling the human circulatory system, or more generally in the field of biology, particularly when simulating the behavior of the heart or the flow of blood through arteries for example [65, 94, 95]. Additionally, the numerical investigation of slosh dynamics² inside tanks also benefits from FSI simulations [76, 81].

Numerical FSI cases are multi-physics problems, as they involve both computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and computational structural dynamics (CSD). Additional physical effects may also be incorporated. The most common are thermal effects, which are particularly important in the design of mechanical components subjected to temperature variations, such as turbine blades [11, 78], and acoustics [8, 105], which plays a significant role in the prediction of noise generation. It became evident from an early stage in the numerical investigation of such problems that dedicated solvers for each subtask or physical phenomenon were sometimes more relevant, rather than relying on a single solver to handle all aspects of the problem simultaneously [16].

The separation of a coupled system into specialized solvers is known as the partitioned approach, while the use of a single solver that simultaneously models all relevant phenomena is referred to as the monolithic approach. The latter can offer greater robustness and efficiency for certain applications. However, the partitioned approach provides increased flexibility during the modeling phase and allows for the reuse of existing components that are optimized for specific

¹<https://eurocodes.jrc.ec.europa.eu/EN-Eurocodes/eurocode-1-actions-structures>

²Slosh refers to the movement of liquid inside another object.

subtasks. This simulation strategy presents its own set of challenges, particularly in the transfer of information at solver interfaces and in the coupling of the underlying systems [48, 100]. Additionally, the potential for scalability on multi-core clusters or heterogenous architectures (with acceleration devices such as GPGPUs) is also a topic of interest when dealing with the partitioned approach [67].

This context defines the foundations of the present master thesis, which focuses on a detailed study of the open-source coupling library `preCICE`³, designed to facilitate the implementation of partitioned multi-physics simulations. This work will investigate the data mapping techniques used to transfer information between solvers at coupling interfaces, as well as the coupling algorithms employed by `preCICE`, with a particular focus on their implementation. Numerical benchmarks, such as the lid-driven cavity and the TUREK-HRON FSI3 case (see **Sect. 1.3** for more information), will be used to evaluate the simulation setup against classical, well-established reference cases. All numerical simulations are conducted on a modern large-scale computing cluster hosted at Helmut-Schmidt-Universität⁴ and the MARVIN computing cluster owned by the Fluid Mechanics Department (Pfs).

The structure of this thesis is as follows: The first chapter of this report is dedicated to providing an overview of the theoretical background relevant to the numerical investigation of FSI cases. It also introduces the terminology commonly used in this field and within the context of `preCICE`, as well as the software tools used in this study. The second and third chapters present a detailed analysis of the data mapping techniques and coupling algorithms implemented in `preCICE`, respectively. Both chapters includes theoretical discussions, implementation details, and corresponding numerical experiments. The report concludes with a summary of the findings and suggestions for future research directions related to the integration of `preCICE` into the simulation environment at Pfs/HSU.

³<https://precice.org/>

⁴Computational resources on the HPC cluster HSUper have been provided by the project hpc.bw, funded by dtec.bw – Digitalization and Technology Research Center of the Bundeswehr. dtec.bw is funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU.

Introduction to Fluid-Structure Interaction with preCICE

This chapter begins with an overview of the theoretical background relevant to the numerical investigation of FSI problems in the context of preCICE, including a presentation of the key features implemented in the library. The two solvers used, *FASTEST-3D* and *CalculiX*, are introduced in **Sect. 1.2**, along with a brief overview of their capabilities. The numerical benchmarks and test cases employed in this work are described in **Sect. 1.3**.

1.1 Overview of preCICE features and related terminology

This section briefly describes the features included in the preCICE library and the terminology used in the context of partitioned FSI simulations. It is intended to familiarize the reader with the key concepts and components of preCICE, which will be essential for understanding the numerical experiments and results presented in this work.

1.1.1 What is preCICE?

preCICE, which stands for *Precise Code Interaction Coupling Environment*, is a coupling *library* that facilitates the setup and execution of partitioned multi-physics simulations. As illustrated in **Fig. 1.1**, preCICE enables the coupling of different solvers through the use of *adapters*, which are software components responsible for calling the preCICE library to handle communication, data mapping, and coupling. For solvers with available source code, the preCICE adapter typically replaces the main solver loop and advances its respective part of the simulation or the solver integrates preCICE directly in its main loop.

¹<https://github.com/precice/precice.github.io/tree/master/material>

Figure 1.1 – Overview of the preCICE coupling library. Source: [preCICE official materials](#)¹.

Contrary to what the figure might suggest, preCICE does not rely on a central instance to orchestrate the simulation. Instead, it employs a peer-to-peer architecture, where each component, which is referred to as a *participant* in the preCICE terminology, independently performs computations and communicates with others as needed.

preCICE is written in C++ and hosted on [GitHub](#)². It is free and open-source software, distributed under the GNU LGPL3 license. The library offers ready-to-use adapters for popular solvers such as OpenFOAM, FEniCS, and CalculiX. Additionally, it provides bindings to its API in C, Fortran, Python, Julia, Rust, and MATLAB. preCICE is developed and actively maintained in the groups of Benjamin UEKERMANN (Usability and Sustainability of Simulation Software) and Miriam SCHULTE (Simulation of Large Systems) at the **University of Stuttgart** and in the group of Hans-Joachim Bungartz (Scientific Computing in Computer Science) at the **Technical University of Munich (TUM)** (see the [About](#)³ section on the official website).

Figure 1.2 – Coupled simulation setup files for the solvers FASTEST-3D and CalculiX, coupled through preCICE.

²<https://github.com/precice>

³<https://precice.org/about.html>

The complete simulation setup is defined in an XML configuration file, conventionally named `precice-config.xml`. As illustrated in **Fig. 1.2**, this file coexists with the configuration files of the individual participants (in this work, FASTEST-3D and CalculiX). All information related to the coupling procedure is concentrated in the XML file, allowing each solver to be configured largely as if it were running independently, with only minor adjustments required for coupling. A detailed description of all supported options is provided in the [XML configuration reference](#)⁴.

The preCICE configuration file `precice-config.xml` is typically located in the simulation working directory and is read by the preCICE library at runtime. It defines the coupling interface, specifying the data to be exchanged, the mapping methods to be applied, and the coupling algorithms to be used. It also sets the communication protocols and network interfaces (e.g., Ethernet, Infiniband) for data exchange between participants.

The latest preCICE reference paper [25] from 2021 provides a comprehensive overview of the library's features, capabilities, and design principles. This paper describes preCICE **v2.0**, while the version used in this report is **v3.2**. Some information might be outdated, but it serves as a valuable resource for understanding the underlying concepts and implementation details of preCICE. Other relevant publications are presented in [the official literature guide](#)⁵.

The preCICE development follows strict coding standards ensuring that the following principles are respected [25]:

- **Usability** through robust numerical methods, ready-to-use adapters, and a well-defined API with examples
- **Reliability** through extensive testing at multiple levels within the software
- **Sustainability** through community-driven development, well-defined release cycles and CI⁶ pipelines

preCICE has been tested against benchmarks [20], while its performance and scalability were proven in [19, 96]. It has been used in various applications [5, 42, 59, 75].

Each year since 2020, the preCICE community organizes a workshop to discuss the latest developments, share experiences, and foster collaboration. Presentations about real-world applications of preCICE are made in addition to teaching sessions to explain the basis of the library to newcomers.

⁴<https://precice.org/configuration-xml-reference.html>

⁵<https://precice.org/fundamentals-literature-guide.html>

⁶Continuous Integration

Figure 1.3 – Example of non-conforming and non-matching meshes based on [48]. This illustrates the need for data mapping methods to transfer information between different meshes.

1.1.2 Terminology and important concepts

This section introduces key definitions and concepts that are linked to the preCICE library. Some terms are specific to preCICE and might have different meanings in other contexts. Some aspects such as data mapping and coupling schemes are discussed in more detail in their respective chapters.

Data mapping and coupling schemes Data mapping methods and coupling schemes are two key concepts in the simulation of partitioned FSI problems and form the core focus of this report.

Data mapping refers to the process of transferring information, such as forces or displacements, between different simulation participants, specifically from one participant’s mesh to another. This step is crucial, as most FSI cases involve either non-matching or non-conforming meshes. Non-matching meshes may geometrically overlap, while non-conforming meshes share a common underlying geometry at the interface. Both types are likely not to share common nodes and require interpolation or projection techniques to ensure accurate data exchange [48] (see **Fig. 1.3** for an example). This concept is investigated in more details in **Chap. 2**.

On the other hand, the role of coupling schemes, in the context of partitioned FSI simulations, is to define the exchange process and rules on how to combine solutions of the different components at the interface to couple the underlying equations of the different participants. The goal is to produce a suitable approximation of the monolithic solution. Coupling methods available in preCICE are investigated in more details in **Chap. 3** and in the following paragraph.

Partitioned vs. monolithic approaches In Sect. 1.1.1, preCICE is introduced as "a coupling library that facilitates the setup and execution of partitioned multi-physics simulation". The term *partitioned* (sometimes referred to as *staggered* [45]) describes the level of integration between the solvers involved in a simulation. In traditional partitioned setups, individual solvers are employed for each subproblem (e.g., heat transfer, CFD), as opposed to *monolithic* approaches, where the entire problem is modeled and solved within a single, unified solver. As explained in [100], a broad spectrum of approaches exists between these two extremes (see Fig. 1.4). In this context, preCICE itself has no notion of the underlying physics. It is only responsible for the numerical aspects of the coupling.

As shown in Fig. 1.4, partitioned approaches offer increased flexibility, whereas monolithic solutions are often considered more robust and computationally efficient. The aim of preCICE is to challenge this assumption. Specifically, preCICE implements a *black-box* coupling strategy, treating each solver as an independent entity. This means that only minimal internal information is exchanged, with communication between participants limited to input/output data and a few steering commands. While this significantly simplifies the integration of new solvers, it introduces additional complexity in the development of robust coupling strategies.

A further distinction exists between *explicit* (or *weak*) and *implicit* (or *strong*) coupling schemes. In explicit schemes, data exchange between solvers occurs only once per coupling time window. In contrast, implicit schemes perform repeated data exchanges within each time window until convergence at the interface is achieved. The term *time window* refers to the time interval between two converged states of the coupled system. For all practical purposes, since no sub-cycling is performed in the examples presented in this thesis, a time window corresponds to a single time step of the coupled simulation. In the context of implicit schemes, preCICE implements *acceleration* techniques for implicit coupling methods such as AITKEN under-relaxation or quasi-NEWTON methods to stabilize and speed up the convergence process (see Chap. 3 for more details). **Uni-directional** or **bi-directional** coupling between participants is available in preCICE.

Coupling can also be executed in either *serial* or *parallel* mode. In serial mode, solvers are executed sequentially, while in parallel mode, they run concurrently. This classification applies only to inter-participant execution; each solver may still implement internal (intra-solver) parallelism independently, as preCICE explicitly distinguishes solver- and simulation-level parallelism.

Communication protocols preCICE follows a peer-to-peer communication model. All coupled solvers are launched independently, and there is no central server-like instance orchestrating the simulation. Instead, each participant is responsible for its own execution and communication with the other participants. Indeed, using any central instance would be detrimental to the per-

Figure 1.4 – Partitioned vs. monolithic approaches to multi-physics simulations. *Source:* [100].

Figure 1.5 – Overview of the setup between two participants. *Source:* *preCICE official examples*⁸.

formance of communication protocols [25] as this introduces a bottleneck within the simulation setup, but this can also lead to high memory loads for large cases. As illustrated in **Fig. 1.5**, each participant invokes preCICE via its adapter, with the library running in the same processes as the solver itself. Mapping operations are performed within the execution environment of the participant to which they are assigned in the configuration file, as there is no server-like instance to steer the simulation or perform these operations. preCICE first establishes a list of connections between the MPI ranks of each participants. Each participant is launched within a separate MPI communicator with one or more dedicated MPI processes to which the MPI ranks refer here, even though the communication process is defined through TCP/IP. Once this step is done, communication between participants is performed in a fully parallel and asynchronous manner.

Communication between participants is typically handled via TCP/IP sockets, regardless of whether the simulation is running on a single machine or across distributed computing clusters, where processes of the participant may be dispatched over multiple hosts. preCICE also supports communication via MPI ports. However, this last option suffers from stability issues depending on the MPI implementation used (MPICH, OpenMPI, etc.), as it may lack some necessary features. While socket communication is the recommended default, the use of MPI may provide performance benefits in compute-intensive applications involving very large meshes and long simulation times, according to the official documentation for *communication protocols*⁷.

⁷<https://precice.org/configuration-communication.html>

⁸<https://github.com/precice/precice.github.io/tree/master/material>

1.2 Simulation setup and relevant software tools

The goal of this internship is to support the integration of preCICE into the simulation environment at PfS/HSU, as illustrated in **Fig. 1.6**. This section introduces the two solvers used in this work, FASTEST-3D and CalculiX, along with a brief overview of their capabilities. The numerical benchmarks and test cases employed in this work to validate the simulation setup are described later in **Sect. 1.3**. ASTE, a testing framework based on preCICE and used in the present study to automate the testing of various mapping methods is also presented later in **Sect. 2.3.1**.

Figure 1.6 – Overview of the coupled simulation setup used in this work. The fluid flow is computed using FASTEST-3D, while the structural response is predicted using CalculiX. The two solvers are coupled through preCICE v3.2.

1.2.1 FASTEST-3D

To predict the flow in the various test cases studied in this work, the in-house CFD solver FASTEST-3D[16, 37], initially developed at the University of Erlangen-Nürnberg is used. It is capable of solving the incompressible NAVIER-STOKES equations using various turbulence models (DNS, RANS, LES, etc.) within an Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian (ALE) framework [56]. This particular formulation aims to bridge the gap between the Lagrangian formulation, usually used in the context of CSD with finite-element methods, and the Eulerian formulation, which is commonly used in the context of fluid mechanics. The ALE formulation is often used in the context of fluid-structure interactions as it facilitates flow computations on moving grids. The integral form of the governing equations for a time-dependent domain is then given by:

$$\int_{S(t)} \rho_f (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}^{\text{grid}}) \cdot \mathbf{n} \, ds = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{V(t)} \rho_f \mathbf{u} \, dv + \int_{S(t)} \rho_f (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}^{\text{grid}}) \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n} \, ds = - \int_{S(t)} \underline{\underline{\tau}} \cdot \mathbf{n} \, ds + \int_{S(t)} p \mathbf{n} \, ds, \quad (1.2)$$

where \mathbf{u} is the flow velocity, \mathbf{u}^{grid} is the grid velocity at which the surface of a control volume is moving, ρ_f is the fluid density, $\underline{\underline{\tau}}$ is the stress tensor, p is the pressure, $S(t)$ is the surface of the control volume $V(t)$, and \mathbf{n} is the outward normal vector to the surface [15]. The equations are discretized using the finite-volume method on a curvilinear, block-structured, body-fitted grid with a collocated variable arrangement. Mesh adaptation techniques, which allows the grid to move as the structure around which the fluid flows deforms, are also implemented. These are

based on transfinite interpolation (TFI), inverse distance weighting (IDW), and radial basis functions (RBF). TFI is the fastest method, but it provides worse results than its counterparts. The theory behind each of these methods is given in [91]. To alleviate the drawbacks of each method to some extent, a hybrid method is also available. On block-structured grids, the hybrid mesh deformation methodology combines two elementary steps: one for the deformation of block interfaces where a costly method is used (IDW), and one for the inner points where TFI is applied.

The pressure and the viscosity are linearly interpolated to the cell faces, thus resulting in a second-order accurate scheme. The velocities used for the prediction of the convective fluxes on the cell faces are estimated using a second-order central scheme. To solve the NAVIER-STOKES equations, the time integration can be performed following two approaches:

- **Semi-implicit** [16] – A predictor-corrector scheme is used. For this purpose, the momentum equations are time-marched using a low-storage RUNGE-KUTTA scheme to derive an intermediate velocity field \mathbf{u}^* . Then the corrector step yields a divergence-free velocity field by solving a POISSON equation with a SIP⁹ solver.
- **Fully-implicit** [37] – A projection method based on either a backward differencing scheme or a CRANK-NICHOLSON scheme with a pressure correction algorithm of the SIMPLE¹⁰ type as a smoother is used.

The momentum interpolation technique of Rhie and Chow [82] is applied to predict the mass fluxes through the cell faces preventing unwanted oscillations. More details about the numerical methods implemented in FASTEST-3D can be found in [16, 37, 46]. The integration of preCICE into FASTEST-3D was introduced by G. DE NAYER.

1.2.2 CalculiX

CalculiX is a free and open-source finite-element analysis (FEA) application, whose development began in 1998. It features both a finite-element solver (CCX or CalculiX CrunchiX), developed by DHONDT [34], as well as a pre- and post-processor (CGX), developed by WITTIG [107]. Since its inception, the software has received strong support from MTU Aero Engines and has fostered an active online community. In addition to its FEA capabilities to solve structural problems, CalculiX supports other types of computations, such as electromagnetism, CFD, and heat transfer. However, these options will not be used in the present work. For a detailed overview of its capabilities, please refer to [the official overview of its FEM features](#)¹¹ by Guido DHONDT, as well as the book that covers much of the theory behind its implementation [35]. The source code of this software is available on its [official repository](#)¹². The version 2.20 of CGX and CCX will

⁹Strongly Implicit Procedure or STONE's method is an algorithm for solving a sparse linear system of equations based on an incomplete LU decomposition.

¹⁰Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure Linked Equation

¹¹https://www.dhondt.de/ov_calcu.htm

¹²<https://github.com/Dhondtguido/CalculiX>

Figure 1.7 – VON MISES stress distribution inside a turbine segment visualized using CGX. Taken from <http://www.dhondt.de/>.

be used for the numerical experiments. An official [preCICE adapter](#)¹³ exists for this version.

CalculiX supports a wide array of analysis types, including static (both linear and nonlinear with geometric and material nonlinearities), frequency analysis, and dynamic simulations (linear and nonlinear, with transient and steady-state harmonic loading), as well as buckling analysis. These capabilities make it suitable for a range of applications from simple linear elastic behavior to complex time-dependent, large deformation problems. Its element library is particularly rich, encompassing various dimensionalities and formulations. It includes 8-node and 20-node brick elements, tetrahedral and wedge elements (including incompressible formulations), 2D plane stress/strain and axisymmetric elements with different nodal configurations, as well as shell, membrane, beam, truss, and spring/dashpot elements with varying numbers of nodes. Both reduced and full integration schemes are available for high-order elements, and user-defined elements are supported for customization.

In addition to its robust analysis and solver capabilities, CalculiX supports an extensive range of material models, allowing accurate simulation of diverse physical behaviors. It includes linear elastic formulations for isotropic, orthotropic, and fully anisotropic materials, as well as nonlinear materials to name a few. Users can also define customized material behaviors. The loading options are equally comprehensive, ranging from basic concentrated forces and distributed pressures to more complex centrifugal, gravity, volumetric, thermal, and residual stress loadings. For boundary conditions, CalculiX enables simple single-point constraints and linear multi-point constraints, as well as advanced contact modeling such as tied contact and penalty-based

¹³<https://github.com/precice/calculix-adapter>

node-to-face or face-to-face interactions. It also provides rich kinematic control tools, allowing the enforcement of rigid-body motion, planar and linear constraints, mean rotations, and coupling or distributing conditions.

After the discretization of the weak form of CAUCHY’s first equation of motion, the system of equations to be solved is given by:

$$\mathbf{K} \mathbf{d} + \mathbf{M} \ddot{\mathbf{d}} = F, \quad (1.3)$$

where \mathbf{K} is the stiffness matrix, \mathbf{M} is the mass matrix, \mathbf{d} is the displacement vector, and F is the global force vector. Spatial discretization is done through finite elements. The spatial order of accuracy will depend on the type of elements chosen. The only time-stepping method available in CalculiX is the α -method (or Hilber-Hughes-Taylor method) [34, 55, 102]. It yields the following time integration scheme for the displacement \mathbf{d} , and velocity \mathbf{v} of a given material point P from time t_n to t_{n+1} :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{v}_{n+1} &= \mathbf{v}_n + \Delta t [(1 - \gamma) \mathbf{a}_n + \gamma \mathbf{a}_{n+1}] \\ \mathbf{d}_{n+1} &= \mathbf{d}_n + \Delta t \mathbf{v}_n + \frac{1}{2} \Delta t^2 [(1 - 2\beta) \mathbf{a}_n + 2\beta \mathbf{a}_{n+1}] \quad \text{with} \quad \begin{cases} \beta = \frac{1}{4} (1 - \alpha)^2 \\ \gamma = \frac{1}{2} - \alpha \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (1.4)$$

where \mathbf{a} denotes the corresponding acceleration. The parameter α controls high-frequency dissipation with its default value set to $\alpha = -0.05$ in CalculiX. This scheme is proven to be second-order accurate and unconditionally stable for $\alpha \in [-1/3, 0]$ if (γ, β) are expressed as shown in (1.4) for linear problems.

To integrate the resulting system of equations, CalculiX provides interfaces to several state-of-the-art direct sparse matrix solvers, including SPOOLES¹⁴, TAUCS¹⁵, PARDISO¹⁶, and PaStiX¹⁷, as well as an iterative solver with options for diagonal scaling and CHOLESKY preconditioning.

1.3 Numerical benchmarks

In this study, two well-known numerical benchmarks are used to validate the simulation setup and to perform the required tests. The first is the lid-driven cavity problem, which is a common benchmark in fluid dynamics [49], but can be modified to be used for FSI by introducing a flexible bottom. The second is the TUREK/HRON FSI3 test case. Both cases are described in detail below.

¹⁴<https://www.netlib.org/linalg/spooles/spooles.2.2.html>

¹⁵<https://github.com/sivantoleado/taucs/>

¹⁶<https://panua.ch/pardiso/>

¹⁷<https://solverstack.gitlabpages.inria.fr/pastix/>

1.3.1 Lid-driven cavity modified for FSI

The lid-driven cavity is a well-known numerical benchmark for viscous incompressible flow solvers [49]. Its original formulation consists of a square cavity with a lid moving at a constant velocity u , while the other walls are stationary. The fluid solver FASTEST-3D used in the context of the present study (see **Sect. 1.2.1**) has proven scalability on modern HPC architectures based on this benchmark [80]. Wall et al. [104] introduced a flexible bottom wall to this benchmark to make it suitable for FSI simulations in 2D. This version was then modified by Mok [74] for 3D cases. In addition to the moving lid, Spenke et al. [93] and others [6, 102] applied an inlet boundary condition (see **Fig. 1.8**) where a part of the left wall imposes a linear velocity profile, from $u_x = 0$ to $u_x = \hat{u}$, with \hat{u} the velocity imposed by the top lid following this time-varying profile:

$$\hat{u}(t) = 1 - \cos\left(\frac{2\pi t}{T_f}\right) \quad \text{with } T_f = 5 \text{ s.} \quad (1.5)$$

The outlet is located on the opposite wall to the inlet, with the static pressure set to zero over the whole patch. In the context of FSI simulations in general, the pressure field must be uniquely defined, because the actual pressure values are required at the fluid-structure interface to compute the structural responses. While pure fluid mechanical problems are defined with boundary conditions for the velocity field, the pressure is only determined up to an additive constant (which doesn't affect the flow). This non-uniqueness can cause solvers to fail and leads to inconsistencies when structural coupling is involved [61]. To resolve this, the reference *static* pressure must be fixed, commonly by setting it to zero in a chosen cell or enforcing a constant pressure at the outlet of the computational domain. These measures ensure that the resulting force on the coupling surface is computed correctly.

The fluid is defined by its density $\rho_f = 1.0 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and its dynamic viscosity $\mu_f = 0.01 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$. The bottom wall is defined by its density $\rho_s = 500 \text{ kg/m}^3$, its YOUNG's modulus $E_s = 250 \text{ N/m}^2$ and its POISSON's ratio $\nu = 0.0$ as defined in the original case. The flexible bottom has a thickness e of $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}$. The computational domain is a cube of size $1 \times 1 \times 1 \text{ m}^3$ discretized using a block-structured Cartesian mesh with equidistant hexahedral elements for the fluid and quadratic shell elements S8 [34] for the bottom lid. The REYNOLDS number for this case is defined as:

$$\text{Re} = \frac{\rho_f L \langle \hat{u} \rangle}{\mu_f} = 100$$

with $\langle \hat{u} \rangle = 1 \text{ m/s}$ the temporally averaged mean velocity over the top wall and $L = 1 \text{ m}$ the length of the cavity. **Fig. 1.8** shows a comparison between the original pure CFD lid-driven cavity test case [49] and the modified version used in the present work.

Varying mesh refinements are available for the fluid and structure grids, with 32, 64, 128, 256

Figure 1.8 – Comparison between the original lid-driven cavity test case from GHIA [49] (**left**) and the modified FSI version [93] used in the present work (**right**).

and 512 mesh elements per geometry side. A slice from the $64 \times 64 \times 64$ CVs mesh is shown in **Fig. 1.9**. During the experiments, the structure mesh is always less refined than the fluid mesh, as the structure problem requires less resolution than the fluid problem. As a throwback to **Fig. 1.3**, the meshes are non-conforming in this case. If the same mesh refinement is used for both, they would be matching and conforming.

Depending on the time-stepping scheme used for FASTEST-3D, the time step is set to 1×10^{-3} s for the semi-implicit method and 1×10^{-2} s for the implicit scheme for all available mesh refinements. CalculiX is set to use the same constant time step. The following boundary conditions are applied on the fluid:

- At the top wall, a time-varying velocity profile \hat{u} is set over its whole length \mathcal{S}_t . A section \mathcal{S}_i of the wall at $x = 0$ and a height of 0.125 m is a velocity inlet, which imposes a linear velocity profile from $u_x = 0$ to $u_x = \hat{u}$ as presented in **Fig. 1.10**.
- The outlet enforces a zero pressure condition on the static pressure over the whole patch \mathcal{S}_o .
- The side walls identified as \mathcal{S}_{sym} impose a symmetry condition. All other walls including the bottom lid Γ are no-slip walls.

For the bottom lid, the structure solver applies the following boundary conditions:

- For all points in contact with the symmetry walls identified as \mathcal{L}_{sym} , translation along the z -axis is blocked, as well as rotation around the x - and y -axes.

¹⁷This precision is important as CalculiX can use a dynamic time step. In this case, we set the time step to a constant value for the whole duration of the simulation.

Figure 1.9 – Example of block-structured Cartesian mesh used for the lid-driven cavity with flexible bottom. The mesh presented on this figure is extracted from a slice of the fluid mesh and it features 64×64 CVs at the coupling interface (262144 in the overall computational domain). It is split into 4 blocks with 65536 elements each. The structure mesh is not represented. The deformation observed here is the results of the simulation of the FSI problem under the boundary conditions presented in **Fig. 1.10**. All the meshes used for this case are coarsened version from the $512 \times 512 \times 512$ CVs mesh with different block sizes and distributions.

- The points in contact with no-slip walls identified as \mathcal{L}_c along the z -axis are blocked for all translations but all rotations are free.

Fig. 1.10 highlights the different boundary conditions applied in this case.

Figure 1.10 – Boundary conditions applied to the fluid and structure components of the simulation.

The choice of this benchmark is motivated by the simplicity of the overall geometry and ease of refinement of the mesh, which is ideal for scalability studies. It is also complex enough to stress the coupling and mapping setup. Note that the case defined with the above listed boundary conditions and simulated in the present work is the 2D case. That means that although a three-dimensional computational domain is taken into account, the flow and structured are assumed to remain two-dimensional. The purpose of this setup is to study the mapping and coupling procedure in preCICE and the current grid design allows to have a lot of exchange points in a relatively simple case.

1.3.2 Turek/Hron FSI3 test case

Turek and Hron [99] proposed a set of benchmark settings for the evaluation of computational methods for FSI problems. The configuration presented in **Fig. 1.11** is composed of a two-dimensional, laminar, viscous incompressible channel flow around a rigid and fixed cylinder to which a flexible elastic plate is attached. The test case is precisely defined in [99]. The computational domain is defined as follows:

- The domain has a length of $L = 2.5$ m and a height of $H = 0.41$ m.
- The center of the cylinder is located at $(x_c, y_c) = (0.2, 0.2)$ m. The cylinder has a radius $r = 0.05$ m.
- The elastic plate structure has a length of $\ell_s = 0.35$ m and a height of $h_s = 0.02$ m.
- The right bottom corner of the elastic plate is placed at $(0.6, 0.19)$ while its left end is fully attached to the fixed cylinder.

Figure 1.11 – Simulation setup for the TUREK/HRON FSI3 test case based on [99].

The fluid is defined by its density $\rho_f = 1.0$ kg/m³ and its kinematic viscosity $\nu_f = 1.0$ m²/s. The elastic plate is defined by its density $\rho_s = 1.0$ kg/m³, its POISSON'S coefficient $\nu_s = 0.4$ and its YOUNG'S modulus $E_s = 5.6 \times 10^6$ N/m². The REYNOLDS number is defined based on the diameter of the cylinder $d = 2r$ and the maximum velocity in the channel \hat{u} , which yields the following expression:

$$\text{Re} = \frac{2r\hat{u}}{\nu_f} = 200.$$

A parabolic velocity profile is prescribed at the inlet \mathcal{S}_i :

$$u(0, y) = 1.5 \hat{u} \times \frac{y(H - y)}{\left(\frac{H}{2}\right)^2} \quad \text{with} \quad \hat{u} = 1.2 \text{ m/s}. \quad (1.6)$$

The static outlet pressure is set to zero over the whole outlet patch \mathcal{S}_o . A no-slip condition is imposed on the other boundaries and the fluid-structure interface Γ . A symmetry condition is imposed at the lateral walls \mathcal{S}_{sym} . All boundary conditions are presented in **Fig. 1.12**.

All points of the flexible flap that are in contact with the cylinder have all rotations and translations blocked. The fluid domain is discretized using a block-structured Cartesian mesh with hexahedral elements, while the elastic plate is discretized using 8-nodes linear brick elements C3D8 [34]. The case is 2D with only one layer of elements in the z -direction. The following refinements are available for the structure mesh: $32 \times 2 \times 1$, $64 \times 4 \times 1$ and $128 \times 8 \times 1$ nodes. The fluid mesh is available in 3 levels of refinement: The coarse grid has around 27,000 cells, the

Figure 1.12 – View of the different boundary conditions applied to the fluid and structure components of the simulation.

medium grid has approximately 90,000 cells and finally, the fine grid has around 360,000 cells. A partial visualization of the coarse mesh is presented in **Fig. 1.13**.

Figure 1.13 – Partial visualization of the coarse mesh for the FSI3 benchmark case with approximately 27,000 cells. This figure does not show the structure mesh. The deformation observed is the result of the simulation of the FSI problem under the boundary conditions presented in **Fig. 1.12**. The mesh is refined in areas of interest in the fluid computational domain.

For low REYNOLDS numbers, the stability of the semi-implicit time-marching scheme used in FASTEST-3D is dominated by viscous effects, and therefore time steps for the fluid solver have to be increased accordingly, with $\Delta t_f = 1 \times 10^{-4}$ s, 5×10^{-5} s and 1×10^{-5} s for the coarse, medium and fine grids, respectively. When using the fully implicit time-stepping scheme, the time steps are adjusted to $\Delta t_f = 1 \times 10^{-3}$ s, 5×10^{-4} s and 5×10^{-4} s for the coarse, medium and

fine grids respectively. The structure solver applies a fixed time step equal to the corresponding fluid time step.

The choice of this test case is motivated by its well-established role as a benchmarking tool for FSI simulation setups [10, 16, 40, 66]. Since the elastic material and fluid have similar densities, the added-mass effect is particularly significant (see **Chap. 3** for more details on this phenomenon), thus making the coupling more challenging.

Mapping techniques implemented in preCICE

As stated in **Sect. 1.1**, the coupling of two or more solvers in preCICE requires a mapping of the data exchanged between them on their respective meshes. The fluid and structure meshes are in fact likely not to match or to even exhibit overlaps. This chapter reviews the mapping methods available in the preCICE framework and their respective implementation. This information is crucial for users to select the most suitable mapping method for their specific coupling scenarios with HPC performance and accuracy in mind. Numerical experiments using the ASTE framework (see **Sect. 2.3**) are also presented to illustrate the characteristics of the different mapping methods.

2.1 Overview of available mapping methods

2.1.1 Preliminary definitions

Definition 2.1.1 (Data Mapping). *Let \mathcal{M}_A and \mathcal{M}_B be the meshes of two participants A and B defined by their vertices as:*

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{M}_A &= \{\mathbf{x}_A^1, \mathbf{x}_A^2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_A^{N_A}\} \\ \mathcal{M}_B &= \{\mathbf{x}_B^1, \mathbf{x}_B^2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_B^{N_B}\}\end{aligned}$$

with $\mathbf{x}_A^i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and $\mathbf{x}_B^j \in \mathbb{R}^d$ their vertices, N_A and N_B the number of vertices in each mesh, and d the spatial dimension. The mapping of a vector representing a scalar data field \mathbf{f}_A defined on mesh \mathcal{M}_A to mesh \mathcal{M}_B is denoted as:

$$M_{AB} \mathbf{f}_A = \mathbf{f}_B$$

where M_{AB} is the mapping operator from mesh \mathcal{M}_A to mesh \mathcal{M}_B and \mathbf{f}_B is the mapped scalar data field on mesh \mathcal{M}_B .

When mapping a vector data field $\mathbf{F}_A = (\mathbf{f}_A^1, \mathbf{f}_A^2, \mathbf{f}_A^3)$ defined on mesh \mathcal{M}_A , the mapping operator is applied to each component \mathbf{f}_A^i . According to [67], a mapping method may be considered for

use in a black-box coupling environment such as preCICE if it satisfies the following properties:

- **Accuracy** – The error between the mapped values and the exact values should be small.
- **Computational efficiency** – The mapping method should be scalable with minimal computational cost and resource usage.
- **Black-box compatibility** – The mapping method should be compatible with any mesh type and topology, and should not require any information about the underlying solvers.

We can further distinguish between two types of mapping methods: *Consistent* and *conservative*. In the context of preCICE, these are referred to as *constraints* on the mapping operator. A consistent mapping method ensures the continuity of the data field across the coupling interface Ω . This is particularly useful when mapping intensive¹ quantities, or rigid-body displacements, as it guarantees that the meshes on either side of Ω , $\Omega_A \subset \mathcal{M}_A$ and $\Omega_B \subset \mathcal{M}_B$, remain compatible. In other words, the mapping does not introduce additional gaps or overlaps. However, as shown in [13], consistent mapping does not always ensure conservation of energy across Ω .

In contrast, a conservative method ensures that the integral or total value of the mapped physical quantity is preserved across the interface:

$$\int_{\Omega_A} \mathbf{f}_A \, dS = \int_{\Omega_B} \mathbf{f}_B \, dS,$$

where Ω_A and Ω_B denote the coupling interfaces of meshes \mathcal{M}_A and \mathcal{M}_B , respectively. This property is particularly important when mapping extensive² quantities that must be conserved, such as mass, momentum, energy, or force. The conservation property is independent of the mesh resolution, though it may come at the cost of local continuity, potentially introducing discontinuities in the mapped data field, unlike consistent mapping methods.

These arguments can be translated into mathematical properties of the mapping operator M_{AB} :

Definition 2.1.2 (Conservative and consistent mapping methods). *Let M_{AB} be a mapping operator from mesh \mathcal{M}_A to mesh \mathcal{M}_B as given in Def. 2.1.1. The mapping method is called **consistent** when the sum of the values for each row is equal to one. It is called **conservative** when the sum of the values for each column is equal to one.*

To illustrate the aforementioned properties of consistent mapping methods in term of continuity preservation, given the definition in Def. 2.1.1, if $\mathbf{f}_A^j = c$ for all $j \in \llbracket 1, N_A \rrbracket$, then $\mathbf{f}_B^i = c$ for all

¹An intensive property is a physical quantity whose value does not depend on the amount of substance which was measured. The temperature and the density of a system in thermal equilibrium are examples of intensive quantities.

²An extensive property is a physical quantity whose value is proportional to the size of the system it describes.

$j \in \llbracket 1, N_B \rrbracket$ if $\sum_{j \in \llbracket 1, N_B \rrbracket} M_{AB}^{i,j} = 1$ since

$$\mathbf{f}_B^i = \sum_{j=1}^{N_B} M_{AB}^{i,j} \mathbf{f}_A^j = \sum_{j=1}^{N_B} M_{AB}^{i,j} c = c \sum_{j=1}^{N_B} M_{AB}^{i,j} = c.$$

For a conservative mapping, as explained before, the total value should be the same on both sides of the interface. Only its distribution may change. Using the same notations, if $\sum_{i \in \llbracket 1, N_B \rrbracket} \mathbf{f}_B^i = \sum_{j \in \llbracket 1, N_A \rrbracket} \mathbf{f}_A^j$ is to be valid, then it is necessary for the following equation to hold for all values of \mathbf{f}_A :

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_B} \mathbf{f}_B^i = \sum_{i=1}^{N_B} \sum_{j=1}^{N_A} M_{AB}^{i,j} \mathbf{f}_A^j = \sum_{j=1}^{N_A} \mathbf{f}_A^j \sum_{i=1}^{N_B} M_{AB}^{i,j},$$

which leads to $\sum_{i \in \llbracket 1, N_B \rrbracket} M_{AB}^{i,j} = 1$. A direct consequence of this development is that *the transpose of a consistent mapping operator from A to B is a conservative mapping operator from B to A* [71].

In preCICE, another type of mapping is implemented under the name of *scaled-consistent mapping*. This follows the same principle as consistent mapping, but the output is rescaled by a coefficient to ensure the preservation of integrals. This type of mapping might be used for data such as pressure, where both the local data distribution and its integral value [71] (see [preCICE official documentation](#)³ on mapping configuration) should be preserved.

This section can be summarized as follows:

- **consistent** mapping constraint – should be used for intensive quantities, where the local distribution of values on the interface is important.
- **conservative** mapping constraint – should be used for extensive quantities, where the integral value over the coupling interface matters, but not its distribution across the interface.
- **scaled-consistent** mapping constraint – should be used for intensive quantities where both the local distribution and the integral over the coupling interface need to be preserved.

The notations used in the previous paragraphs offer some insights on the ideas behind the mapping methods, but they are a simplification of the actual mathematical development behind them [13, 48, 101]. Note that most mapping methods offer all three types of implementation, i.e., consistent, conservative and scaled-consistent mapping, except for Nearest Neighbor Gradient (see **Sect. 2.1.2**), for which a conservative version is not possible. The choice of the mapping setup according to the options given above depends on the type of data to be mapped and the requirements of the coupling scenario.

³<https://precice.org/configuration-mapping.html>

2.1.2 Projection-based mapping methods implemented in preCICE

preCICE implements several projection-based mapping methods that do not require a particular configuration setup, and are therefore relatively straightforward to use. These methods are often very cheap in terms of computational cost, but their accuracy is limited [25]. Abbreviations for each mapping method are introduced alongside their definition.

Nearest Neighbor mapping (NN) This method is the simplest and cheapest method available in preCICE. It is, however, the least accurate. In its consistent formulation, each vertex of the target mesh receives the value of the nearest vertex of the source mesh. When using its conservative version, each input vertex adds the value stored at its coordinates to the nearest output vertex to preserve the sum of all values through the interface. Some points of the output mesh may not receive a value, thus rendering the convergence of the receiving participant more complicated than in the case of a consistent mapping. The resulting mapping matrix M_{AB} for a consistent mapping is a boolean matrix defined as:

$$M_{AB}^{i,j} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{iff } \|\mathbf{x}_A^j - \mathbf{x}_B^i\|_2 = \min_{k \in \llbracket 1, N_B \rrbracket} \|\mathbf{x}_A^j - \mathbf{x}_B^k\|_2 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \forall (i, j) \in \llbracket 1, N_B \rrbracket \times \llbracket 1, N_A \rrbracket, \quad (2.1)$$

where each row i of the mapping matrix M_{AB} contains only one non-zero entry corresponding to the point of the source mesh that is closest to the point of the target mesh. If a conservative mapping is needed, then the transposed mapping M_{AB}^T can be used. See **Fig. 2.1** for a simple illustration of both the consistent and conservative formulation. A common problem to all projection-based methods such as *nearest-neighbor* or *nearest-projection* is the omission of nodes in case of non-uniform mesh sizes or concave geometries. This can lead to the omission of local data variation and therefore loss of conservativity [48].

Figure 2.1 – Illustration of the nearest-neighbor mapping method in its *consistent* and *conservative* versions. The blue points represent the source mesh, and the orange points represent the target mesh. The arrows indicate the mapping from the source to the target mesh.

Nearest Projection mapping (NP) This method uses geometric projections of a set of mesh *nodes* from one mesh onto a set of mesh *elements* of another mesh. Since it operates on elements, connectivity information is required. Note that preCICE automatically splits all mesh

elements, such as quadrangles, at the mapping interface into triangles.

For a consistent mapping between meshes \mathcal{M}_A and \mathcal{M}_B , the method uses the nodes of mesh \mathcal{M}_B and the elements of mesh \mathcal{M}_A . For each node $\mathbf{x}_B^i \in \mathcal{M}_B$, an orthogonal projection $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}_B^i)$ is computed onto \mathcal{M}_A . Depending on the closest mesh entity in \mathcal{M}_A , either a triangle, an edge, or a vertex, the value assigned to the node \mathbf{x}_B^i is obtained by using the data stored at $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}_B^i)$ after applying barycentric interpolation based on the vertices $(\mathbf{x}_A^j, \mathbf{x}_A^k, \mathbf{x}_A^l)$ of the mesh element if the projection lies within a triangle or linear interpolation if it falls on an edge. An example is given in **Fig. 2.2**. *Nearest-projection* mapping will switch to a *nearest-neighbor* mapping where it cannot find a mesh element to project onto or if no connectivity information is available [7, 48]. Let $\mathbf{x}_B^i \in \mathcal{M}_B$ with $i \in \llbracket 1, N_B \rrbracket$. The elements of the mapping matrix M_{AB} are then defined as:

- **Projection onto a triangle** defined by its vertices $(\mathbf{x}_A^j, \mathbf{x}_A^k, \mathbf{x}_A^l)$:

$$M_{AB}^{i,j} = \lambda_j, \quad M_{AB}^{i,k} = \lambda_k, \quad M_{AB}^{i,l} = \lambda_l, \quad \text{and} \quad M_{AB}^{i,m} = 0 \quad \forall m \neq j, k, l,$$

where $(\lambda_j, \lambda_k, \lambda_l) \in \mathbb{R}^+$ are the *barycentric coordinates* of \mathbf{x}_B^i in the triangle. These coefficients verify the relation $\lambda_j + \lambda_k + \lambda_l = 1$.

- **Projection onto an edge** defined by its endpoints $(\mathbf{x}_A^j, \mathbf{x}_A^k)$:

$$M_{AB}^{i,j} = \alpha, \quad M_{AB}^{i,k} = 1 - \alpha, \quad \text{and} \quad M_{AB}^{i,m} = 0 \quad \forall m \neq j, k,$$

where $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is the linear interpolation coefficient.

- **Nearest-neighbor assignment** to point \mathbf{x}_A^j :

$$M_{AB}^{i,j} = 1, \quad M_{AB}^{i,k} = 0 \quad \forall k \neq j.$$

Since the **NP** mapping requires additional information about the mesh structure, it is not compatible with the black-box principle of preCICE⁴. This method is, however, more accurate than the nearest-neighbor mapping method.

Nearest Neighbor Gradient mapping (NNG) The nearest-neighbor-gradient mapping method is an extension of its nearest-neighbor counterpart that incorporates additional gradient data to adjust the interpolation and improve the accuracy of the base method. This mapping technique is not compatible with the black-box principle of preCICE, as it requires supplementary gradient information about the data to be mapped. It was introduced by ARIGUIB during his bachelor thesis [7].

⁴NNG also violates this principle. This does not mean that the method is not implemented, but that it requires more information from the participant than what is normally expected.

Figure 2.2 – Illustration of the nearest-neighbor and nearest-projection mapping methods in their *consistent* formulation. The blue points represent the source mesh, and the orange points represent the target mesh. The arrows indicate the mapping from the source to the target mesh. Nearest-neighbor-gradient mapping follows the same principle as nearest-neighbor. The only difference is the addition of gradient data, so that for all $\mathbf{x}_B^i \in \mathcal{M}_B$, $f_B(\mathbf{x}_B^i) = f(\mathbf{x}_A^n) + (\mathbf{x}_B^i - \mathbf{x}_A^n) \cdot \mathbf{grad} f_A(\mathbf{x}_A^n)$ with \mathbf{x}_A^n the point associated to \mathbf{x}_B^i after the nearest-neighbor query. Based on [7, 67].

Let M_{AB} denote the mapping matrix as defined in **Def. 2.1.1**, with the same formulation as used for the nearest-neighbor mapping method, between \mathcal{M}_A and \mathcal{M}_B . The values at each vertex, denoted \mathbf{f}_A and \mathbf{f}_B , are complemented by gradient information $\mathbf{grad}(\mathbf{f}_A) \in \mathfrak{M}_{N_A, d}(\mathbb{R})$ at each vertex of the input mesh \mathcal{M}_A , where d is the spatial dimension of the mesh.

The following matrix $D_{AB} \in \mathfrak{M}_{N_B, N_A}(\mathbb{R})$ is defined as:

$$D_{AB}^{i,j} = \begin{cases} \|x_A^j - x_B^i\|_2 & \text{if } M_{AB}^{i,j} = 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \forall (i,j) \in \llbracket 1, N_B \rrbracket \times \llbracket 1, N_A \rrbracket$$

The mapping equation is then given by:

$$\mathbf{f}_B = M_{AB} \mathbf{f}_A + D_{AB} \mathbf{grad}(\mathbf{f}_A) \quad (2.2)$$

2.1.3 RBF-based mapping methods implemented in preCICE

To provide a more accurate mapping method, preCICE offers several **radial basis function** (RBF) based mapping methods. These methods are computationally more expensive than the projection-based methods, but they achieve better accuracy at the cost of higher complexity in terms of configuration.

2.1.3.1 Definitions and properties of RBF-based mapping methods

A radial basis function or RBF is a real-valued function, whose values only depend on the distance between its input and a given fixed point. A more detailed definition is given in **Def. 2.1.3**:

Definition 2.1.3 (Radial basis function). Let $\phi : \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, a continuous univariate function and $\|\cdot\| : \mathcal{V} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ a metric on a vector space \mathcal{V} . The function ϕ is called a **radial basis function** if its value depends only on the distance to a fixed center point $\mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{V}$, i.e., $\phi(r) = \phi(\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}\|)$ for all $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{V}$. An additional shape parameter $\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is added to the definition, so that $\phi(r) = \phi(\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}\|, \varepsilon)$. A further distinction is made between globally and locally supported functions. For the latter, a support radius is introduced, which is a distance $r_s \in \mathbb{R}^+$ such that $\phi(r) = 0$ for all $r > r_s$. In this case, the radial basis function is defined as $\phi(r) = \phi(\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}\|/r_s)$.

Further distinction is made between RBFs that are **positive definite** (see **Def. 2.1.4**) and those that are **conditionally positive definite** of order m (see **Def. 2.1.5**) [70]. This property is directly transferred to the *kernel matrix* $\mathbf{C} = \{\phi(\|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\|)\}_{(i,j) \in \llbracket 1, N \rrbracket^2}$ constructed from ϕ , which is **positive definite (PD)** or **conditionally positive definite (CPD)** of order m if the function ϕ itself possesses the corresponding property [70]. The matrix \mathbf{C} is also *symmetric*. A positive definite matrix is invertible, which ensures that the linear system arising in the RBF interpolation problem has a unique solution. In contrast, a conditionally positive definite kernel requires the addition of supplementary constraints to guarantee unique solvability of the interpolation problem.

The following definitions can be applied to radial basis functions by using the notation $\Phi(\mathbf{x}) = \phi(\|\mathbf{x}\|)$.

Definition 2.1.4 (Positive definite function [70]). Let $\Phi : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, a continuous and even function. Φ is said to be **positive definite (PD)** if for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and all $\mathbf{w} = \{w_i\}_{i \in \llbracket 1, n \rrbracket} \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \{0\}$ and any set of pairwise distinct centers $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$, the following holds:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_i w_j \Phi(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j) > 0 \quad .$$

Definition 2.1.5 (Conditionally positive definite function [9, 70]). Let $\Phi : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, a continuous and even function. Φ is said to be **conditionally positive definite (CPD)** of order m if for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, any set of pairwise distinct centers $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$ and all $\mathbf{w} = \{w_i\}_{i \in \llbracket 1, n \rrbracket} \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \{0\}$ that satisfy

$$\sum_{i=1}^n w_i q(\mathbf{x}_i) = 0$$

for all polynomials q of degree strictly less than m , the following holds:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_i w_j \Phi(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j) > 0 \quad .$$

When mapping data from mesh \mathcal{M}_A to mesh \mathcal{M}_B , an interpolant $\mathcal{I}(\mathbf{x})$ is built using the nodes

of the source mesh \mathcal{M}_A as centers $\mathbf{x}_A^i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ with the following definition [48, 91, 100]:

$$\mathcal{I}(\mathbf{x}) = \underbrace{\sum_{i=1}^{N_A} w_i \phi(\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_A^i\|, \varepsilon)}_{\mathbf{s}(\mathbf{x})} + \underbrace{\beta_0 + \boldsymbol{\beta}_\ell^T \cdot \mathbf{x}}_{\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x})}, \quad (2.3)$$

under the interpolation condition $\mathcal{I}(\mathbf{x}_A^i) = f(\mathbf{x}_A^i)$ for all $i \in \llbracket 1, N_A \rrbracket$. The component \mathbf{p} is a polynomial of degree 1, while \mathbf{s} is the *purely radial component* of the interpolant. The vector $\mathbf{w} = \{w_i\}_{i \in \llbracket 1, N_A \rrbracket}$ contains the *weights* of the interpolant. When dealing with PD RBF, the polynomial \mathbf{p} can be omitted, as the interpolation problem is uniquely solvable [9]. However, this is not the case for CPD RBF, where the polynomial \mathbf{p} is necessary to ensure the uniqueness of the solution [9]. In this case, further regularization conditions are imposed:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_A} w_i = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{i=1}^{N_A} w_i \mathbf{x}_A^i = \mathbf{0}. \quad (2.4)$$

For a PD RBF, solving the linear system $\mathbf{C} \mathbf{w} = \mathbf{f}$ with \mathbf{f} containing the values of the data field at the centers \mathbf{x}_A^i of the source mesh \mathcal{M}_A is sufficient to determine the weights \mathbf{w} . On the other hand, using a CPD RBF requires the adjunction of the polynomial component into the interpolation problem, thus introducing the following linear system [89]:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{C} & \mathbf{P} \\ \mathbf{P}^T & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{w} \\ \boldsymbol{\beta} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{f} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.5)$$

where the following notations are used:

- $\mathbf{w} = (w_1, \dots, w_{N_A})^T \in \mathbb{R}^{N_A}$, the weights of the pure radial component \mathbf{s} ;
- $\boldsymbol{\beta} = (\beta_0, \boldsymbol{\beta}_\ell^T)^T \in \mathbb{R}^{d+1}$, the coefficients of the polynomial component \mathbf{p} ;
- $\mathbf{C} = \{\phi(\|\mathbf{x}_A^i - \mathbf{x}_A^j\|)\}_{(i,j) \in \llbracket 1, N_A \rrbracket^2} \in \mathfrak{M}_{N_A}(\mathbb{R})$, the kernel matrix of ϕ ;
- $\mathbf{P} = \{1, \mathbf{x}_i^T\}_{i \in \llbracket 1, N_A \rrbracket} \in \mathfrak{M}_{N, d+1}(\mathbb{R})$;
- $\mathbf{f} = (f(\mathbf{x}_A^1), \dots, f(\mathbf{x}_A^{N_A}))^T \in \mathbb{R}^{N_A}$, the data field to be mapped from mesh \mathcal{M}_A .

The system given by **Eq. (2.5)** yields the coefficient vectors \mathbf{w} and $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ following this procedure [89]:

- The polynomial coefficients $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ are calculated by solving the least-squares problem:

$$\min_{\boldsymbol{\beta} \in \mathbb{R}^{d+1}} \|\mathbf{P} \boldsymbol{\beta} - \mathbf{f}\|_2. \quad (2.6)$$

- The coefficients \mathbf{w} are then calculated by solving the linear system:

$$\mathbf{C} \mathbf{w} = \mathbf{f} - \mathbf{P} \boldsymbol{\beta}. \quad (2.7)$$

In the context of preCICE, the polynomial component \mathbf{p} is not strictly necessary for PD RBF as the linear system $\mathbf{C}\mathbf{w} = f$ is uniquely solvable without it. However, it is included and the full system given by **Eq. (2.5)** is solved even for PD kernels, as it greatly improves the accuracy of the mapping and ensures that linear data variations, such as rigid-body displacements, are exactly captured [48, 89]. This renders the mapping by default *consistent*. This does not alter the solvability of the system without its polynomial component, as the full system as expressed in **Eq. (2.5)** is not merged together. To obtain the *conservative* version of the mapping, note that the transposed mapping operator M_{AB}^\top can be used [13, 67].

Fig. 2.3 illustrates the role of each component within the RBF interpolant. The plot on the left represents the reference data field on \mathcal{M}_A , the evaluation of the interpolant \mathcal{I}_f , the radial component \mathbf{s} and the polynomial component \mathbf{p} . The plot on the right shows the relative error between the evaluation of the interpolant and the reference data field for each point of the target mesh \mathcal{M}_B . It is defined as:

$$\left| \frac{\mathcal{I}_f(\mathbf{x}) - f(x)}{f(x)} \right| \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{M}_B \quad .$$

The radial component \mathbf{s} is responsible for reproducing the variations of the data field, while the polynomial component \mathbf{p} ensures that the interpolant matches the actual value of the data field at the centers of the source mesh by translating the radial component. In this example, **RBF-CTPS** yields a relatively constant polynomial term $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x})$, but this is not always the case.

preCICE offers several RBF functions: An exhaustive list is provided below, with the corresponding abbreviations that will be used in graphs throughout the report. In addition to the definition, the type of function support, i.e., the domain in which the function is non-zero, is also given. It can be either *local*, and therefore controlled by a parameter called `support-radius` in the `precice-config.xml` file, or *global*, which means that the function might be non-zero for a significant portion of the domain. Some functions also feature a *shape parameter* ε . r is used to denote the radius, i.e., the distance between a point \mathbf{x} and the center \mathbf{c} for a given RBF with $r(\mathbf{x}) = \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}\|$. \tilde{r} is used to denote the normalized radius with $\tilde{r}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{r(\mathbf{x})}{r_s}$. A visual overview of the different RBFs implemented in preCICE is given in **Fig. 2.4**.

- **Thin Plate Splines (RBF-TPS)** – This RBF has a *global* support and is defined as:

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{cases} r(\mathbf{x})^2 \log r(\mathbf{x}) & \text{if } r(\mathbf{x}) > 0 \\ \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} r^2 \log r = 0 & \text{if } r(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \end{cases} \quad .$$

- **Volume Splines (RBF-VS)** – This RBF has a *global* support and is defined as:

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = r(\mathbf{x}) \quad .$$

Figure 2.3 – Illustration of the role of each component within the RBF interpolant, which was constructed on a 1D grid with 100 points (\mathcal{M}_A) and then evaluated on a 1D grid with 50 points (\mathcal{M}_B). The RBF used here is **RBF-CTPS**($r_s \approx 0.53$) with the RASTRIGIN test function Eq. (2.19) as the data field (see Sect. 2.3).

- **Multiquadric (RBF-MQ)** – This RBF has a *global* support and it accepts a shape parameter $\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^+$. It is defined as:

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = \sqrt{r(\mathbf{x})^2 + \varepsilon^2} \quad .$$

- **Inverse Multiquadric (RBF-IMQ)** – This RBF has a *global* support and it accepts a shape parameter $\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^+$. This function is *positive definite* and has the following definition:

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{r(\mathbf{x})^2 + \varepsilon^2}} \quad .$$

- **Gaussian (RBF-G)** – This RBF can be used with a *global* support and it accepts a shape parameter $\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^+$. It is defined as:

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = \exp\left(-\varepsilon^2 r(\mathbf{x})^2\right) \quad .$$

However, the function can also be used with a *local* support, in which case the definition is [67]:

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = \exp\left(-\varepsilon^2 r(\mathbf{x})^2\right) + \underbrace{\exp\left(-\varepsilon^2 \min\left\{\sqrt{-\frac{\ln \text{decay}}{\varepsilon}}, r_s\right\}\right)}_{\Delta Y} \quad ,$$

Figure 2.4 – Overview of the different RBFs implemented in preCICE with the value used for their respective parameter. Note that **RBF-G** is configured with a global support. All functions are centered around $x = 0.5$.

where $\text{decay} = 1 \times 10^{-9}$. The function is set to zero for all points where

$$r > \min \left\{ \sqrt{-\frac{\ln \text{decay}}{\varepsilon}}, r_s \right\} .$$

- **Compact Thin Plate Splines C2 (RBF-CTPS)** – This RBF has a *local* support and it is *positive definite*. For $r = 0$, the function evaluates to its limit, so that $\phi(0) = 1$. It is defined as:

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = 1 - 30 \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x})^2 - 10 \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x})^3 + 45 \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x})^4 - 6 \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x})^5 - 60 \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x})^3 \log \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x}) .$$

- **WENDLAND [106] Compact Polynomials C0-C8 (RBF-WCn)** – This class of RBF has a *local* support and all WENDLAND compact polynomials C0-8 are *positive definite*. They are defined as follows:

$$\text{RBF-WC0} - \phi(\mathbf{x}) = (1 - \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x}))^2$$

$$\text{RBF-WC2} - \phi(\mathbf{x}) = (1 - \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x}))^4 (4 \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x}) + 1)$$

$$\text{RBF-WC4} - \phi(\mathbf{x}) = (1 - \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x}))^6 (35 \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x})^2 + 18 \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x}) + 3)$$

$$\text{RBF-WC6} - \phi(\mathbf{x}) = (1 - \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x}))^8 (32 \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x})^3 + 25 \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x})^2 + 8 \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x}) + 1)$$

$$\text{RBF-WC8} - \phi(\mathbf{x}) = (1 - \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x}))^{10} (1287 \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x})^4 + 1350 \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x})^3 + 630 \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x})^2 + 150 \tilde{r}(\mathbf{x}) + 15)$$

Unless stated otherwise, all functions that are not *positive definite* are only *conditionally positive definite* (see **Def. 2.1.5**). For a RBF using a local support, the function is considered to be

Figure 2.5 – Illustration of the influence of the support radius r_s and the shape parameter ε on the RBF. All functions are centered around $x = 0.5$.

non-zero if its value is above a threshold set to 1×10^{-9} .

It is important to note that the support radius and the shape parameter do not represent the same concept. The support radius r_s has a straightforward physical interpretation: It defines the maximum distance from the center of the RBF beyond which the function evaluates to zero, making it easy to visualize it as a radial cut-off in space. In contrast, the shape parameter ε is a scaling factor that affects the flatness or peakedness of the RBF. It governs how rapidly the function decays to a constant, flat state, but it does not correspond to a physical distance and cannot be directly represented on a geometric surface. An example using **RBF-CTPS** and **RBF-MQ** for different values of their respective parameters is provided in **Fig. 2.5** to illustrate the role of the support radius and shape parameter on the shape of the RBF. A small support radius concentrates the information of the function in a small domain, while a large shape parameter will simply flatten the function. The shape parameter strongly depends on the function that uses it, while a value of the support radius can be more easily used across multiple RBFs. The value of both parameters is closely linked to the characteristic length of the problem being solved.

The choice of the support radius or shape parameter for a given RBF has a significant impact on the interpolant quality as shown in **Fig. 2.6**. The maximum relative error computed from the evaluation of the test function and the interpolant on the target mesh varies significantly with the value of both parameters. Note that the optimal value for the shape parameter and the support radius do not lie in the same order of magnitude. The optimal value for the shape

Figure 2.6 – Influence of the support radius r_s and the shape parameter ϵ on the quality of the RBF interpolation. The input mesh, upon which the RBF interpolant is built, is a uniform 1D grid between 0 and 1 with 100 points \mathcal{M}_A , while the output mesh \mathcal{M}_B is a uniform 1D grid between 0 and 1 with 50 points. The data field used for the interpolation is the RASTRIGIN test function **Eq. (2.19)**. The RBF interpolant is built using **RBF-CTPS** and **RBF-MQ**.

parameter will also vary greatly between the RBF that require it. For instance, a Gaussian RBF as defined previously and using the same setup as **Fig. 2.6** will yield a shape parameter optimal between 1 and 10.

Flatter basis functions such as **RBF-MQ** and **RBF-IMQ** offer better accuracy on smooth data, but at the cost of a worse conditioning of the kernel matrix \mathbf{C} . Both the shape parameter and the support radius have a strong influence on the computational cost of the mapping. Indeed both parameters have a direct influence on the sparsity of the kernel matrix \mathbf{C} and its condition number $\kappa(\mathbf{C})$ as shown for **RBF-CTPS** in **Fig. 2.7** and for **RBF-MQ** in **Fig. 2.8**. On these figures, the actual kernel matrix elements are plotted. Decreasing the support radius will increase the sparsity of the matrix and concentrate the information on the diagonal. Note that a diagonal kernel has an excellent condition number, but the interpolant quality is suboptimal as there is not enough information to construct a good approximation [89]. Increasing the shape parameter on the other hand will shift information outside the diagonal. **Fig. 2.6** highlights these remarks. These two parameters require a separate optimization procedure to choose an optimal value as they do not have the same effect on the interpolation problem. Choosing a value that is not appropriate for the problem at hand can increase the likelihood of the underlying solvers to fail at solving the systems **Eq. (2.6)** and **Eq. (2.7)** due to ill-conditioning.

2.1.3.2 Partition of Unity for RBF mapping

It is difficult and time-consuming to choose adequate parameters (support radius or shape parameter) to decrease mapping errors or ill-conditioning issues as these parameters heavily depend

Figure 2.7 – Visualization of the kernel matrix \mathbf{C} for **RBF-CTPS** with $r_s = 0.1$ (left) and $r_s = 1.0$ (right). The mesh used to generate the kernel matrix is a uniform 1D grid between 0 and 1 with $N = 50$ points. The color scale represents the value of \mathbf{C}_{ij} for $(i, j) \in \llbracket 1, N \rrbracket^2$.

Figure 2.8 – Visualization of the kernel matrix \mathbf{C} for **RBF-MQ** with $\varepsilon = 1.0$ (left) and $\varepsilon = 0.01$ (right). The mesh used to generate the kernel matrix is a uniform 1D grid between 0 and 1 with $N = 50$ points. The color scale represents the value of \mathbf{C}_{ij} for $(i, j) \in \llbracket 1, N \rrbracket^2$.

on several parameters, such as the basis function or the input and output meshes for instance. Let Ω be the mapping interface, preCICE offers a *partition of unity* (PU) approach to RBF mapping [89] to reduce the influence of the RBF parameters on the simulation setup and improve computational efficiency on large problems. In this context, a *partition of unity*, which gives the method its name, is a set of *continuous, non-negative, compactly supported* functions Ψ from Ω to $[0, 1]$ such that the following holds:

- For every $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega$, there exists a neighborhood that intersects with a *finite* number of supports⁵ $\mathcal{S} = \{\text{supp}(\psi)\}_{\psi \in \Psi}$.
- The sum of the functions in Ψ is equal to 1, i.e.:

$$\sum_{\psi \in \Psi} \psi(\mathbf{x}) = 1 \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in \Omega \quad . \quad (2.8)$$

The mapping interface Ω can be divided into M overlapping domains or clusters $\{\Omega_k\}_{k \in \llbracket 1, M \rrbracket}$ so that:

$$\Omega \subseteq \bigcup_{k=1}^M \Omega_k \quad .$$

Let $\Psi = \{\psi_k\}$ be the set of PU functions and their corresponding domains Ω_k for $k \in \llbracket 1, M \rrbracket$. A local approximant \mathcal{I}_k^f is constructed on each subdomain Ω_k . A global solution \mathbf{I}_f is then obtained by combining the local approximants weighted by the PU functions:

$$\mathbf{I}_f(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{k=1}^M \psi_k(\mathbf{x}) \mathcal{I}_k^f(\mathbf{x}) \quad . \quad (2.9)$$

In preCICE, the partition of unity is implemented using SHEPARD's method [89]. The RBF **WC2** is used as a starting point to form the set of PU functions, since it is continuous, positive and compactly supported. We denote **WC2** as \mathbf{wc}_k in the following when it is defined on a cluster Ω_k with a support radius $r_{s,k}$ so that $\text{supp}(\mathbf{wc}_k) \subset \Omega_k$ with the center \mathbf{c}_k , the center of the cluster Ω_k . The PU function set is then defined as:

$$\Psi = \left\{ \psi_k = \frac{\mathbf{wc}_k}{\sum_{k=1}^M \mathbf{wc}_k} \right\}_{k \in \llbracket 1, M \rrbracket} \quad . \quad (2.10)$$

The scaling by $\sum_{k=1}^M \mathbf{wc}_k$ ensures that the partition of unity condition given by **Eq. (2.8)** is satisfied. The global interpolant \mathbf{I}_f is then used to evaluate the data field at any point $\mathbf{x}_B^i \in \mathcal{M}_B$ of the output mesh.

This method requires a clustering step before performing the actual computation of the interpolant. preCICE uses an equally spaced clustering within a cubic bounding box around the

⁵In this context, the support of a real-valued function f is the subset of the function domain of elements that are not mapped to zero.

mapping interface Ω with the same cluster radius r_M and the same RBF configuration for all clusters. The user can configure the target number of points per cluster N_M and the relative overlap between clusters $c_s \in [0, 1[$ in the `precice-config.xml` file. These parameters are then transformed into the cluster radius r_M [89]. The clustering process is illustrated in **Fig. 2.9** for a 2D case. Equally spaced clusters are created within the bounding box. All empty clusters are discarded and the remaining clusters have their centers projected onto points in the input mesh that are part of the mapping interface. The clusters are then used to define the PU functions as described above. Note that the PU-RBF method will fail if the coupling meshes have not sufficiently matching geometries. The preCICE documentation does not provide a criterion to define what is a sufficiently matching geometry, but it is recommended that overlap and gaps are reduced to a minimum. Mesh elements should not vary in number or size too much across the interface. The main advantage of the PU method is that it splits the global interpolation problem into several smaller problems. This reduces the conditioning issues encountered with the full kernel matrix \mathbf{C} evaluated on the entire computational domain [89].

Figure 2.9 – Illustration of the clustering algorithm used in preCICE. The clustering algorithm starts by creating equally spaced clusters within a bounding box around the mapping interface Ω . After discarding empty clusters, the centers of the remaining clusters are projected onto the mapping interface. They are then used to define the partition of unity functions. Taken from [89].

2.1.3.3 Choice of support radius and shape parameter

The choice of these two parameters depending on the RBF used is crucial as explained before. preCICE might simply report an error if these parameters lead to poorly conditioned systems and the underlying solvers fail to converge. There is a need for guidelines on how to choose these parameters, as they are not always intuitive.

Choice of support radius for RBF-WC n and RBF-CTPS Among the RBFs available in preCICE, only the **RBF-WC n** , the **RBF-CTPS** and optionally **RBF-G** require a support radius, as they have a local support. Looking back at **Fig. 2.7**, the support radius influences the density of the matrix \mathbf{C} and its condition number $\kappa(C)$. A large support radius leads to a

denser matrix, which can increase the computational cost, but [12] explains that a large support radius leads to more accurate solutions. preCICE recommends to use a support radius that covers only a handful of vertices in radial direction. The final choice should be motivated by the specific problem at hand, the mesh resolution, and the desired accuracy. It should be large enough to cover a limited number of vertices, but small enough to not degrade the conditioning of the system too much. By default, the partition of unity method implemented in preCICE uses around 50 vertices per cluster. This is a good order of magnitude to choose a support radius. A rule of thumb for a first guess could be $r_s \approx K \times \ell_c$ with K the desired number of vertices in a given direction and ℓ_c a characteristic mesh length, like for instance the minimal mesh width. When using the partition of unity method, the support radius should be chosen close to the equivalent cluster radius computed from the number of vertices per cluster, so that the interpolation uses as much information as possible from the surrounding vertices.

Choice of shape parameter for RBF-IMQ, RBF-MQ and RBF-G Only the **RBF-MQ**, the **RBF-IMQ** and the **RBF-G** require a shape parameter ε . This is a topic of interest as much as the choice of support radius, as it also has a strong influence on the conditioning of the system given by **Eq. (2.5)** as shown in **Fig. 2.8**.

HARDY [54] suggested the use of the following criterion for interpolation in \mathbb{R}^2 using multiquadric or inverse multiquadric RBFs:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{1}{0.815 d} \quad \text{with} \quad d = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \min \{ \|x_i - x_j\|, j \in \llbracket 1, N \rrbracket \}. \quad (2.11)$$

FRANKE [47] on the other hand suggested using the following criterion for the shape parameter:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{0.8\sqrt{N}}{D} \quad , \quad (2.12)$$

where D is the diameter of the smallest circle containing all data points and N is the number of data points. While these methods are simple to implement, they might not scale correctly to complex problems.

An analytical method was proposed by RIPPA [83] to determine the shape parameter for multiquadric, inverse-multiquadric and Gaussian RBFs. A simple but costly algorithm can be derived from his work.

Let $\mathcal{M} = \{x_i\}_{i \in \llbracket 1, N \rrbracket}$ be a set of points in \mathbb{R}^d , ϕ a radial basis function and f the function to be interpolated on \mathcal{M} . Given a purely radial interpolant \mathbf{s} as defined in **Eq. (2.3)** with the same notations, the weights \mathbf{w} are determined by solving the linear system $\mathbf{C} \mathbf{w} = \mathbf{f}$. Let $k \in \llbracket 1, N \rrbracket$ and $\mathcal{M}^{[k]}$ is the set of points in \mathcal{M} excluding x_k . A truncated interpolant $\mathbf{s}^{[k]}$ is constructed

upon $\mathcal{M}^{[k]}$ with the weights $\mathbf{w}^{[k]}$ computed using the matrix $\mathbf{C}^{[k]}$, which is \mathbf{C} without its k -th row and column. The truncated interpolant is then defined as:

$$\mathbf{s}^{[k]}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq k}}^N w_i^{[k]} \phi(\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_i\|) \quad . \quad (2.13)$$

This allows the creation of an error vector \mathcal{E} defined as:

$$\mathcal{E} = \begin{bmatrix} E_1 \\ \vdots \\ E_k \\ \vdots \\ E_N \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_1 - \mathbf{s}^{[1]}(\mathbf{x}_1) \\ \vdots \\ f_k - \mathbf{s}^{[k]}(\mathbf{x}_k) \\ \vdots \\ f_N - \mathbf{s}^{[N]}(\mathbf{x}_N) \end{bmatrix} \quad . \quad (2.14)$$

A cost function $\mathbf{c} : \varepsilon \rightarrow \|\mathcal{E}\|$ is then defined, which allows to determine the optimal shape parameter ε^* as the solution of the following optimization problem:

$$\varepsilon^* = \arg \min_{\varepsilon} \|\mathcal{E}\| \quad , \quad (2.15)$$

with $\|\cdot\|$ the L_1 or L_2 -norm. This method is rather costly. To reduce the number of operations, RIPPA [83, 111] showed that the method can be simplified to a simple formula to compute the error vector:

$$\mathcal{E} = \left\{ \frac{c_k}{\text{diag}(\mathbf{C}^{-1})} \right\}_{k \in \llbracket 1, N \rrbracket} \quad , \quad (2.16)$$

where $\text{diag}(\mathbf{C}^{-1})$ represents the vector containing the diagonal elements of the inverse of the kernel matrix \mathbf{C} . c_k is the k -th element of the vector $\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{C}^{-1} f$. The procedure remains the same, but the computational cost is reduced significantly. According to [83], this changes the complexity of the algorithm from $\mathcal{O}(N^4)$ to $\mathcal{O}(N^3)$ depending on the algorithm used to compute the inverse of the kernel matrix. The procedure proposed by RIPPA is based on the *LOOCV* (*Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation*) method, which is a common model validation technique in machine learning and statistics. For **RBF-G**, the support radius can be expressed as $r_s = m \times h_{\max}$, where m is a integer representing the desired number of points in a given direction to define the support of the function and h_{\max} is the maximum mesh width of the input mesh \mathcal{M}_A . Based on this expression, the corresponding shape parameter can be computed as [67]:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\sqrt{-\log d}}{m \times h_{\max}} \quad . \quad (2.17)$$

This ensures that the RBF function decays to d (typically $d = 10^{-9}$) within m neighboring vertices from its center \mathbf{c} using the notations in **Def. 2.1.3**.

2.1.4 Other available mapping methods

In addition to the methods described above, preCICE also includes other mapping methods, such as:

- **Linear Cell Interpolation (LCI)** – This method is used for volumetric coupling where the coupling interface is a region of space rather than a surface. It was introduced for the master thesis of MARTIN [71]. Since volumetric coupling will not be used in the context of the present thesis, this method will not be described in detail here. The interested reader is referred to [71] for more information.
- **Geometric multiscale mapping** – This collection of methods allows to map data from dimensionally heterogeneous meshes, i.e., from a 3D mesh to a 1D mesh for instance. This is an experimental feature of preCICE since V3.0.0 and therefore it will not be used further in the present report. The interested reader is referred to the [official preCICE documentation](#)⁶ for more information.

2.1.5 Convergence properties of the mapping methods

Definition 2.1.6 (Order of accuracy). *Let f be an arbitrary function and f_h its approximation, with h being a discretization parameter. The **order of accuracy** quantifies the convergence rate of the numerical approximation. An approximation method is said to be of order p if there exists a constant $C > 0$ for $h \rightarrow 0$ such that:*

$$\varepsilon_p(h) = \|f - f_h\|_\infty \leq C h^p \quad .$$

Using big-O notation, this can be expressed as:

$$\varepsilon_p(h) = \|f - f_h\|_\infty = \mathcal{O}(h^p) \quad .$$

According to [7, 67], the order of accuracy of the mapping methods implemented in preCICE is as follows:

- **Nearest Neighbor mapping (NN)** – This method is first-order accurate, i.e., $\mathcal{O}(h)$ [7].
- **Nearest Projection mapping (NP)** – This method is second-order accurate, i.e., $\mathcal{O}(h^2)$ in terms of mesh spacing, but first-order accurate, i.e., $\mathcal{O}(\delta)$ in term of separation distance δ between meshes [7] if the mapping interface has gaps between the input and output meshes.
- **Nearest Neighbor Gradient mapping (NNG)** – This method is second-order accurate, i.e., $\mathcal{O}(h^2)$ [7].

⁶<https://precice.org/configuration-mapping.html>

- **RBF mapping** – LINDNER[67] provides an overview of the different results on RBF convergence properties. In general, the order of accuracy is between first and second-order, i.e., $\mathcal{O}(h)$ to $\mathcal{O}(h^2)$ or even higher. This depends strongly on the choice of the radial basis function, the support radius, and the shape parameter [67].

This can be tested in practice by performing a convergence study, i.e., by comparing the mapping error for different mesh spacings h and checking if the error decreases as expected. The interested reader is referred to [25] for an example of such a convergence study. Similar results are provided in **Sect. 2.3**.

2.2 Review of the mapping implementation in preCICE

In this section, a review of the implementation of the mapping methods that were previously described is provided. An overview of the configuration options available to the user is given in **Sect. 2.2.1** followed by a quick review of the details behind the actual implementation of the mapping methods in **Sect. 2.2.2**.

2.2.1 User-level configuration options for mapping methods

Most of the information provided in this section is based on the official documentation of preCICE for the [configuration of the mapping methods](#)⁷. All configuration options are defined through the `precice-config.xml` file. A simple example taken from the documentation is provided in **Lst. 2.1**. A participant, as defined in **Chap. 1**, may provide or receive one or more meshes through the tags `provide-mesh` and `receive-mesh`.

```
<participant name="MySolver1">
  <provide-mesh name="MyMesh1"/>
  <receive-mesh name="MyMesh2" from="MySolver2"/>
  <read-data name="Displacements" mesh="MyMesh1"/>
  <write-data name="Forces" mesh="MyMesh1"/>
  <mapping:nearest-neighbor direction="read" from="MyMesh2" to=
    "MyMesh1" constraint="consistent"/>
  <mapping:nearest-neighbor direction="write" from="MyMesh1" to
    ="MyMesh2" constraint="conservative"/>
  ...
</participant>

<participant name="MySolver2">
  <provide-mesh name="MyMesh2"/>
```

⁷<https://precice.org/configuration-mapping.html>

```
<read-data name="Forces" mesh="MyMesh2"/>
<write-data name="Displacements" mesh="MyMesh2"/>
...
</participant>
```

Listing 2.1 – Example of a mapping configuration in the `precice-config.xml` file.

A mesh itself is defined through the tag `mesh`. The data fields that are provided by this mesh are defined through the tag `use-data`. Note that a mesh may provide multiple data fields as seen in **Lst. 2.2**.

```
<mesh name="MyMesh1" dimensions="3">
  <use-data name="Displacements"/>
  <use-data name="Forces"/>
</mesh>
```

Listing 2.2 – Example of a mesh definition in the `precice-config.xml` file.

The tags `read-data` and `write-data` in the definition of a participant are used to specify which data fields are required by the participants on which they are defined and which data fields should be written by the participant itself. Any participant can read or write multiple data fields. For instance, in **Lst. 2.1**, the participant `MySolver1` requires `displacements` data to perform its computations and it will output `forces` data. All data defined in both `read-data` and `write-data` should be available on the meshes defined by a `provide-mesh` tag in the participant.

The `mapping` tag is used to specify the mapping methods to be used. It connects a `provide-mesh` (where data is written by the participant) and a `receive-mesh` (where data is read by the participant), and specifies a direction, which can be `read` or `write` in addition to a constraint (`consistent`, `conservative`, etc.). **Fig. 2.11** is obtained using the [configuration visualization tool](#)⁸. It illustrates the configuration setup in **Lst. 2.1**. The difference between a *read* and *write* mapping is the timing of the execution of the mapping operation:

- A *read* mapping is executed before the participant actually uses the data stored on the mesh defined through `provide-mesh` to perform its computations. For instance, in **Fig. 2.11**, the `Displacements` data field is received from the mesh `MyMesh2` defined in the corresponding `receive-mesh` tag. It is then mapped to the mesh `MyMesh1` before the participant `MySolver1` reads it on `MyMesh1`.
- A *write* mapping is executed once the participant has written data to the mesh defined using `provide-mesh`. For instance, `MySolver1` writes the `Forces` data field to the mesh `MyMesh1`. This data is then mapped to the mesh `MyMesh2` defined in the corresponding `receive-mesh` tag.

⁸<https://precice.org/tooling-config-visualization.html>

To clarify the distinction between *read* and *write* mappings, **Fig. 2.10** illustrates the sequence of operations for both cases. In this work, FASTEST-3D computes the fluid forces acting on the structure and stores them on the `Fluid_Centers` mesh, while CalculiX computes the structural displacements, which FASTEST-3D requires to deform the fluid mesh (`Fluid_Nodes` and `Fluid_Centers`). As shown in **Fig. 2.10**, a *write* mapping transfers data to the mesh of another participant after it has been written to the local mesh, whereas a *read* mapping retrieves data from another participant before it is read from the local mesh.

Figure 2.10 – Illustration of the difference between a *read* and a *write* mapping operation.

As shown in **Fig. 2.11**, note that the mesh `MyMesh2` is also made available to the participant `MySolver1`. In this context, the different meshes are actually the vertices located on the coupling interface between the participants. The mesh provided by `MySolver2` undergoes a repartitioning procedure when it is transferred to `MySolver1`. Indeed, participants may run on a different number of processes, across which the mesh is split. Therefore, it is necessary to repartition the mesh to distribute the vertices of the mesh `MyMesh2` across the processes of `MySolver1`. This is done by preCICE internally through a filtering operation and was implemented during the thesis of UEKERMANN [100]. This procedure is also presented on **Fig. 2.10**. More details on this operation is found in Chapter 4 of [100].

The configuration as explained above is valid for all projection-based mapping methods, such as `NN`, `NP`, `NNG`. However, for RBF-based mapping methods, the `mapping` tag has to be extended. Kernel mapping methods in preCICE include two variants since the release of preCICE

Figure 2.11 – Example of a mapping configuration in preCICE. The participant MySolver1 provides the mesh MyMesh1 and receives the mesh MyMesh2 from MySolver2, which provides the mesh MyMesh2 and receives the mesh MyMesh1. Based on the preCICE documentation.

3.0. The user can choose between global RBF method under the tag `rbf-global-...` and the PU method `rbf-pum-direct`. The `rbf-global-...` methods construct a global interpolant based on the vertices of either the from or to mesh, depending on the constraint (`consistent` or `conservative`). There are two solvers for this method: `rbf-global-direct`, which uses dense linear algebra (typically with [Eigen](https://eigen.tuxfamily.org/index.php?title=Main_Page)⁹) and solves the system via a matrix decomposition (Cholesky or QR, depending on basis-function definiteness), and `rbf-global-iterative`, which uses [PETSc](https://petsc.org/release/)¹⁰ for sparse, iterative, fully MPI-parallel solving. This last version is recommended only for compactly supported basis functions with limited support radius such as **RBF-WC n** . The `rbf-pum-direct` method is the implementation of the method explained in [Sect. 2.1.3.2](#). As explained before, it addresses scalability by partitioning the domain into small, overlapping clusters, solving the interpolation locally within each cluster (again using Eigen and dense solvers), and blending the results using a partition of unity. This method is fully MPI-parallel and generally outperforms the global variants in large-scale problems. However, it assumes geometrically compatible meshes and may perform poorly if there are large gaps between them. `rbf-pum-direct` is better suited for large and distributed problems, while `rbf-global` methods offer precise control at smaller scales or in serial execution. The execution backend (CPU or GPU) can be specified through the tag `executor`. GPU-based acceleration requires preCICE to be compiled with explicit support for these functionalities. Note that preCICE provides the alias `rbf` to let the library choose which option is best suited for the problem. A typical configuration for RBF mapping methods is shown in [Lst. 2.3](#).

```
<mapping:rbf direction="read" from="MyMesh2" to="MyMesh1"
  constraint="consistent">
  <basis-function:thin-plate-splines/>
</mapping:rbf>
```

Listing 2.3 – Example of a RBF mapping configuration in the `precice-config.xml` file.

⁹https://eigen.tuxfamily.org/index.php?title=Main_Page

¹⁰<https://petsc.org/release/>

Additional parameters can be specified within the `<basis-function:...>` tag depending on the basis function used. As an example, the support radius for **RBF-CTPS** can be specified using the `support-radius` attribute, while for **RBF-MQ**, the shape parameter can be specified using the `shape-parameter` attribute. The partition of unity method lets the user choose the number of vertices per cluster and the overlap between clusters to be used when performing the clustering step as explained in **Sect. 2.1.3.2**. For more information on all the options available, please refer to the [XML reference documentation](#)¹¹.

An important point to take into account is that for a participant in a sequential mode, any combination of `read/write-consistent/conservative` is valid. For a participant running in parallel, only `read-consistent` in combination with `write-conservative` is possible. For any other combinations, like for instance `read-consistent` and `write-consistent`, the mapping declaration should be split and declared under another participants as explained in the documentation. The reason behind this requirement is explained in [100]. This is due to internal repartitioning of the meshes within preCICE, where invalid combinations would lead to a non-unique mapping.

2.2.2 Implementation of the mapping methods in preCICE

The mapping methods are directly implemented in the preCICE library within the `mapping` package, located inside the `src` directory of the source code. Like each package, it follows the following structure:

- **config** – Contains the logic to use the options defined in the configuration file located at the root of any preCICE project, `precice-config.xml`.
- **device** – Contains device code that relies on vendor specific libraries such as [Nvidia CUDA](#)¹² and [AMD ROCm](#)¹³ for running computations on GPGPUs. It also contains methods relying on the [Ginkgo](#) library.
- **impl** – Contains implementations of several utility functions that are used across multiple mapping methods.
- **tests** – Contains unit tests for the mapping methods.

The logic of the mapping methods is mostly located at the root of the `mapping` package. The actual definition of the RBF kernels is done in `impl/BasisFunctions.hpp`. The mathematical definitions provided in **Sect. 2.1.3** are directly taken from this file. Functions related to the query of specific points within a mesh, most notably to find the nearest neighbor of a given point is implemented in the package `query`, which is located outside of the `mapping` package at the root of the `src` directory. According to [7], it is based on a R^* index-tree provided by the

¹¹<https://precice.org/configuration-xml-reference.html>

¹²<https://developer.nvidia.com/cuda-toolkit>

¹³<https://rocm.docs.amd.com/>

*Boost.Geometry*¹⁴ package from the Boost library.

preCICE relies on *PETSc*¹⁵ and the library *Eigen*¹⁶ to perform heavy-duty linear algebra operations and to provide efficient data structures to manipulate the different mathematical objects that appear during mapping operations.

The actual implementation of the mapping methods is detailed in the different theses and publications written by the preCICE team, most notably by UERKERMANN [100], LINDNER [67], and ARIGUIB [7]. UERKERMANN focuses on the parallelization and inter-participant communication aspects of the mapping methods, while LINDNER discusses the mathematical background behind the implementation of RBF-based mapping methods for the options `rbf-global-...` detailed in **Sect. 2.2.1**. SCHNEIDER et al. [88] worked on porting RBF implementations for use with acceleration devices such as GPGPU using CUDA, ROCm and Ginkgo. ARIGUIB [7] explains the implementation of the nearest neighbor gradient mapping method and its integration within preCICE proper. SCHNEIDER et al. [89] is the reference publication for the implementation of the partition of unity method.

2.2.2.1 Implementation of projection-based mapping methods

As explained in **Sect. 2.1.3.1**, the *nearest-neighbor* mapping method assigns vertex values from an input mesh to the spatially closest vertices of an output mesh using a pointwise constant interpolation. The spatial distance to the closest neighbor in terms of Euclidian distance is predicted through an R^* index-tree implemented in the package `query`. The matched vertex indices are stored in an array. Depending on the constraint, *conservative*, where all input values are used, or *consistent*, where all output vertices receive a value, the search direction is reversed. The actual mapping uses Eigen's dynamic-size `VectorXd` object to store values and assigns them based on the precomputed index array. For a mesh containing n points, the computational cost of the overall method includes building the R^* -tree in $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$ time, performing each nearest-neighbor query in $\mathcal{O}(\log n)$ time, and applying a constant-cost in $\mathcal{O}(1)$ assignment per vertex. This leads to a total time complexity for n_A input vertices and n_B output vertices of $\mathcal{O}(n_B \log n_A)$ [7, 48].

The *nearest-projection* mapping method computes the value of each output vertex by projecting it onto the closest triangle of the input mesh. If no triangle is found, the algorithm falls back to the closest edge, and then to the nearest vertex, defaulting to a nearest-neighbor approach if necessary. The method handles this by identifying the closest geometric entity and storing the association in an array, which holds barycentric interpolation weights. As with nearest-neighbor

¹⁴<https://www.boost.org/>

¹⁵<https://petsc.org/release/>

¹⁶https://eigen.tuxfamily.org/index.php?title=Main_Page

mapping, an R^* -tree from the `query` package is used to accelerate the search for the closest triangle, edge, or vertex. The actual interpolation is performed in the `map` method using the stored weights. For *conservative* mapping, the search is performed from input to output mesh, requiring full connectivity on the output mesh. For *consistent* mapping, the direction is reversed. The computational complexity includes building the R^* -tree in $\mathcal{O}(m \log m)$ time, where m is the number of mesh elements, (triangles, edges, and vertices) in the searched mesh. Each neighbor query is done in $\mathcal{O}(\log m)$ with a constant-time assignment per vertex. The overall total cost is $\mathcal{O}(n_B \log m_A)$ for n_B output vertices and m_A input entities. However, since the number of entities m scales as $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$ for n vertices, this method is computationally more intensive than nearest-neighbor mapping, although it retains the same asymptotic growth rate in $\mathcal{O}(n_B \log n_A)$ [7, 48].

The *nearest-neighbor-gradient* mapping method extends the nearest-neighbor mapping by incorporating gradient information given by the participants to improve value assignment. While nearest-neighbor mapping directly assigns the value from the nearest vertex, the gradient-based method adjusts the value using a linear interpolation formula involving the gradient and the offset between matched vertices as explained in **Sect. 2.1.3.1**. The method perform its operations in a similar way as nearest-neighbor, but it performs an additional matrix multiplication to incorporate gradient effects. Since gradient-based mapping is not compatible with the *conservative* constraint, only the *consistent* variant is implemented. The overall computational complexity of $\mathcal{O}(n_B \log n_A)$ remains the same as nearest-neighbor mapping, where n_A is the number of input vertices and n_B the number of output vertices [7, 48].

The implementation of the aforementioned projection-based mapping methods is done at the root of the `mapping` package. The `NearestNeighborMapping`, `NearestProjectionMapping`, and `NearestNeighborGradientMapping` classes (found in a `.cpp` and `.hpp` files of the same name) inherit from the abstract class `Mapping` and implement its methods in an object-oriented fashion.

2.2.2.2 Implementation of RBF-based mapping methods

As explained in **Sect. 2.2.1**, there are three implementations of RBF-based mapping methods in preCICE: `rbf-global-direct`, `rbf-global-iterative`, and `rbf-pum-direct`. The implementation of the first two methods is based on the work of LINDNER [67] with GPGPU-based acceleration provided by SCHNEIDER [88]. The `rbf-pum-direct` method is based on the work of SCHNEIDER et al. [89].

The `rbf-global-direct` method uses a dense matrix decomposition of \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{P} to solve the systems in **Eqs. 2.6** and **2.5**. If the basis function is positive definite, the CHOLESKY decomposition is used, otherwise the QR decomposition is used [88]. Even if preCICE runs on multiple MPI processes, the scatter-gather approach used behind the scenes leads to data collection inside

a single process, so that the mapping procedure is performed in a serial fashion.

The `rbf-global-iterative` method uses the PETSc library to solve the linear system given by [Eq. \(2.5\)](#) in fully MPI-parallel fashion. QR decomposition is still used for \mathbf{P} to solve the linear least-square problem in [Eq. \(2.6\)](#) but [Eq. \(2.5\)](#) is solved using a GMRES (generalized minimal residual) iterative solver. Details on the implementation of this method especially its optimization and the integration of preCICE and PETSc data structures can be found in [\[67\]](#).

The implementation of the Partition of Unity RBF interpolation in preCICE (`rbf-pum-direct`) focuses on computational efficiency and parallelization. For local RBF interpolation within a cluster, preCICE uses a dense matrix implementation provided by the Eigen library. Since the kernel matrix \mathbf{C} is symmetric, only the upper (or lower) part is assembled, followed by a dense matrix decomposition. If the RBF is strictly positive definite, a Cholesky decomposition is used. Otherwise, a QR decomposition is preferred, particularly for solving least-squares problems related to polynomial contributions. All matrix decompositions are performed during initialization to enable efficient forward and backward substitutions during evaluation. Scaled weights needed for the interpolation are also precomputed and stored per cluster, facilitating the independent computation of local weighted solutions.

The partition of unity is built using an index tree to assign each mesh vertex to relevant clusters. In the evaluation phase, local weighted solutions are accumulated into a global solution vector. The transformation from global to local data indices is managed with a `boost::flat_set` from the Boost library, which offers constant-time traversal and logarithmic insertion complexity. This transformation is only required during initialization.

For parallelization, the algorithm is designed for distributed memory environments, where individual MPI ranks hold different subdomains. Repartitioning algorithms in preCICE allow ranks to share only relevant mesh data. Each rank computes its own cluster radius r_M , performs clustering, and handles its own partition of unity independently. The interpolation on the output mesh is performed in parallel, requiring the collection of input mesh vertices from all clusters covering a given vertex. This may duplicate cluster data at partition boundaries, but avoids costly inter-rank communication during evaluation. As a result, the algorithm achieves efficient parallel performance, though it remains tied to the quality of partitioning of the output mesh. Unless otherwise specified, the discussion above is valid for consistent mappings, however the implementation of conservative mappings is similar, barring some additional mathematical transformations. This is explained in detail in [\[67\]](#) for global implementations.

The implementation of the RBF-based mapping methods is done at the root of the `mapping` package within files named following the pattern `RadialBasisFct*`.

2.3 Numerical experiments using the ASTE framework

In this section, a series of numerical experiments is performed to compare the different mapping methods available in preCICE. The ASTE framework is used to perform these experiments, as it allows to test mapping methods in a controlled environment. ASTE is introduced in **Sect. 2.3.1**, while the numerical setup is described in **Sect. 2.3.2**, followed by the results of the numerical experiments in **Sect. 2.3.3**.

2.3.1 ASTE testing framework

The ASTE testing framework is hosted in a separate [GitHub repository](#)¹⁷ and its own [documentation](#)¹⁸ in the *Tooling* section of the official preCICE documentation. It is used across multiple preCICE related publications, such as [7, 89, 90] to name a few.

ASTE is a collection of tools that can be used to reproduce and evaluate particular mapping setups without using actual solver codes. Two common use cases according to its documentation are: The reproduction of a specific mapping setup when a given case behaves unexpectedly or crashes, and the *replay mode*, where a participant in a coupled setup is replaced by ASTE. This last use case is useful for debugging and developing new adapters.

In addition to its dependency on preCICE, ASTE relies on [VTK](#)¹⁹ to read and write mesh files in the `.vtk` or `.vtu` format, and [METIS](#)²⁰ for mesh partitioning. It also needs Python as it is composed of several Python scripts with a C++ backend. It is composed of four components that can be called through the command line:

- `precice-aste-run` – Core module interfacing with preCICE, which performs the actual mapping and data transfer within the testing environment.
- `precice-aste-evaluate` – Python script to compute and store data on mesh files in the `.vtk` or `.vtu` format.
- `precice-aste-partition` – Python script to partition a single mesh file into several ones for parallel runs
- `precice-aste-join` – Python script to join several mesh files into a single mesh file for parallel runs. It should be used in conjunction with `precice-aste-partition` to combine the results of a parallel run into a single mesh file.

As any simulation using preCICE, ASTE requires a configuration file in the `precice-config.xml` format. Instead of actual data fields, ASTE uses dummy data fields generated using test functions specified through `precice-aste-evaluate`. It can then provide error metrics on the

¹⁷<https://github.com/precice/aste>

¹⁸<https://precice.org/tooling-aste.html>

¹⁹<https://vtk.org/>

²⁰<https://github.com/KarypisLab/METIS>

Figure 2.12 – View of the wind turbine blade mesh used in the ASTE framework. The mesh is composed of tetrahedral elements and is available at different refinement levels.

output of the mapping process to evaluate the quality of the interpolation in addition to the actual result of the mapping. To obtain meshes in compatible formats, a dry-run of a real case or a single simulation step in a full setup can be performed with the export functionality of preCICE enabled.

2.3.2 Description of the test setups

To compare the different mapping methods available in preCICE and identify their characteristics, a series of numerical experiments were performed using various meshes and test functions to stress the underlying mapping procedure implemented in preCICE with somewhat realistic conditions. Below is a description of the geometries and meshes used in the tests:

- **Lid-driven cavity** – The meshes used for this case are taken from those used to simulate the lid-driven cavity benchmark (see **Sect. 1.3.1**) The geometry is limited to the fluid-structure interaction (FSI) interface between the structure and fluid meshes. The computational domain is defined as $\mathcal{D}_f = [0, 1] \times [0, 1]$, with its center at $\mathbf{c} = (0.5, 0.0, 0.5)$. The fluid and structure meshes consist of 2D Cartesian grids with quadrilateral elements and are available at different resolutions: 32×32 , 64×64 , 128×128 , and 256×256 .
- **Wind turbine blade** – This geometry is provided by the [official ASTE tutorial](#) and is used, for example, in [89]. The meshes are available from the [GitLab repository](#)²¹. Several refinement levels are provided, and the use of tetrahedral elements enables investigation of different mesh types and testing in a 3D scenario. See **Fig. 2.12** for an example with a minimum element size of $h = 0.01$ m.

To study a given mapping, specified through a standard `precice-config.xml` file, a dummy data field is first generated on the input mesh. ASTE already provides test functions commonly used in the context of optimization algorithm testing to generate such data. However, to offer a broader selection of functions with varying characteristics, additional functions have been implemented in this thesis. A Python script was written to automate result generation and feed it to ASTE. Note that the functions are rescaled and recentered relative to their original definitions [79]. This adjustment introduces more features within the test domain than the standard

²¹<https://gitlab.lrz.de/precice/precice2-ref-paper-setup>

formulation would provide.

Given a scale factor \mathbf{s} , a center $\mathbf{c} = \{c_i\}_{i \in \llbracket 1, D \rrbracket}$, and $D = 3$, the notation $\tilde{x}_i = \mathbf{s} \cdot (x_i - c_i)$ is used. All properties and formulas presented below are taken from [7, 79]. Note that scale factors are determined arbitrarily to concentrate a certain number of features in the test domain.

- **Sphere function** – This is one of the simplest optimization test function. It is mainly used for debugging purposes. It is continuous, convex, differentiable and unimodal. See **Fig. 2.13** for a representation of this function with $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{D}_f$. It is defined as:

$$\text{sphere}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^D (x_i - c_i)^2. \quad (2.18)$$

- **Rosenbrock function** – The ROSEN BROCK function is introduced to emulate a simple deformation of the lid in the case of the lid-driven cavity. See **Fig. 2.14** for a representation of this function with $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{D}_f$. It is defined as:

$$\text{rosenbrock}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^{D-1} \left[100 \cdot (\tilde{x}_{i+1} - \tilde{x}_i^2)^2 + (\tilde{x}_i - 1)^2 \right] \quad \text{with } \mathbf{s} = 10.$$

- **Rastrigin function** – This function is multimodal and has a large number of local minima. It is used to test the mapping on regions with many features. See **Fig. 2.15** for a representation of this function with $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{D}_f$. To break symmetries, the standard definition provided in [79] is slightly modified. In this case, it is defined as:

$$\text{rastrigin_mod}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^D \left[\tilde{x}_i^2 - 10 \cdot \cos(2\pi \cdot \tilde{x}_i) \right] - \tilde{x}_0 \tilde{x}_3 \quad \text{with } \mathbf{s} = 10. \quad (2.19)$$

To ensure that the computation of a relative error is possible and to enable comparison of results, a linear rescaling of the test function to the interval $[0, 1]$ is performed, as specified in **Eq. (2.20)**. An offset is added to ensure that the function does not reach zero within the domain, which would lead to an infinite relative error. In our case, the offset is equal to 1, so that all functions have values in the range $[1, 2]$. The rescaling is performed using the following equation:

$$\bar{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{f(\mathbf{x}) - m}{M - m} + \text{offset} \quad \text{with } m = \min_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{D}_f} f(\mathbf{x}) \text{ and } M = \max_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{D}_f} f(\mathbf{x}). \quad (2.20)$$

To compare the different methods, error metrics taken from [7, 67, 89] are used. Given a predicted value $f_a(\mathbf{x}_k)$ using the analytical test function on an output mesh point \mathbf{x}_k and the actual value at this point computed after the mapping procedure $g(\mathbf{x}_k)$, the following definitions are used:

(a) Projection of the sphere function in 2D.

(b) 3D representation of the sphere function.

Figure 2.13 – Visualization of the sphere function based on its definition in **Eq. (2.18)** after rescaling according to **Eq. (2.20)**.

(a) Projection of the ROSENBRACK function in 2D.

(b) 3D representation of the ROSENBRACK function.

Figure 2.14 – Visualization of the ROSENBRACK function based on its definition in **Eq. (2.3.2)** after rescaling according to **Eq. (2.20)**.

(a) Projection of the modified RASTRIGIN function in 2D.

(b) 3D representation of the modified RASTRIGIN function.

Figure 2.15 – Visualization of the RASTRIGIN function based on its definition in **Eq. (2.19)** after rescaling according to **Eq. (2.20)**.

- **Relative error** – The relative error ε_r is defined as:

$$\varepsilon_r(\mathbf{x}_k) = 100 \times \left| \frac{f_a(\mathbf{x}_k) - g(\mathbf{x}_k)}{f_a(\mathbf{x}_k)} \right| \quad \forall k \in \llbracket 1, N_B \rrbracket \quad . \quad (2.21)$$

- **Maximum absolute error** – The maximum absolute error per vertex or (discrete L^∞ norm) ε_a is defined as:

$$\varepsilon_a = \max_{k \in \llbracket 1, N_B \rrbracket} |f_a(\mathbf{x}_k) - g(\mathbf{x}_k)| \quad . \quad (2.22)$$

- **Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)** – The root mean square error $\bar{\varepsilon}$ (discrete L^2 norm) is defined as:

$$\bar{\varepsilon} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_B} \sum_{k=1}^{N_B} |f_a(\mathbf{x}_k) - g(\mathbf{x}_k)|^2} \quad . \quad (2.23)$$

Note that these metrics are relevant for consistent mapping methods. Conservative mapping methods are more difficult to evaluate independently. After discussions with the preCICE team, it was decided that no particular attention would be paid to the conservative mapping methods in the context of this thesis, since preCICE does not provide a straightforward way to assess their performance and no clear guidelines exist for their evaluation in contrast to consistent methods. The interested reader is referred to Chapter 4 of [67], where some insights in this topic are provided.

2.3.3 Results of the numerical experiments

Using the ASTE framework, a series of tests was performed to compare the different mapping methods available in preCICE. The results are presented in the following paragraphs. The meshes used for these experiments are those described in **Sect. 2.3.2**. The exact test setup for each case is detailed in the following sections.

2.3.3.1 Validation of the mapping procedure based on the lid-driven cavity case

Numerical setup The goal of this section is to validate the mapping procedure on the meshes used in one of the reference numerical benchmarks explained in **Sect. 1.3**. Note that it could be possible to use data taken directly from a real FSI simulation to validate using the export functionality of preCICE, however, this would not allow to compute error metrics as there would be no analytical solution to compare with. Therefore, a dummy data field is used instead. As described in **Sect. 2.3.2**, the Cartesian meshes at the coupling interface taken from the lid-driven cavity benchmark for both the structure and fluid domains are used. Through its adapter, FASTEST-3D exposes to the preCICE library two meshes for the fluid domain: the *nodes* mesh, which represent the vertices of the quadrilateral elements, and the *centers* mesh, which represents the center of these elements. An example for a 32×32 CVs mesh is shown in **Fig. 2.16**. Note that, for the same refinement, the structure mesh is strictly identical to the fluid *nodes* mesh. When simulating the full benchmark, the displacements are mapped under a *consistent* constraint from the structure mesh to the fluid *nodes* mesh. The numerical setup used here reproduces this scenario. A detailed description of the test setup is provided below:

- **Meshes** – The resolution of the structure mesh is 64×64 CVs. The target mesh is the fluid *nodes* mesh at a resolution of 128×128 CVs. This means that the structure mesh contains 65 nodes in each directions (4225 nodes in total), while the fluid mesh contains 129 nodes in each direction (16,641 nodes in total). Thus, the structure mesh is *coarser* than the fluid mesh, as it is usually the case in FSI simulations. The direction of the mapping is from the structure mesh to the fluid mesh in order to emulate the mapping of displacements in the real benchmark, which requires to use the *consistent* constraint.
- **Dummy data field** – A dummy data field is generated on the structure mesh using the ROSENBROCK test function defined in **Eq. (2.3.2)** and the modified RASTRIGIN test function defined in **Eq. (2.19)**. As explained in **Sect. 2.3.2**, all test functions are rescaled and recentered according to **Eq. (2.20)** to ensure that their values are in the range $[1, 2]$.
- **Mapping methods** – All projection-based mapping methods are tested: **NN**, **NP** and **NNG**. A subset of RBFs are used: **RBF-TPS**, **RBF-G**, and **RBF-CTPS**. The PU method is systematically applied, as it will be used in real simulation setups. Four processes are attached to run the mapping in parallel. The PU method uses the default value implemented in preCICE for the number of vertices per cluster, which is 20. The

configuration for **RBF-G** was determined using **Eq. (2.17)** with $d = 10^{-9}$, $m = 15$ and $h_{\max} = 7 \times 10^{-3}$ m, which yields a shape parameter of $\varepsilon = 50$. The configuration for **RBF-CTPS** was determined using the empirical rule $r_s = K \times \ell_c$ with $K = 15$ and $\ell_c = 7 \times 10^{-3}$ m, which yields a support radius equals to $r_s = 1.0 \times 10^{-1}$ m.

- **Post-processing** – For each mapping method, a visualization of the mapped data field is provided, along with the distribution of the relative error per vertex (or nodes). The relative error is computed using **Eq. (2.21)** with the analytical solution f_a being the evaluation of the test function at the vertex.

Figure 2.16 – Difference between mesh *nodes* and *centers*. The nodes are the vertices of the quadrilateral elements, while the centers are the center of these elements. The mesh displayed here features 32×32 CVs, with 33 nodes in each direction. The mesh is directly extracted from the lid-driven cavity benchmark.

Results on projection-based mapping methods A preliminary remark can be made on the results obtained using **NP** mapping. According to UERKERMANN [100], meshes undergo a partitioning process to distribute the workload across multiple processes. This partitioning leads to a loss of connectivity information at the subdomain boundaries, which is crucial for the nearest projection mapping method. As a result, **NP** mapping falls back to **NN** mapping at these boundaries, leading to a higher error in these regions. This phenomenon is visible in the results presented for this method in **Fig. 2.17**. Since four processes are used by ASTE for each emulated participant, four subdomains are clearly visible. This means that the maximum error

on a given mesh for the **NP** mapping is the same as the **NN** mapping due to this behavior. **NP** mapping is the only method to exhibit this behavior among all the methods tested in this thesis, as it is the only one that requires connectivity information.

Figure 2.17 – Connectivity loss due to partitioning causes higher error at the subdomain boundaries for **NP** mapping. The test function used is the ROSENBROCK function defined in **Eq. (2.3.2)**. The error metric is the relative error per vertex with v_f being the value of the test function at the vertex and v_m being the value after mapping. The mesh displayed here is the output mesh with a resolution of 128×128 CVs. The input mesh is the structure mesh with a resolution of 64×64 CVs (not shown).

The results for the **NN** mapping method are shown in **Fig. 2.18**. A checkerboard pattern is visible in the error distribution. This can also be seen when using **NNG** mapping, as it uses the same underlying principle as **NN**. **NP** mapping also exhibits this pattern. This is a characteristic feature of projection-based mapping methods caused by the omission of nodes during the mapping process or the lack of sufficiently near neighbors that would allow a finer representation of the data field, as explained in **Sect. 2.1.2**. This is especially visible in **Fig. 2.19**. In this figure, the same setup is used as specified above, but with a structure mesh of resolution 32×32 CVs and a fluid mesh of resolution 64×64 CVs to highlight the link between error distribution and input/output mesh nodes distribution. The error is concentrated in areas where there are no input mesh nodes in the vicinity of output mesh nodes. Furthermore, the error is more pronounced in regions with significant data variations (the reader is referred to **Fig. 2.14a** for the 2D plot of the test function), which is expected as the smaller density of data points in similar areas naturally would degrade the quality of any interpolation method.

As expected, **NNG** mapping produces slightly more accurate results through the use of gradient data as the error is lower than when using **NN**: The maximum relative error for **NN** is 9%, while the maximum relative error for **NNG** is 3%. This can be seen by comparing **Fig. 2.18**

(NN) and **Fig. 2.20** (NNG). This statement is valid for all data field tested, although they are not shown here for the sake of conciseness. The actual relative error is relatively small for all methods, which is expected given the overlap between the meshes used in this test. The error distribution remains similar to NN, since it is a nearest-neighbor projection method at its core. The use of gradient data might cause issues with data fields exhibiting discontinuities or sharp variations over small areas. Note that the checkerboard pattern would be less visible when using more randomly distributed meshes that are not directly subsets of each other.

Figure 2.18 – Mapping using NN on the lid-driven cavity with the modified RASTRIGIN test function defined in **Eq. (2.19)**. The error metric is the relative error per vertex with v_f being the value of the test function at the vertex and v_m being the value after mapping. The mesh displayed here is the output mesh with a resolution of 128×128 CVs. The input mesh is the structure mesh with a resolution of 64×64 CVs (not shown).

Results on RBF-based mapping methods Results using RBF-based mapping methods are shown in **Fig. 2.22** (RBF-TPS), **Fig. 2.23** (RBF-G), and **Fig. 2.24** (RBF-CTPS). Note that all methods produce smoother error distributions than their projection-based counterparts and have overall lower error metrics. This was expected as RBF-based mapping methods are more accurate than the other methods implemented in preCICE. All RBF methods exhibit an error concentration near the computational domain boundaries in addition to an error increase in high gradient regions, where the data field exhibits significant variations over a small area.

The concentration of the interpolation error near the boundaries of the computational domain is influenced by both the characteristics of the input data and the mesh topology. In the case studied, the modified RASTRIGIN function exhibits strong gradients at the edges, which naturally leads to larger interpolation errors in those regions. Moreover, the topology of the fluid and structure meshes contributes to this effect, as both grids exhibit significant overlap, cre-

Figure 2.19 – Error distribution for NN mapping with input and output mesh nodes. The test function used is the ROSENBROCK function defined in **Eq. (2.3.2)**. The error metric is the relative error per vertex. Note that the error distribution is presented using a smooth contour plot with the coloring boosted for the biggest values. ■ represents the input mesh nodes and ■ the output mesh nodes. The output mesh has a resolution of 64×64 CVs. The input mesh is the structure mesh with a resolution of 32×32 CVs.

Figure 2.20 – Mapping using **NNG** on the lid-driven cavity with the modified **RASTRIGIN** test function defined in **Eq. (2.19)**. The error metric is the relative error per vertex with v_f being the value of the test function at the vertex and v_m being the value after mapping. The mesh displayed here is the output mesh with a resolution of 128×128 CVs. The input mesh is the structure mesh with a resolution of 64×64 CVs (not shown).

ating areas with fewer distinct input points near the domain boundaries. Similar boundary error patterns are observed across different radial basis functions (**RBF-TPS**, **RBF-G**, and **RBF-CTPS**) as shown in **Figs. 2.22, 2.24, and 2.23**. The error intensity varies depending on the underlying data field according to tests performed on other data fields (not shown in this report). To understand this phenomenon, the reader is referred to **Fig. 2.21**, which presents a 1D example with a similar point distribution. It illustrates that while the boundary itself sees low interpolation error, due to the exact alignment of the input and output grid, the second row of points inward from the boundary suffers higher errors. This arises because these points do not have nearby counterparts in the input grid. This absence of local support points leads to reduced interpolation accuracy, creating the characteristic boundary error pattern seen in the 2D error maps. This pattern is generally associated with projection-based methods as shown before in this section. Since there are less points inside the clusters used by the PU method, as we are at the edges of the computational domain, the interpolant quality is reduced, leading to higher errors in these regions. This phenomenon was already noted in the dissertation of DAVIS [28]. All RBF-based methods achieve a maximum relative error around 1% compared to around 3% for **NP** and **NNG** (9% for **NN**).

To complement and summarize the findings based on the lid-driven cavity benchmark, a comparison of different error metrics is presented in **Fig. 2.25**. This figure shows clearly that RBF-based mapping methods outperform projection-based methods in terms of accuracy for the configuration used here.

Figure 2.21 – Absolute error distribution for a 1D example with the modified RASTRIGIN test function to show the error increase at the boundaries. The data presented in this plot was generated using a custom Python script and not ASTE. It uses a global approach instead of the partition of unity formulation to solve the interpolation problem.

Figure 2.22 – Mapping using **RBF-TPS** with PU on the lid-driven cavity with the modified RASTRIGIN test function defined in **Eq. (2.19)**. The error metric is the relative error per vertex with v_f being the value of the test function at the vertex and v_m being the value after mapping. The mesh displayed here is the output mesh with a resolution of 128×128 CVs. The input mesh is the structure mesh with a resolution of 64×64 CVs (not shown).

Figure 2.23 – Mapping using **RBF-G** with PU on the lid-driven cavity with the modified RASTRIGIN test function defined in Eq. (2.19). The error metric is the relative error per vertex with v_f being the value of the test function at the vertex and v_m being the value after mapping. The shape parameter is set to $\varepsilon = 50$. The mesh displayed here is the output mesh with a resolution of 128×128 CVs. The input mesh is the structure mesh with a resolution of 64×64 CVs (not shown).

Figure 2.24 – Mapping using **RBF-CTPS** with PU on the lid-driven cavity with the modified RASTRIGIN test function defined in Eq. (2.19). The error metric is the relative error per vertex with v_f being the value of the test function at the vertex and v_m being the value after mapping. The support radius is set to $r_s = 0.1$ m. The mesh displayed here is the output mesh with a resolution of 128×128 CVs. The input mesh is the structure mesh with a resolution of 64×64 CVs (not shown).

Figure 2.25 – Comparison of different error metrics for meshes extracted from the lid-driven cavity benchmark. The error metrics are the maximum relative error per vertex, the maximum absolute error, and the RMSE.

Remarks The results obtained in this section are consistent with previous theoretical findings. Given the simplicity of the geometry, almost all mapping methods are able to produce accurate results with low relative error. RBF-based mapping methods are more accurate than projection-based mapping methods, as expected. The choice of the basis function will depend on the exact data field, but by default, **RBF-TPS** with the PU method is used as it produces good results without the need for additional configuration (shape parameter, support radius) compared to projection-based methods or other RBFs. Outside the testing framework ASTE, it is difficult to easily find an optimal value for the shape parameter or support radius of the kernels. The simplest rules provided in **Sect. 2.1.3.3** can be applied to provide a starting point, but ultimately the user must experiment with different values to find the best configuration for their specific problem. With the introduction of the PU method, **RBF-TPS** can be used on large problems, where it was previously unfeasibly expensive. **NN** or **NNG** mapping could be satisfying in this context as it is extremely cheap compared to RBF-based methods, but also because the structure and fluid meshes exhibit significant overlap. However, the present experiment does not represent the full mapping procedure of the lid-driven cavity benchmark. Indeed, in addition to the mapping of displacements from the structure mesh to the fluid mesh, the forces acting on the structure mesh must be transferred under a *conservative* constraint from the fluid *centers* mesh to the structure mesh. This step is not modeled and there is no mesh overlap in this case. In addition to this fact, RBF-based mappings have smoother error distributions than projection-based methods, which is a desirable property for the stability of coupling methods. This further motivates the use of RBF-based mapping methods in the context of FSI simulations.

2.3.3.2 Comparison of the mapping methods on the wind turbine blade geometry

The results obtained using the lid-driven cavity benchmark are not fully representative of the performance of the mapping methods in a broader context, due to the simplicity of the geometry and the significant overlap between meshes. This initial test was intended primarily to validate the basic functionality and usability of the mapping methods on one of the benchmarks introduced in **Sect. 1.3**, rather than to evaluate their overall effectiveness. To conduct a more comprehensive assessment, a more complex setup is therefore required.

Numerical setup The wind turbine blade geometry (see **Sect. 2.3.2**) was selected due to the availability of multiple refinement levels, offering greater flexibility in the choice of input and output meshes. The dummy data field used as input for the mapping procedure is generated using the modified RASTRIGIN test function defined in **Eq. (2.19)**. This function was chosen because of its complex behavior—characterized by numerous local minima and maxima and sharp variations over small regions—making it a suitable stress test for the mapping methods.

Figure 2.26 – Input and output meshes for the comparison of different mapping methods on the wind turbine blade geometry. The input mesh has a width of 0.02 m, and the output mesh a width of 0.004 m. The dummy data field displayed on the input mesh is the modified RASTRIGIN test function as defined in **Eq. (2.19)**.

In this configuration, the input mesh has a characteristic width of 0.02 m (average mesh length), while the output mesh has a finer resolution of 0.004 m. A visualization of the dummy field along with the corresponding input and output meshes is provided in **Fig. 2.26**. This setup deliberately introduces a significant difference in mesh resolution between source and target. This is commonly encountered in practical applications, where the fluid mesh is often finer than the

structure mesh to accurately capture flow features around the structure. The mapping method used to map from the coarse input mesh to the fine output mesh is representative of the displacement mapping from the structure to the fluid mesh in a fluid-structure interaction (FSI) simulation under a *consistent* constraint. It also facilitates the identification of error distribution patterns across the domain.

The mapping methods evaluated in this section are the same as those introduced previously: **NN**, **NNG**, **NP**, **RBF-TPS**, **RBF-G**, and **RBF-CTPS**. For all RBF-based approaches, the partition of unity (PU) method is systematically applied. The configuration for **RBF-G** is based on the shape parameter defined by **Eq. (2.17)**, using $d = 10^{-9}$, $m = 15$, and $h_{\max} = 0.02$ m, resulting in a shape parameter of $\varepsilon = 15$. For **RBF-CTPS**, the support radius is determined empirically using the relation $r_s = K \times \ell_c$, with $K = 15$ and $\ell_c = 0.02$ m, yielding $r_s = 0.3$ m.

The error metric displayed in the different figures used in this section is the absolute error per vertex, computed using **Eq. (2.22)**. The analytical solution f_a is the evaluation of the test function at the output mesh nodes. The relative error is not used as error metric in this case, because the absolute error is already computed by ASTE and saved in the output files. Since processing is done through Paraview and the implementation of the test function would be difficult, this approach is deemed sufficient for the analysis. The computation of the relative error would help to better visualize the error.

Results obtained for projection-based methods The results obtained using the projection-based mapping methods are presented in **Fig. 2.27**. The mapped data field is shown on the left, while the corresponding absolute error distribution is displayed on the right. In contrast to the observations made in **Sect. 2.3.3.1**, clear distinctions can be observed among the three methods.

The **NN** mapping yields poor results, with noticeable artifacts in the output field corresponding to the input mesh cells. These block-like patterns indicate that the mapped values are overly influenced by the discrete structure of the coarse input mesh. As expected, the absolute error is highest in regions with significant data variation, a characteristic behavior of this method previously discussed.

The **NNG** mapping produces substantially improved results in terms of error magnitude compared to both **NN** and **NP**. However, a residual checkerboard pattern remains visible in the error distribution as expected due to the nature of nearest-neighbor interpolation. This phenomenon was already observed in **Sect. 2.3.3.1**.

The **NP** mapping is affected by the loss of connectivity resulting from domain partitioning, as described in **Sect. 2.3.3.1**. Although the overall error magnitude is lower than that of **NN**,

and the error distribution appears smoother, four distinct subdomains are clearly visible in both the mapped field and the error distribution. These correspond to the number of processes used during the mapping procedure. As previously observed, the maximum absolute error is concentrated near the subdomain boundaries, highlighting the sensitivity of this method to partitioning effects.

Figure 2.27 – Results obtained using projection-based mapping methods (NN, NNG, NP) on the wind turbine blade geometry. The mapping result (on the left) is displayed alongside the relative error distribution (on the right). The dummy data field used is the modified RASTRIGIN test function as defined in **Eq. (2.19)**. The input mesh has a width of 0.02 m, and the output mesh a width of 0.004 m.

Results obtained for RBF-based methods The results obtained using the RBF-based mapping methods are presented in **Fig. 2.28**. The mapped data field is shown on the left, while the corresponding absolute error distribution is displayed on the right. All three methods demonstrate similar behavior, characterized by smooth error distributions and low maximum absolute errors. The error scale used is consistent with that in **Fig. 2.27** for the projection-based methods, allowing for direct visual comparison.

No discernible patterns are visible in either the mapped fields or the error distributions, indicating a high level of accuracy and spatial consistency, at this scale. Among the three, **RBF-G** yields the best results, with a maximum absolute error of approximately 3×10^{-3} , well below the range captured in **Fig. 2.27** under the shared color scale.

To provide a more quantitative comparison, the maximum absolute error and root mean square error (RMSE) for all methods are summarized in **Fig. 2.29**. As expected, the NN mapping performs the worst in terms of both metrics, while **RBF-G** outperforms all others by a significant margin. Overall, the RBF-based methods consistently achieve better results than their projection-based counterparts.

It is worth noting that **RBF-TPS** offers competitive performance without requiring any parameter tuning, making it an appealing choice for general use. However, this case study highlights the advantage of parametric methods: when appropriately configured, they can yield substantially lower errors, as show here by the performance of **RBF-G**.

Figure 2.28 – Results obtained using RBF-based mapping methods (**RBF-TPS**, **RBF-G**, **RBF-CTPS**) on the wind turbine blade geometry. The mapping result (on the left) is displayed alongside the absolute error distribution (on the right). The dummy data field used is the modified RASTRIGIN test function as defined in [Eq. \(2.19\)](#). The input mesh has a width of 0.02 m, and the output mesh a width of 0.004 m. The dots visible in the error distribution are the output mesh nodes. They are displayed to help see the underlying geometry as the error is very low.

2.3.3.3 Convergence order of the mapping methods

The goal of this subsection is to assess the convergence order of the different mapping methods available in preCICE and to compare the results with the theoretical convergence order given in [Sect. 2.1.5](#). To achieve this goal, a similar process as the one used in [\[25\]](#) for preCICE v2 is followed. A description of the numerical setup is provided below:

- **Meshes** – The COARSE and FINE mesh series used in this convergence order study are presented in [Tab. 2.1](#) and originate from the preCICE v2 reference paper [\[25\]](#). Additional details are provided in [Sect. 2.3.2](#). The underlying geometry is the wind turbine blade shown in [Fig. 2.12](#), a realistic and complex model previously used in several preCICE studies [\[7, 89, 90\]](#). Mapping is performed onto a fixed output mesh, specific to each series. For the COARSE series, all meshes are projected onto a mesh with element width $h = 0.009$ m, while the FINE series uses a target mesh with $h = 0.0014$ m. These choices are motivated by the availability of multiple refinement levels, their established use in prior works, and the availability of existing convergence results on this geometry [\[25\]](#).

Figure 2.29 – Maximum absolute error and RMSE for the different mapping methods on the wind turbine blade geometry.

- **Dummy data field** – A dummy data field is generated on the input meshes using the test function defined in **Eq. (2.24)**, the same as the one used in [25]. The choice of this test function instead of those previously introduced in **Sect. 2.3.2** is motivated by its simplicity and the reproduction of the test setup presented in [25]. The test functions given earlier in this report serve as stress tests for the mapping methods and they were not meant to be used for convergence order studies.

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = 0.78 + \cos\left(10 \sum_{i=1}^n x_i\right) \quad (2.24)$$

- **Error metric** – The error metric used to assess the convergence order is the RMSE defined in **Eq. (2.23)**. The RMSE is computed between the analytical solution f_a and the mapped data field g at the output mesh nodes.
- **Mapping methods** – All mapping methods available in preCICE using their PU version only.
- **Comparison with reference paper** – The original study uses the `rbf-global-iterative` for RBF-based mapping methods. All other parameters, except the configuration of the RBF themselves, are identical.

In contrast to the original study [25], the parameter (support radius or shape parameter) is set to a fixed value for a given series of meshes in the present investigation. The following configuration is used for the convergence order study:

- **COARSE** series – The support radius of all locally supported RBF is set to $r_s = 0.1$, the shape parameter of **RBF-MQ** is set to $\varepsilon = 0.01$, the shape parameter of **RBF-IMQ** is set to 0.01 and for **RBF-G** to 50.
- **FINE** series – The support radius of all locally supported RBF is set to $r_s = 0.01$, the shape parameter of **RBF-MQ** is set to $\varepsilon = 0.001$, the shape parameter of **RBF-IMQ** is set to 0.001 and for **RBF-G** to 400.

COARSE mesh series			FINE mesh series		
h	N_V	N_T	h	N_V	N_T
0.03	438	1007	0.004	21283	43352
0.02	924	2027	0.003	38112	77271
0.01	3458	7246	0.002	84882	171319
0.009	4302	8970	0.0014	172803	347815
0.008	5310	11025	0.001	338992	681069
0.006	9588	19712	0.0007	691426	1387249
0.004	21283	43352	0.0005	1354274	2714699

Table 2.1 – COARSE and FINE mesh series used for the convergence order study based on the wind turbine blade geometry. The mesh size h is given in meters, while N_V and N_T are the number of vertices and triangles in the mesh, respectively. Every mesh in this series is mapped onto the mesh with $h = 0.009$ m for COARSE and $h = 0.0014$ m for FINE. Taken from [25].

Some results are available from the reference paper for preCICE v2 [25] and are shown in **Fig. 2.30**. Nearest neighbor (NN) mapping is clearly first-order accurate for both series, while nearest projection (NP) is between first and second-order accurate. All RBF methods presented in the figure are shown to be around second-order accurate. A strong influence of the support radius on the mapping accuracy is observed for **RBF-CTPS**. Note that these results were obtained using the `rbf-global-iterative` method. As stated in the original paper, the case using **RBF-TPS** is unfeasibly expensive for the FINE series, so no results are shown for this method. Note that the support radius is modified as a function of the mesh size h for **RBF-CTPS**.

The choice of constant parameters for all RBF methods in the present work is to avoid complex adjustments especially for the shape parameter. Indeed, while some prediction methods are given in **Sect. 2.1.3.3**, the size of the meshes renders the optimization algorithm proposed by RIPPA [83] extremely expensive without a parallel or GPU-based implementation. Furthermore, the methods presented in **Sect. 2.1.3.3** are designed for a global RBF method and not the PU approach. An optimization algorithm for the PU method would require to implement the partitioning algorithm already implemented in preCICE, which is not feasible within the time frame of this thesis. The choice of constant parameters for all meshes is therefore preferred for simplicity and efficiency.

Figure 2.30 – Convergence order of the mapping methods from the preCICE v2 reference paper for the COARSE and FINE mesh series. C-TPS refers to **RBF-CTPS** (compact thin plate splines) and G-TPS refers to **RBF-TPS** (thin plate splines). Using TPS is unfeasible for the FINE series according to the authors of [25]. The error metric used in this study is the RMSE. Taken from [25].

The convergence order is computed by performing a linear regression of the logarithm of the error metric (RMSE) against the logarithm of the mesh size h . The slope of the regression line is then used to determine the convergence order. Convergence orders are therefore approximations given the shape of the curve obtained for certain methods. The mapping procedure is done through the ASTE framework as presented in **Sect. 2.3.1**.

The results of the convergence order study are shown in **Fig. 2.31**. The results are consistent with the theoretical convergence order presented in **Sect. 2.1.5**. The nearest-neighbor mapping is first-order accurate for both series, while the nearest projection mapping is between first and second-order accurate. The nearest-neighbor-gradient is second-order accurate, as stated in [7]. The RBF methods are all second-order accurate, or even higher. However this result is largely influenced by the choice of the parameter (support radius or shape parameter) for the basis functions that require one. To illustrate this point, the convergence order for the basis functions **RBF-CTPS** and **RBF-MQ** are computed for different values of their respective parameters on the COARSE series. The results are shown in **Figs. 2.32** and **2.33**. Both the actual RMSE for each test point and the overall convergence order of the method are strongly influenced by the choice of the parameter in both cases. These observations remain coherent with previous remarks made in **Sect. 2.1.3**. Note that on **Fig. 2.31** for the FINE series, the error does not decrease for some RBF-based methods. This may be due to a concept tied to RBF interpolation called *error saturation* [67]. Even if the mesh width approaches zero, the error may not converge to zero, but may have a lower bound, called the *saturation error*. Another explanation for this phenomenon could be the concentration of error in certain regions of the mesh, leading to a lack of improvement in the overall error metric.

Figure 2.31 – Convergence order of the mapping methods from the ASTE framework for the COARSE and FINE mesh series for preCICE v3 (current version). The error metric used in this study is the RMSE.

Figure 2.32 – Convergence order of the RBF-based mapping using the basis function **RBF-CTPS** for different support radii. The error metric used here is the RMSE. The dummy data field is generated using the `sphere` test function defined in **Eq. (2.18)**.

Figure 2.33 – Convergence order of the RBF-based mapping using the basis function **RBF-MQ** for different shape parameters. The error metric used here is the RMSE. The dummy data field is generated using the `sphere` test function defined in **Eq. (2.18)**.

To ensure continuity with the lid-driven cavity benchmark, a similar convergence order study is conducted using the various mesh resolutions available for this test case. The procedure follows the exact same methodology as that applied to the wind turbine blade geometry, with the only difference being the choice of meshes.

Specifically, fluid *nodes* meshes at resolutions of 32×32 , 64×64 , and 128×128 CVS are mapped onto a fluid *centers* mesh corresponding to a 256×256 resolution. The distinction between fluid *nodes* and fluid *centers* meshes is illustrated in **Fig. 2.16**. Due to low-level memory errors related to the ASTE framework, it was not possible to use the 256×256 fluid *nodes* mesh as the output mesh. This issue, which could not be resolved, was not encountered in the complete lid-driven cavity benchmark or in any other test cases.

The results of the convergence study are presented in **Fig. 2.34**. They align well with the theoretical expectations discussed in **Sect. 2.1.5** and are consistent with the findings obtained for the wind turbine blade geometry.

Figure 2.34 – Convergence order of the mapping methods using the ASTE framework for the lid-driven cavity benchmark. The error metric used in this study is the RMSE. The dummy data field is generated using the modified RASTRIGIN test function defined in **Eq. (2.19)**.

2.4 Preliminary conclusion

In this chapter, efforts were made to provide a comprehensive and uniform description of the mapping methods available in preCICE. The focus was on the theoretical foundations, practical implementations, and performance characteristics of these methods, with the aim of facilitating their understanding and application in FSI simulations. Pointers to configuration optimization strategies for RBF-based mapping methods were provided, but the complexity of the problem and the time constraints of this thesis limits their implementation in a real test scenario. The ASTE framework was introduced as a tool to test the mapping methods in a controlled environment, allowing for the evaluation of their performance on a numerical benchmark and the assessment of their convergence order. It was integrated within a set of Python scripts to automate the testing of mapping methods. The results obtained from the numerical experiments confirmed the theoretical expectations regarding the convergence properties of the mapping methods. The RBF-based mapping methods were shown to be more accurate than projection-based methods, with the choice of basis function and configuration parameters playing a crucial role in their performance. The introduction of the partition of unity method allowed for the use of RBF-based mapping methods on large meshes, making them more practical for real-world applications.

Review of coupling methods implemented in preCICE

In the context of *monolithic* FSI simulations, a discretization of the overall problem yields a system of equations encompassing the flow variables \mathbf{f} and the structural variables \mathbf{s} , which can be expressed as [48]:

$$\mathcal{A}(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{s}) = \mathbf{0} \quad , \quad (3.1)$$

with \mathcal{A} a usually non-linear operator representing the problem. Focusing now on *partitioned* FSI simulations, the fluid and structure equations are solved separately, leading to a coupled system of equations that can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{f} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{s}) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{s} = \mathcal{S}(\mathbf{f}) \quad , \quad (3.2)$$

where \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{S} are the fluid and structure operators, respectively. The goal of a coupling scheme is to reconstruct the solution of the monolithic system (3.1) from the solutions of the partitioned system (3.2). In this chapter, the different coupling algorithms implemented in preCICE are reviewed with numerical examples to illustrate their features and limitations.

3.1 Theory behind the available coupling methods

In preCICE, two types of coupling schemes are available: *implicit* and *explicit*. For each type, both a serial and a parallel variant are implemented. In this context, *parallel* refers to inter-solver parallelism. preCICE explicitly distinguishes between the parallelization strategies of the participant (labeled as intra-solver parallelism) and the parallelization of the coupling procedure as a whole (including mapping, coupling algorithm, communication etc.), which is labeled as inter-solver parallelism. For explicit coupling, preCICE provides a *conventional serial staggered (CSS)* and a *conventional parallel staggered (CPS)* scheme (see **Sect. 3.1.1**). For implicit coupling, preCICE implements a serial Block GAUSS–SEIDEL (**GS**) scheme and a parallel Block

JACOBI (**J**) scheme, both of which can be combined with various *acceleration methods* (see **Sect. 3.1.2**). Here, the term *acceleration methods* refers to numerical techniques that enhance the stability and convergence rate of implicit coupling schemes¹.

In the context of FSI simulations, instabilities can arise not only from the flow or structural models but also from the partitioned coupling itself. In particular, the *added-mass effect* introduces an intrinsic instability [18, 23, 48]. This phenomenon has a direct impact on the simulation setup and must be considered when selecting a coupling scheme.

The *added-mass effect* is a primary driver of instabilities in partitioned FSI simulations involving incompressible flows. In fluid mechanics, it refers to the additional inertia imposed on a system when a body moves through a fluid and must displace a certain volume of that fluid along with it [57, 94]. Explicit coupling schemes are particularly sensitive to this effect, but implicit methods are not immune. Instabilities arise when the fluid and structural equations are solved in a staggered (partitioned) fashion, where one or both solvers advance in time by predicting interface boundary values from the other solver, rather than iterating toward convergence within the same time step. This effectively renders the boundary treatment an explicit coupling step, regardless of whether each solver internally uses implicit time integration [48]. The added-mass effect becomes particularly significant when the fluid and structural densities are of similar magnitude. This is notably the case in hemodynamic simulations, such as blood flow in arteries, where the densities of blood and arterial tissue are close to each other [23, 94]. GATZHAMMER in Section 2.3.3 of his thesis [48] provides a concise literature review of the *added-mass effect*. The geometry of the domain and the coupling interfaces also plays a significant role in the severity of the added-mass effect, especially for light or slender structures. Other physical properties of the solid and fluid media, such as viscosity and stiffness also influence the emergence of instabilities.

3.1.1 Explicit coupling schemes

Explicit coupling schemes use only one sub-iteration per time step to approximate the monolithic solution. Their stability is largely dictated by instabilities inherent to, or induced by, the numerical setup [85]. Such schemes are often adequate for compressible FSI problems where fluid-structure coupling is weak and oscillations remain small, as in aeroelasticity. However, they may fail to converge in incompressible flows when the fluid and structure densities are comparable and/or when strong oscillations occur. In particular, their performance is strongly affected by the *added-mass effect* [18], the severity of which depends on the specific simulation configuration.

Conventional Serial Staggered (CSS) In the **CSS** coupling scheme, the fluid and structure solvers are executed sequentially (see **Algo. 1**). The fluid solver \mathcal{F} computes the fluid variables \mathbf{f}_{n+1} at time step $n + 1$ based on the structure variables \mathbf{s}_n at time step n , the structure solver

¹Acceleration techniques are not available for explicit coupling schemes.

\mathcal{S} then computes the structure variables \mathbf{s}_{n+1} at time step $n + 1$ based on the fluid variables \mathbf{f}_{n+1} . PIPERNO et al. [77] and FARHAT et al. [44] showed that this coupling scheme is first-order accurate in time, regardless of the time stepping accuracy of the fluid and structure solvers used in the simulation setup. According to FARHAT et al. [44], the CSS coupling scheme can incorporate a subcycling strategy, where the fluid solver is executed with a smaller time step size than the structure solver multiple times to achieve a better convergence. This is particularly useful when the timescales of the structure and fluid solvers differ significantly. To illustrate the data flow between the solvers, **Fig. 3.1a** shows a schematic representation of the CSS coupling scheme.

Algorithm 1 Conventional Serial Staggered (**CSS**) coupling scheme. n is the time step index, \mathbf{f}_n and \mathbf{s}_n are the fluid and structure variables at time step n , respectively, with \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{S} the fluid and structure operators [32, 48].

```

1: for  $n = 0, 1, \dots, n_{\max}$  do
2:   Transfer  $\mathbf{s}_n$  to the fluid solver.
3:   Solve  $\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{s}_n) = \mathbf{f}_{n+1}$ 
4:   Transfer  $\mathbf{f}_{n+1}$  to the structure solver.
5:   Solve  $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{f}_{n+1}) = \mathbf{s}_{n+1}$ 
6: end for

```

Conventional Parallel Staggered (CPS) To allow inter-solver parallelism, the **CPS** coupling scheme is used (see **Algo. 2**). In this scheme, the fluid and structure solvers are executed in parallel. The fluid solver computes the fluid variables \mathbf{f}_{n+1} at time step $n + 1$ based on the structure variables \mathbf{s}_n at time step n , while the structure solver computes the structure variables \mathbf{s}_{n+1} at time step $n + 1$ based on the fluid variables \mathbf{f}_n at time step n . FARHAT et al. [44] shows that the CPS scheme requires relatively small time-steps to ensure its numerical stability and its accuracy. To illustrate the data flow between the solvers, **Fig. 3.1b** shows a schematic representation of the CPS coupling scheme.

Algorithm 2 Conventional Parallel Staggered (**CPS**) coupling scheme. n is the time step index, \mathbf{f}_n and \mathbf{s}_n are the fluid and structure variables at time step n , respectively, with \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{S} the fluid and structure operators [32, 48]. The execution of both solvers is performed in parallel.

```

1: for  $n = 0, 1, \dots, n_{\max}$  do
2:   Transfer  $\mathbf{s}_n$  to the fluid solver and  $\mathbf{f}_n$  to the structure solver.
3:   Solve  $\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{s}_n) = \mathbf{f}_{n+1}$  and  $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{f}_n) = \mathbf{s}_{n+1}$ .
4: end for

```

Limitations of explicit coupling schemes The major advantage of explicit coupling schemes is their simplicity and ease of implementation. They also offer low memory consumption and CPU costs in case of FSI as only a fixed number of remeshing steps caused by the moving grids are required. However, the main drawback in the context of fluid-structure interaction

(a) Conventional Serial Staggered (CSS). (b) Conventional Parallel Staggered (CPS).

Figure 3.1 – Schematic representation of explicit coupling schemes.

simulations is that they may suffer from stability issues if the coupling between the dynamics of the fluid and structure is too strong, especially in incompressible flows with high density ratios, where the added-mass effect is particularly pronounced [18, 48]. This leads to the introduction of implicit coupling schemes, as described in the next section.

3.1.2 Implicit coupling schemes

As stated in the introduction of this chapter, preCICE implements two implicit coupling schemes: the Block GAUSS–SEIDEL (**GS** or multiplicative SCHWARZ procedure [48]) and the Block JACOBI (**J** or additive SCHWARZ procedure [48]) coupling schemes. In this section, an overview of both methods is provided in addition to convergence criteria. An important aspect of implicit coupling schemes is the addition of *acceleration* methods. In the context of preCICE, constant under-relaxation, AITKEN relaxation, and interface quasi-NEWTON (**IQN**) acceleration methods are available. **Sect. 3.1.2.2** is dedicated to these numerical methods.

3.1.2.1 Block Gauß–Seidel and Block Jacobi coupling schemes

Pseudo-codes for the Block GAUSS–SEIDEL and Block JACOBI coupling schemes are provided in **Algo. 3** and **Algo. 4**, respectively. **Fig. 3.2a** illustrates the coupling iteration process for the Block GAUSS–SEIDEL scheme, while **Fig. 3.2b** shows the same for the Block JACOBI scheme. The **GS** scheme is referred to as a *serial* implicit coupling method because it updates one participant after the other, whereas **J** is considered as a *parallel* implicit coupling method, as it updates both participants simultaneously.

The convergence of the procedure can be measured by the residual of the fixed-point iteration. Let $\tilde{\cdot}$ denote the result of a fixed-point iteration before being fed to any acceleration method, the fixed-point residual is defined as:

$$\mathbf{r}_{k+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+1} - \mathbf{s}_k \quad \text{with} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+1} = \mathcal{S} \circ \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{s}_k) \quad (3.3)$$

The residual \mathbf{r}_{k+1} can be used to assess convergence of the sub-iteration process [48, 100]. By construction, $\mathbf{r}_{k+1} = \mathbf{0}$ if a fixed point is reached. Thus, $\mathbf{r}_k > 0$ can be used as a convergence

Algorithm 3 Block GAUSS–SEIDEL coupling scheme. n is the time step index and k the sub-iteration index, with \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{S} the fluid and structure operators [32, 48].

```

1: for  $n = 0, 1, \dots, n_{\max}$  do
2:    $k = 0$ 
3:   Let  $\mathbf{s}_0 = \mathbf{s}^n$  ▷ Use the last converged solution.
4:   while not converged do
5:     Solve  $\mathbf{f}_{k+1} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{s}_k)$ 
6:     Transfer  $\mathbf{f}_{k+1}$  to the structure solver.
7:     Solve  $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_k = \mathcal{S}(\mathbf{f}_{k+1})$ 
8:     Compute  $\mathbf{s}_{k+1} = \text{Acc}(\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_k, \mathbf{s}_k)$ . ▷ Acceleration method.
9:      $k = k + 1$ 
10:  end while
11: end for
    
```

Algorithm 4 Block JACOBI coupling scheme for a given time step n . k the sub-iteration index, with \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{S} the fluid and structure operators [48].

```

1: for  $n = 0, 1, \dots, n_{\max}$  do
2:   Let  $\mathbf{s}_0 = \mathbf{s}^n$  and  $\mathbf{f}_0 = \mathbf{f}^n$ . ▷ Use the last converged solution.
3:    $k = 0$ 
4:   while not converged do
5:     Transfer  $\mathbf{s}_k$  to the fluid solver and  $\mathbf{f}_k$  to the structure solver.
6:     Solve  $\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_k = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{s}_k)$  and  $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_k = \mathcal{S}(\mathbf{f}_k)$ .
7:     Compute  $(\mathbf{f}_{k+1}, \mathbf{s}_{k+1})^\top = \text{Acc}((\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_k, \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_k)^\top, (\mathbf{s}_k, \mathbf{f}_k)^\top)$ . ▷ Acceleration method.
8:      $k = k + 1$ 
9:   end while
10: end for
    
```


(a) Block GAUSS–SEIDEL (GS) coupling scheme. (b) Block JACOBI (BJ) coupling scheme.

Figure 3.2 – Schematic representation of implicit coupling schemes.

criterion. An absolute convergence criterion can be formulated as:

$$\|\mathbf{r}_{k+1}\|_2 = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (r_{k+1,i})^2} \leq \varepsilon_{\text{abs}} \quad (3.4)$$

with $r_{k,i}$ a component of \mathbf{r}_k , N the degrees of freedom in the coupling problem and ε_{abs} the absolute convergence tolerance. A *relative* convergence criterion is required as the residual can vary by many orders of magnitude during the coupling iterations. Such a criterion can be defined as:

$$\frac{\|\mathbf{r}_k\|_2}{\|\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k)\|_2} \leq \varepsilon_{\text{rel}} \quad (3.5)$$

with ε_{rel} the relative convergence tolerance. In practice, both criteria can be combined to ensure robust convergence. Choosing a relevant convergence criterion is by no means an easy and trivial task as explained by UEKERMANN [100] and EISENSTAT et al. [38]. Several criteria are already implemented in preCICE and presented to the end-user in [XML reference](#)². More details about the configuration and user-level optimization steps related to convergence criteria will be provided in [Sect. 3.2](#).

The implicit coupling schemes are related to their explicit counterparts, as they can be seen as multiple calls to an explicit coupling until convergence in a sub-iteration loop. This is clearly highlighted when comparing the different illustrations presented for the explicit and implicit schemes. Thus, they inherit the same stability issues as explicit schemes [48, 63, 104]. Therefore, it is highly recommended as stated in the [preCICE documentation](#)³ to use an *acceleration* method.

The sub-iteration process of implicit coupling schemes is based on fixed-point iterations and requires each participant to solve the same time step multiple times under updated coupling boundary conditions. To guarantee the validity of this procedure, preCICE employs the concept of a *checkpoint*, defined as a saved, fully converged state of the coupled system that serves as a reliable fallback in time during iterative coupling. At the beginning of each new sub-iteration, participants must be able to revert to such a checkpoint if the convergence criterion is not met. Acceleration methods are introduced specifically to retain information from previous iterations, thereby enabling the process to restart from an improved initial guess. Without them, the sub-iteration process would always restart from the last converged state, meaning the procedure would be equivalent to an explicit coupling scheme repeated multiple times. By enforcing rollbacks to the last converged interface values, checkpoints ensure that each iteration starts from a consistent and physically admissible state, thereby preventing the accumulation of errors or instabilities.

²<https://precice.org/configuration-xml-reference.html>

³<https://precice.org/configuration-coupling.html>

3.1.2.2 Acceleration methods for implicit coupling schemes

Several methods exist in preCICE to accelerate the convergence of implicit coupling schemes and to stabilize them [48, 85, 87]: constant under-relaxation, AITKEN relaxation and two interface quasi-NEWTON (IQN) variants.

Constant under-relaxation and Aitken relaxation *Constant under-relaxation* is a simple acceleration method that combines the output of the fixed-point iteration with the previous solution to obtain the next solution. For a given coupling variable \mathbf{x} , the acceleration step is defined as:

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = (1 - \alpha) \mathbf{x}_k + \alpha \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} = \mathbf{x}_k + \alpha \mathbf{r}_{k+1} \quad (3.6)$$

where $\alpha \in]0, 1[$ is the under-relaxation factor and $\mathbf{r}_{k+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} - \mathbf{x}_{k+1}$ the fixed-point residual. Note that if α is close to 0, the convergence is slow but the overall stability is increased. The opposite applies if α is close to 1, where the convergence is fast but the overall stability is decreased. The optimal value for α is problem-dependent and must be set empirically.

The *AITKEN relaxation* technique can be seen as a generalization of the previous method as it tries to improve the convergence rate of the fixed-point iteration by using a dynamic relaxation factor α_k at each sub-iteration k . This method is derived from AITKEN's Δ^2 ("Delta-squared") process [3], a technique for accelerating the convergence of a sequence, which is particularly useful in iterative fixed-point methods. A possible formulation of the relaxation factor at sub-iteration k is given by GATZHAMMER [48]:

$$\alpha_k = -\alpha_{k-1} \frac{\mathbf{r}_k^\top (\mathbf{r}_{k+1} - \mathbf{r}_k)}{\|\mathbf{r}_{k+1} - \mathbf{r}_k\|_2^2} \quad (3.7)$$

It can then be used in place of the constant relaxation factor α in **Eq. (3.6)**. The particular formulation given in **Eq. (3.7)** was first proposed by IRONS et al. [58]. Alternative formulations are explored in [64, 69]. Note that the first time step requires an initialization value α_{init} to start the process. In the following time steps, GATZHAMMER [48] suggests the following relation to initialize sub-iterations:

$$\alpha_0 = \max(\alpha_k^{n-1}, \alpha_{\text{init}}) \quad (3.8)$$

where α_k^{n-1} is the relaxation factor used in the previous time step $n - 1$ at sub-iteration k . **Algo. 5** summarizes the Block GAUSS–SEIDEL procedure with AITKEN under-relaxation. Note that the same procedure can be applied to the Block JACOBI scheme by replacing the structure variables \mathbf{s} with the concatenated vector $\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{f})^\top$.

Interface Quasi-Newton (IQN) acceleration preCICE provides two variants of the *interface quasi-NEWTON (IQN)* method: **IQN-ILS** (*interface-quasi-NEWTON with inverse Jacobian from a least-squares model*) and **IQN-IMVJ** (*interface-quasi-NEWTON with inverse multi-vector Jacobian updates*). These acceleration techniques have proven particularly effective for

Algorithm 5 Block GAUSS–SEIDEL procedure with AITKEN under-relaxation. n is the time step index and k the sub-iteration index, with \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{S} the fluid and structure operators. α_{init} is the initial relaxation factor [48]. In this example, the acceleration step is only applied to the structure variables \mathbf{s} (e.g., displacements) by construction of the GAUSS–SEIDEL scheme.

```

1: for  $n = 0, 1, \dots, n_{\text{max}}$  do
2:   Let  $\mathbf{s}_0 = \mathbf{s}_n$ 
3:    $k = 0$ 
4:   if  $n = 0$  then
5:      $\alpha_0 = \alpha_{\text{init}}$  ▷ Initialize the relaxation factor.
6:   else
7:      $\alpha_0 = \max(\alpha_k^{n-1}, \alpha_{\text{init}})$  ▷ Construct the relaxation factor with Eq. (3.8).
8:   end if
9:   while not converged do
10:    Solve  $\mathbf{f}_{k+1} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{s}_k)$ .
11:    Solve  $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+1} = \mathcal{S}(\mathbf{f}_{k+1})$ .
12:    Compute the fixed-point residual  $\mathbf{r}_{k+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+1} - \mathbf{s}_k$ .
13:    if  $k > 0$  then
14:      Compute the relaxation factor  $\alpha_k$  using Eq. (3.7).
15:    end if
16:    Update the structure variables  $\mathbf{s}_{k+1} = \mathbf{s}_k + \alpha_k \mathbf{r}_{k+1}$ . ▷ Acceleration step.
17:     $k = k + 1$ 
18:  end while
19: end for

```

FSI simulations [85, 100], which justifies a more detailed discussion. Both variants build upon the NEWTON-RAPHSON scheme, which forms the foundation of the IQN methods [48]. This section starts with a presentation of this underlying scheme, then the principles of the two IQN variants are described. Finally, a review of improvements related to the implementation of these methods by the preCICE team [28, 48, 85, 100] is presented. Before diving into the details, some notations are introduced to simplify the following developments.

The fixed-point iteration for both the JACOBI (**J**) and GAUSS–SEIDEL (**GS**) coupling schemes can be expressed in a unified form as:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l}
 \text{(J)} : \left[\begin{array}{cc} \mathbf{0} & \mathcal{S} \\ \mathcal{F} & \mathbf{0} \end{array} \right] \left[\begin{array}{c} \mathbf{s} \\ \mathbf{f} \end{array} \right] = \left[\begin{array}{c} \mathbf{s} \\ \mathbf{f} \end{array} \right] \\
 \text{(GS)} : \mathcal{S} \circ \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{s}) = \mathbf{s}
 \end{array} \right\} \implies \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x} \quad , \quad (3.9)$$

where $\mathcal{H} : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^N$ denotes the fixed-point iteration operator at the FSI coupling interface, and N the number of unknowns in \mathbf{x} . For the JACOBI scheme, \mathbf{x} corresponds to the concatenated vector $(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{f})^\top$, while for GAUSS–SEIDEL \mathbf{x} simply equals to \mathbf{s} . The residual operator can be defined as: $\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}) := \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{x}$. Its matrix representation in the state space defined by the coupling variable is denoted as $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{M}_N(\mathbb{R})$. The fixed point is then reached when $\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{0}$. As a throwback to previous notations, it can be noted that the fixed-point residual for the

coupling sub-iteration k is given by $\mathbf{r}_k = \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}_k)$. Note that the notations used in this section mainly focus on FSI problems, considering only fluid and structure as simulation components. However, the presented methods remain applicable to other multi-physics problems involving more than two components.

All the methods introduced after this point rely on an approximation of the Jacobian matrix $\mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{R}}$ or its inverse to accelerate the convergence of the fixed-point iterations. The Jacobian matrix is defined as follows for the sake of completeness:

$$\mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathbf{x}) := \left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{R}}{\partial x_1}(\mathbf{x}), \frac{\partial \mathcal{R}}{\partial x_2}(\mathbf{x}), \dots, \frac{\partial \mathcal{R}}{\partial x_N}(\mathbf{x}) \right] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathcal{R}_1}{\partial x_1}(\mathbf{x}) & \cdots & \frac{\partial \mathcal{R}_1}{\partial x_N}(\mathbf{x}) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{R}_N}{\partial x_1}(\mathbf{x}) & \cdots & \frac{\partial \mathcal{R}_N}{\partial x_N}(\mathbf{x}) \end{bmatrix}$$

To better contextualize quasi-NEWTON methods, it is important to explain the underlying principles of the original NEWTON method for fixed-point iterations and its limitations.

The Newton–Raphson acceleration scheme The primary goal of all acceleration methods is to reduce the number of coupling iterations, as evaluating \mathcal{H} is extremely costly. NEWTON-RAPHSON schemes (hereafter referred to as NEWTON) exploit the Jacobian matrix of the residual operator $\mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{R}}$ in order to accelerate the convergence of fixed-point iterations. The NEWTON approach seeks the root of the residual equation $\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{0}$ under the assumption that \mathcal{R} behaves locally in a linear fashion. The corresponding iterative process and state update can be expressed as [48, 85, 87]:

$$\mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathbf{x}_k) \Delta \mathbf{x}_k = -\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}_k) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{x}_k + \Delta \mathbf{x}_k. \quad (3.10)$$

The main computational challenge lies in computing the Jacobian matrices required at each iteration, which can be prohibitively expensive. FANG et al. [43], as cited by SCHEUFELE [85], report that for certain problems the standard NEWTON scheme, as expressed in **Eq. (3.10)**, becomes impractical due to its high computational cost. Such cases typically involve high-dimensional state spaces, the absence of an analytical Jacobian (or its prohibitively expensive computation), costly evaluations of the residual operator \mathcal{R} , and significant noise in its evaluation. Furthermore, when solvers are treated as black boxes, the Jacobian matrix is generally unavailable to the coupling framework.

To address these issues, one possible solution is to use an approximation of the Jacobian matrix. This is precisely the motivation behind the *Interface Quasi-NEWTON* methods, which aim to provide both fast convergence and stability [53, 85].

Common basis for Interface Quasi-Newton (IQN) numerical methods The methods introduced later in this section can be defined as *multi-secant* schemes, as they build an approximation of a Jacobian matrix (or its inverse) based on multiple *secant* equations. These conditions can be formulated, for instance, for the Jacobian matrix of the residual operator \mathcal{R} as:

$$\mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{R}} \Delta \mathbf{x}_k^i \approx \Delta \mathbf{r}_k^i \quad \text{with } i < k \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{cases} \Delta \mathbf{x}_k^i = \mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{x}_i \\ \Delta \mathbf{r}_k^i = \mathbf{r}_k - \mathbf{r}_i = \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}_k) - \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}_i) \end{cases} .$$

Early developments relevant to the introduction of quasi-NEWTON methods in the context of partitioned FSI simulations include the technique later known as ANDERSON acceleration [4] and the generalized BROYDEN methods proposed by EYERT [39], building on the work of BROYDEN [17].

Both approaches accelerate fixed-point iterations by incorporating information from previous coupling steps, but from different perspectives: ANDERSON [4] acceleration is often interpreted as a residual mixing strategy that implicitly enforces all available secant conditions, while BROYDEN's update [17] explicitly constructs an approximate Jacobian (or its inverse) that satisfies only a limited number of secant equations. In this sense, ANDERSON acceleration can be shown to be mathematically equivalent to a generalized BROYDEN scheme using all past iterations, which explains why both approaches are commonly grouped under the umbrella of *multi-secant* formulations.

These theoretical developments gave rise to the practical interface quasi-NEWTON (IQN) methods widely used in partitioned FSI. The **IQN-ILS** method, introduced through the work of VIERENDEELS et al. [103] and DEGROOTE et al. [33], corresponds to an ANDERSON-type formulation employing least-squares residual minimization. The **IQN-IMVJ** method, by contrast, follows the generalized BROYDEN interpretation by constructing and updating an approximate Jacobian (inverse) from multiple secant conditions, as described by BOGAERS [14]. For a more mathematical and historical overview of quasi-NEWTON methods, HAELTERMANN [53] provides a detailed account. The developments necessary to understand the current implementation of quasi-NEWTON schemes in preCICE build upon the work of GATZHAMMER [48], UEKERMANN [100], SCHEUFELE [85, 87], and DAVIS [28], among other publications by the preCICE team. The following developments are taken from these sources and will be cited along the way.

A few rewriting steps are necessary to express the NEWTON iteration in a form suitable for multi-secant approximations. Let $\tilde{\cdot}$ denote the output of the fixed-point iteration, such that $\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k) = \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k$, with k the sub-iteration index and $\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}_k) = \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k) - \mathbf{x}_k$. The residual operator

can then be expressed in terms of the inverse of the fixed-point map \mathcal{H}^{-1} as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}_k) &= \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k) - \mathbf{x}_k \\
 &= \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k) - \mathcal{H}^{-1}(\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k)) \\
 &= \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k - \mathcal{H}^{-1}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k) \\
 &= \widetilde{\mathcal{R}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k).
 \end{aligned}$$

It is then possible to rewrite the NEWTON iteration in **Eq. (3.10)** using the Jacobian matrix $\mathbf{J}_{\widetilde{\mathcal{R}}}$ of $\widetilde{\mathcal{R}}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{x}_{k+1} &= \mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{R}}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_k) \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}_k) \\
 &= \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k + \mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{R}}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_k) \widetilde{\mathcal{R}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k) \\
 &= \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k - (\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k - \mathbf{x}_k) - \mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{R}}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_k) \widetilde{\mathcal{R}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k) \\
 &= \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k - \underbrace{(\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{R}}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_k))}_{\mathbf{J}_{\widetilde{\mathcal{R}}}^{-1}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k)} \widetilde{\mathcal{R}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k) \\
 &= \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k - \mathbf{J}_{\widetilde{\mathcal{R}}}^{-1}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k) \widetilde{\mathcal{R}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k)
 \end{aligned}$$

To show that $\mathbf{J}_{\widetilde{\mathcal{R}}}^{-1}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k) = (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{R}}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_k))$, one can demonstrate that $(\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{R}}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_k)) \mathbf{J}_{\widetilde{\mathcal{R}}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k) = \mathbf{I}$. To avoid any confusion, note that $\mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{R}}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_k)$ (or similar objects) is a matrix, and not a vector as the notation might suggest. It is the inverse Jacobian matrix of \mathcal{R} evaluated at \mathbf{x}_k . The proof is as follows⁴:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{R}}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_k)) \mathbf{J}_{\widetilde{\mathcal{R}}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k) &= (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{J}_{\widetilde{\mathcal{R}} \circ \mathcal{H}}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_k)) \mathbf{J}_{\widetilde{\mathcal{R}}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k) \quad \text{since } \mathcal{R} = \widetilde{\mathcal{R}} \circ \mathcal{H} \\
 &= \left(\mathbf{I} + \left(\mathbf{J}_{\widetilde{\mathcal{R}}}(\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k)) \mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{H}}(\mathbf{x}_k) \right)^{-1} \right) \mathbf{J}_{\widetilde{\mathcal{R}}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k) \\
 &= \left(\mathbf{I} + \left(\mathbf{J}_{\widetilde{\mathcal{R}}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k) \mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{H}}(\mathbf{x}_k) \right)^{-1} \right) \mathbf{J}_{\widetilde{\mathcal{R}}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k) \\
 &= \mathbf{J}_{\widetilde{\mathcal{R}}}^{-1}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k) + \mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{H}}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_k) \underbrace{\left(\mathbf{J}_{\widetilde{\mathcal{R}}}^{-1}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k) \mathbf{J}_{\widetilde{\mathcal{R}}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k) \right)}_{=\mathbf{I}} \\
 &= \mathbf{J}_{\widetilde{\mathcal{R}}}^{-1}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k) + \mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{H}}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_k) \\
 &= \mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{I} - \mathcal{H}^{-1}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k) + \mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{H}}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_k) \quad \text{since } \widetilde{\mathcal{R}} = \mathbf{I} - \mathcal{H}^{-1} \\
 &= \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{H}^{-1}}(\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k)) + \mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{H}}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_k) \\
 &= \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{H}}^{-1}(\mathcal{H}^{-1}(\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k))) + \mathbf{J}_{\mathcal{H}}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_k) \quad \text{since } \mathbf{J}_{f^{-1}}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{J}_f^{-1}(f^{-1}(\mathbf{x})) \\
 &= \mathbf{I}.
 \end{aligned}$$

The subsequent step consists in constructing an approximation of $\mathbf{J}_{\widetilde{\mathcal{R}}}^{-1}$, denoted $\widehat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1}$, using information from previous coupling iterations in a multi-secant fashion, i.e., $\widehat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1} \mathbf{V}_k^\eta = \mathbf{W}_k^\eta$, with

⁴This proof was suggested by Prof. Miriam SCHULTE from the University of Stuttgart after informal exchanges.

$(\mathbf{V}_k^\eta, \mathbf{W}_k^\eta) \in \mathfrak{M}_{N,\eta}(\mathbb{R})$. The matrices \mathbf{V}_k^η and \mathbf{W}_k^η store input-output difference vectors from previous NEWTON iterations and are defined as:

$$\mathbf{W}_k^\eta = [\Delta \tilde{x}_k^{k-1}, \Delta \tilde{x}_k^{k-2}, \dots, \Delta \tilde{x}_k^{k-\eta}] \quad \text{with} \quad \Delta \tilde{x}_k^i = \tilde{x}_k - \tilde{x}_i = \mathcal{H}(\tilde{x}_k) - \mathcal{H}(\tilde{x}_i), \quad (3.11)$$

$$\mathbf{V}_k^\eta = [\Delta \mathbf{r}_k^{k-1}, \Delta \mathbf{r}_k^{k-2}, \dots, \Delta \mathbf{r}_k^{k-\eta}] \quad \text{with} \quad \Delta \mathbf{r}_k^i = \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}_k) - \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}_i). \quad (3.12)$$

The parameter $0 \leq \eta \leq k$ controls the amount of information from previous coupling iterations that is incorporated into the approximation. As noted by SCHEUFELE [85], information from previous *time steps* can also be included in \mathbf{V}_k^η and \mathbf{W}_k^η . In this notation, η is bounded by $k + \sum_{q \in [0, n-1]} k_q$, where n is the number of elapsed time steps and k_q denotes the number of coupling sub-iterations at time step q . For many applications, the assumption that $\eta \ll N$ holds true, which leads to the system $\hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1} \mathbf{V}_k^\eta = \mathbf{W}_k^\eta$ being underdetermined. To find a unique solution, the inverse Jacobian approximation is computed as the solution of the following norm-minimization problem [28, 85]:

$$\min_{\hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1}} \left\{ \left\| \hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1} - \hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1} \right\|_F \right\} \quad \text{subject to} \quad \hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1} \mathbf{V}_k^\eta = \mathbf{W}_k^\eta \quad (3.13)$$

with $\|\cdot\|_F$ denoting the FROBENIUS norm and $\hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1}$ a previous approximation or initial guess. The choice of the initial guess $\hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1}$ allows to differentiate between **IQN-ILS** and **IQN-IMVJ** as explained later. In the following developments, \mathbf{V}_k^η and \mathbf{W}_k^η will be simply written as \mathbf{V}_k and \mathbf{W}_k , respectively. To obtain the update formula for the inverse Jacobian approximation, the norm-minimization problem given in **Eq. (3.13)** can be reformulated into an unconstrained optimization problem using LAGRANGE multipliers. In this context, the Lagrangian can be written as:

$$\mathcal{L}(\hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1}, \lambda) = \frac{1}{2} \left\| \hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1} - \hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1} \right\|_F^2 + \lambda \left(\hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1} \mathbf{V}_k - \mathbf{W}_k \right). \quad (3.14)$$

The KKT (KARUSH-KUHN-TUCKER) conditions [62] for this optimization problem can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} \nabla_{\hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1}} \mathcal{L} = \hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1} - \hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1} + \lambda \mathbf{V}_k^\top = \mathbf{0} \\ \nabla_{\lambda} \mathcal{L} = \hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1} \mathbf{V}_k - \mathbf{W}_k = \mathbf{0} \end{cases}. \quad (3.15)$$

The optimality conditions given in **Eq. (3.15)** can be rearranged to obtain an expression for the LAGRANGE multiplier λ that satisfies the given constraints:

$$\lambda = -(\mathbf{W}_k - \hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1} \mathbf{V}_k) \left(\mathbf{V}_k^\top \mathbf{V}_k \right)^{-1}. \quad (3.16)$$

This yields the generic update formula with which both **IQN-ILS** and **IQN-IMVJ** can be derived:

$$\hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1} = \hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1} + (\mathbf{W}_k - \hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1} \mathbf{V}_k) \left(\mathbf{V}_k^\top \mathbf{V}_k \right)^{-1} \mathbf{V}_k^\top = \hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1} + \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_k \mathbf{V}_k^\dagger, \quad (3.17)$$

with $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_k := \mathbf{W}_k - \hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1} \mathbf{V}_k$ and $\mathbf{V}_k^\dagger := \left(\mathbf{V}_k^\top \mathbf{V}_k \right)^{-1} \mathbf{V}_k^\top$, the MOORE-PENROSE pseudo-inverse [53] of \mathbf{V}_k . This leads to the current formulation as implemented in preCICE by SCHEUFELE

[85] for both **IQN-ILS** and **IQN-IMVJ**.

Differences between IQN-ILS and IQN-IMVJ The *least-squares* (**IQN-ILS**) approach exploits all available information from the current time step by setting $\eta = k$ in the definitions of \mathbf{V}_k and \mathbf{W}_k from **Eq. (3.11)** and **Eq. (3.12)**. It can also incorporate information from previous time windows, a technique also labeled as *recycling*. As explained before, \mathbf{V}_k and \mathbf{W}_k are expanded to receive additional columns with information from earlier time steps, in addition to information from previous coupling sub-iterations in the current time step. In this setting, the initial inverse Jacobian approximation is set to zero, $\hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1} = \mathbf{0}$, so that the update rule in **Eq. (3.17)** reduces to:

$$\hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1} = \mathbf{W}_k \left(\mathbf{V}_k^\top \mathbf{V}_k \right)^{-1} \mathbf{V}_k^\top = \mathbf{W}_k \mathbf{V}_k^\dagger, \quad (3.18)$$

Since no prior Jacobian approximation is used, the quality of $\hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1}$ depends entirely on the retained input/output data. As noted by SCHEUFELE [85], the optimal choice of η is problem-dependent and requires careful tuning: retaining too much information can degrade the conditioning of **Eq. (3.18)** due to linearly dependent columns from redundant or outdated data.

This formulation admits a *matrix-free* implementation, which avoids explicit construction of $\hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1}$ [51, 52]. Instead, its action on the residual vector $\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}_k) = \mathbf{r}^k$ can be computed directly as $\mathbf{W}_k \mathbf{V}_k^\dagger (-\mathbf{r}^k) = -\mathbf{W}_k \alpha$. The vector $\alpha = \mathbf{V}_k^\dagger \mathbf{r}^k$ is computed from the QR decomposition of \mathbf{V}_k with $\mathbf{V}_k = \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{R}$ with $\mathbf{R}\alpha = -\mathbf{Q}^\top \mathbf{r}^k$, where \mathbf{Q} is an orthogonal matrix and \mathbf{R} is an upper triangular matrix. The resulting update is: $\Delta \mathbf{x}^k = \mathbf{W}_k \alpha$ with $\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{x}_k + \Delta \mathbf{x}^k$.

In contrast to **IQN-ILS**, the *multi-vector* (**IMVJ**) approach searches for an approximate inverse Jacobian $\hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1}$ that remains close to the estimate from the previous time step. The current step $n + 1$ is initialized with the previous estimate $\hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1} = [\hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1}]_n$ and perform the k -th sub-iteration update on $\hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1}$ is simply the generic update formula given by **Eq. (3.17)** without any simplifications:

$$\hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1} = \underbrace{[\hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1}]_n}_{\hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1}} + \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_k \mathbf{V}_k^\dagger, \quad (3.19)$$

where \mathbf{V}_k and \mathbf{W}_k collect the last k residual and solution differences of the *current* time step, $\mathbf{V}_k^\dagger = (\mathbf{V}_k^\top \mathbf{V}_k)^{-1} \mathbf{V}_k^\top$ (computed via a QR factorization of \mathbf{V}_k), and $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_k := \mathbf{W}_k - \hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1} \mathbf{V}_k = \mathbf{W}_k - [\hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1}]_n \mathbf{V}_k$.

Since **Eq. (3.19)** uses $\hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1}$ explicitly, **IQN-IMVJ** is not straightforwardly matrix-free and without further measures entails $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ memory and computational complexity, which is prohibitively expensive for large-scale problems. At the same time, because information from the previous step is implicitly retained through $\hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1}$, the method can operate with a smaller number $\eta = k$ of retained iterations compared to **IQN-ILS**. To mitigate the memory and computational cost, several improvements to the basic **IQN-IMVJ** method have been proposed by SCHEUFELE

[28, 85], which are summarized in the following paragraph.

Starting from **Eq. (3.19)**, by unrolling the successive summations of $[\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_k \mathbf{V}_k^\dagger]_q$ with $q \in \llbracket 0, n-1 \rrbracket$ for the n -th time step into $\widehat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1}$, the computation of the initial Jacobian approximation can be approximated itself as an explicit sum by retaining only one pair of secant matrices per time step:

$$\widehat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1} \approx \sum_{q=0}^{n-1} [\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_k \mathbf{V}_k^\dagger]_q, \quad (3.20)$$

where $[\cdot]_q$ denotes the contribution accumulated during time step q (grouping all iterations of step q into one pair $(\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_{k_q}, \mathbf{V}_{k_q}^\dagger)$ from its last coupling iteration. This allows computing the NEWTON correction without explicitly forming $\widehat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1}$:

$$\Delta \mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k - \sum_{q=0}^{n-1} [\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_k]_q \left([\mathbf{V}_k^\dagger]_q \mathbf{r}_k \right), \quad (3.21)$$

i.e., by on-the-fly matrix-vector products with the stored pairs $([\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_k]_q, [\mathbf{V}_k^\dagger]_q)$. Further improvements can be made to this approach by introducing *restart* methods in order to bound the memory/computational cost of the methods as n grows. The overall simulation is partitioned into chunks of m time steps and the history is periodically condensed into a compact representation. At restart, the representation of $\widehat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1}$ is cleared and re-initialized with a well chosen $[\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_k \mathbf{V}_k^\dagger]_0$, so that it can be expressed as:

$$\widehat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1} = [\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_k \mathbf{V}_k^\dagger]_0 + \sum_{q=n-m}^n [\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_k \mathbf{V}_k^\dagger]_q. \quad (3.22)$$

The different restart strategies available in preCICE control how the history is retained and condensed when starting a new chunk:

- **RS-0** (clear-all): Discard all past information. Looking back at the update step written in **Eq. (3.21)**, the sum represents the action of $\widehat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1}$ on \mathbf{r}_k , which allows to compute the update $\Delta \mathbf{x}_{k+1}$. Using the restart method **RS-0**, this action can be written as:

$$\widehat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1} \mathbf{r}_k = \sum_{q=n-m}^n [\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_k]_q \left([\mathbf{V}_k^\dagger]_q \mathbf{r}_k \right) \quad (3.23)$$

with $(\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_k, \mathbf{V}_k^\dagger)$ explicitly retained from the last m time steps only. This forgets outdated data but typically degrades convergence [28, 85].

- **RS-LS**: Drop the sum representation but explicitly retain information from the $\xi < m$

time steps within the current chunk, so that the initial guess $\hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1}$ is given by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1} = \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_k^{\eta_\xi} \mathbf{V}_k^{\eta_\xi, \star} \quad \text{with} \quad \begin{cases} \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_k^{\eta_\xi} = [\mathbf{W}_{k_q}]_{q \in \llbracket n-\xi, n \rrbracket} \\ \mathbf{V}_k^{\eta_\xi, \star} = \hat{\mathbf{R}}^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{Q}}^\top \quad \text{from} \quad \mathbf{V}_k^{\eta_\xi} = [\mathbf{V}_{k_q}]_{q \in \llbracket n-\xi, n \rrbracket} \end{cases} \quad (3.24)$$

The notation $\hat{\mathbf{Q}} \hat{\mathbf{R}}$ for the QR-decomposition of $\mathbf{V}_k^{\eta_\xi}$ is explained in Section 2.2.2 of SCHEUFELE's thesis [85]. It represents the *economy-size QR-decomposition* for "tall and skinny" matrices, where only the first η_ξ columns of the orthogonal matrix $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathfrak{M}_N(\mathbb{R})$ and the upper $\eta_\xi \times \eta_\xi$ -block in $\mathbf{R} \in \mathfrak{M}_{N, \eta_\xi}(\mathbb{R})$ are retained.

- **RS-SVD:** Drop the sum representation but keep the dominant modes of the Jacobian inverse via a *truncated SVD* (Singular Value Decomposition):

$$\hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1} = \tilde{\Psi} \tilde{\Sigma} \tilde{\Phi}^\top = [\Psi_i]_{i \in \llbracket 1, \bar{\kappa} \rrbracket} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 & & & \\ & \sigma_2 & & \\ & & \ddots & \\ & & & \sigma_{\bar{\kappa}} \end{bmatrix} [\Phi_i]_{i \in \llbracket 1, \bar{\kappa} \rrbracket} \quad (3.25)$$

where only the $\bar{\kappa}$ largest singular values based on cutoff threshold ε_{SVD} are retained from the SVD decomposition of the previous Jacobian approximation $\hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1} = \Psi \Sigma \Phi^\top$. To make this approach practical, an efficient low-rank SVD update is implemented in preCICE [85].

Improvements to the implementation of IQN methods Several measures can be implemented to improve the performance of **IQN** methods in terms of robustness, efficiency, and memory consumption. One such measure was already introduced as *recycling* for **IQN-ILS**, where a fixed number of previous converged time steps are incorporated into \mathbf{V}_k and \mathbf{W}_k . **IQN-IMVJ** already incorporates a form of recycling by construction as seen in the update rule given by **Eq. (3.19)**. SCHEUFELE et al. [86] showed that explicit retention of information beyond what is already kept by the method does not improve convergence. In the following paragraphs, additional improvements introduced by the preCICE team are explored.

The accuracy and performance of *multi-secant* methods may suffer from the accumulation of outdated information or linearly dependent columns in \mathbf{V}_k that arise from nonlinearities in the fixed-point mapping \mathcal{H} , rounding errors, convergence to steady states, or excessive reuse of history vectors η . To mitigate these issues, the use of *filtering* techniques was introduced into preCICE. They appear during the computation of the QR-decomposition of \mathbf{V}_k to identify and remove potentially problematic columns. The actual procedure used to perform this operation during the coupling iteration is a critical step in terms of performance. It was developed by UEKERMANN [100] and later improved by SCHEUFELE [85] under the term *QR-update scheme*. DAVIS [28] in Section 2.2.4 of his work provides a summary of the procedure. Three filtering

methods are currently available in preCICE since version 3.2: **QR1**, **QR2** [85], and **QR3** [28]:

- **QR1** – Initially introduced by DEGROOTE [33], the **QR1** filtering step evaluates the linear dependency of a new column compared to previous columns in \mathbf{V}_k by comparing the diagonal elements of \mathbf{R} to its FROBENIUS norm via a numerical threshold ε_f . A column i is deleted if the element $\mathbf{R}_{ii} < \varepsilon_f \|\mathbf{R}\|_F$ with \mathbf{R} being the upper triangular matrix from the QR decomposition [85].
- **QR2** – Initially introduced by HAELTERMANN [50], the **QR2** filtering uses the norm of a column after orthogonalization compared to the norm before orthogonalization during the QR-decomposition as a mean to quantify the amount of new information added decide whether to keep or discard it. This filter has a tendency to remove older columns [28].
- **QR3** – Introduced by DAVIS [28] for preCICE, it builds upon **QR2** to improve the performance of the QR-decomposition step. The procedure is split into three steps: (i) The newest column integrated in \mathbf{V}_k is inserted into an existing QR-decomposition; (ii) A column i is tagged for removal if it satisfies the condition $\mathbf{R}_{ii} < \varepsilon_f \|\mathbf{V}_{k,(:,i)}\|_2$, where $\mathbf{V}_{k,(:,i)}$ contains the i -th column of \mathbf{V}_k ; (iii) If at least one column is tagged for removal, a normal **QR2** filtering step is performed instead.

In parallel to the filtering steps, *pre-scaling* can be employed when dealing with a JACOBI-type coupling scheme. The different components in the concatenated coupling vector \mathbf{x} may have very different characteristic time scales (e.g., pressure waves vs. structural displacements). This disparity can lead to a poor conditioning of the overall system. By applying a *preconditioner* to the individual components, this issue can be mitigated. UEKERMANN [100] implemented the use of *per-sub-vector* pre-scaling on \mathbf{V}_k and \mathbf{r}_k . This modifies the vectors as follows:

$$\mathbf{V}'_k = \mathbf{\Lambda}_k \mathbf{V}_k \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{r}'_k = \mathbf{\Lambda}_k \mathbf{r}_k \quad (3.26)$$

with $\mathbf{\Lambda}_k = \text{diag}(\lambda_k^1, \dots, \lambda_k^N)$ with N the total number of entries in \mathbf{x}_k . The weights λ_k^i are chosen to normalize the entries in the concatenated vector $\mathbf{x}_k = (\mathbf{s}_k, \mathbf{f}_k)^\top$. As the name suggest, the same rescaling is applied to all components of a given sub-vector (e.g., \mathbf{s}_k or \mathbf{f}_k). Several approaches are available in preCICE, the most robust according to UEKERMANN [100] is labeled as *residual-sum* and it yields the following expression for the scaling factors in the context of FSI simulation:

$$\lambda_k^s = \left(\sum_{j=1}^k \frac{\|\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{f}_k^j) - \mathbf{f}_k^j\|}{\|\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k^j) - \mathbf{x}_k^j\|} \right)^{-1} \quad \text{and} \quad \lambda_k^f = \left(\sum_{j=1}^k \frac{\|\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{s}_k^j) - \mathbf{s}_k^j\|}{\|\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k^j) - \mathbf{x}_k^j\|} \right)^{-1}. \quad (3.27)$$

The JACOBI system would then appear as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \lambda_k^s \mathcal{S} \\ \lambda_k^f \mathcal{F} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{s} \\ \mathbf{f} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_k^s \mathbf{s} \\ \lambda_k^f \mathbf{f} \end{bmatrix}.$$

SCHEUFELE [85] highlights that this rescaling approach requires a computation of the QR-decomposition from scratch at each coupling iterations, since the weights are recomputed for each iteration. When using **IQN-ILS**, the pre-scaling step needs to be reverted to maintain a consistent information history. **IQN-IMVJ** requires some modifications in its update rule to implement this change [85].

To conclude this section, the pseudo-codes for **IQN-ILS** and **IQN-IMVJ** with pre-scaling and filtering procedures are presented in **Algo. 6** and **Algo. 7**, respectively. These algorithms summarize the key steps introduced above and are applicable to both GAUSS–SEIDEL and JACOBI coupling schemes. At each time step $n + 1$, the coupling iteration begins with an initial guess \mathbf{x}_0 (typically the solution from the previous time step). The fixed-point mapping \mathcal{H} is then evaluated to obtain $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0$ and the corresponding residual \mathbf{r}_0 . An initial under-relaxation step with a constant factor α_{init} is performed to compute the first iterate \mathbf{x}_1 .

The subsequent coupling iterations proceed until convergence or until the maximum number of iterations k_{max} is reached. During this process, the history matrices \mathbf{V}_k and \mathbf{W}_k are constructed and progressively enriched with the latest difference vectors. Intermediate storage of these objects is done by preCICE for every coupling iterations based on configuration parameters and it is not shown on the different algorithms. Pre-scaling weights $\mathbf{\Lambda}_k$ are then computed and applied to \mathbf{V}_k and \mathbf{r}_k , after which a QR-decomposition of the pre-scaled matrix $\mathbf{\Lambda}_k \mathbf{V}_k$ is performed. The pre-scaling step has far reaching consequences in the implementation as explained by SCHEUFELE [85]. Most notably, the pre-scaling must be reverted when storing \mathbf{V}_k and \mathbf{W}_k to maintain a coherent history. A filtering step (e.g., QR1, QR2, or QR3) follows to remove nearly linearly dependent columns, ensuring numerical stability. The QR-decomposition and its update during the coupling iterations are critical steps in term of numerical stability. SCHEUFELE [85] provides a detailed analysis of the actual implementation to minimize the cost of the procedure during the iteration process by leveraging an efficient QR-update scheme.

After filtering, the subsequent operations depend on the chosen quasi-NEWTON variant. In the case of **IQN-ILS**, the update $\Delta \mathbf{x}_{k+1}$ is obtained via a matrix-free approach that avoids explicit construction of the approximate inverse Jacobian. In contrast, **IQN-IMVJ** computes $\Delta \mathbf{x}_{k+1}$ based on the selected restart strategy (**RS-0**, **RS-LS**, or **RS-SVD**). The coupling iteration continues with the update of the coupling variable \mathbf{x}_{k+1} until convergence. More specific pseudo-code overviews are presented in SCHEUFELE’s [85] and DAVIS’ [28] dissertations.

Algorithm 6 pseudo-code for IQN-ILS [28, 85] with pre-scaling and filtering procedures. Note that the time step index n is omitted for clarity in the coupling loop. Note that the first coupling iteration uses constant under-relaxation with a factor α_{init} given as an input of the method.

```

for  $n = 0, 1, \dots, n_{\text{max}}$  do
  Initialize coupling iteration:  $k = 1, \mathbf{x}_0$ .
   $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0 = \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_0)$  and  $\mathbf{r}_0 = \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0 - \mathbf{x}_0$ .
   $\mathbf{x}_1 = \mathbf{x}_0 + \alpha_{\text{init}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0 - \mathbf{x}_0)$  ▷ Initial under-relaxation step.
  while not converged and  $k < k_{\text{max}}$  do
     $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k = \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k)$  and  $\mathbf{r}_k = \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}_k) = \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k - \mathbf{x}_k$ .
     $\Delta \mathbf{r}_k = \mathbf{r}_k - \mathbf{r}_{k-1}$  and  $\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k = \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1}$ .
    Append  $\Delta \mathbf{r}_k$  and  $\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k$  to  $\mathbf{V}_{k-1}$  and  $\mathbf{W}_{k-1}$  to construct  $\mathbf{V}_k$  and  $\mathbf{W}_k$ .
    Compute the pre-scaling weights  $\Lambda_k$ .
    Compute the QR-decomposition  $\Lambda_k \mathbf{V}_k = \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{R}$  and filter.
    Solve  $\mathbf{R} \alpha = -\mathbf{Q}^\top (\Lambda_k \mathbf{r}_k)$ .
    Compute  $\Delta \mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{W}_k \alpha$ .
    Update:  $x_{k+1} = x_k + \Delta x_{k+1}$ .
     $k \leftarrow k + 1$ .
  end while
end for
    
```

Algorithm 7 pseudo-code for IQN-IMVJ [28, 85] with pre-scaling and filtering procedures. Note that the time step index n is omitted for clarity in the coupling loop. Note that the first coupling iteration uses constant under-relaxation with a factor α_{init} given as an input of the method.

```

for  $n = 0, 1, \dots, n_{\text{max}}$  do
  Initialize coupling iteration:  $k = 1, \mathbf{x}_0$ .
   $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0 = \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_0)$  and  $\mathbf{r}_0 = \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0 - \mathbf{x}_0$ .
   $\mathbf{x}_1 = \mathbf{x}_0 + \alpha_{\text{init}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0 - \mathbf{x}_0)$  ▷ Initial under-relaxation step.
  while not converged and  $k < k_{\text{max}}$  do
     $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k = \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k)$  and  $\mathbf{r}_k = \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}_k) = \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k - \mathbf{x}_k$ .
     $\Delta \mathbf{r}_k = \mathbf{r}_k - \mathbf{r}_{k-1}$  and  $\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k = \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1}$ .
    Append  $\Delta \mathbf{r}_k$  and  $\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k$  to  $\mathbf{V}_{k-1}$  and  $\mathbf{W}_{k-1}$  to construct  $\mathbf{V}_k$  and  $\mathbf{W}_k$ .
    Compute the pre-scaling weights  $\Lambda_k$ .
    Compute the QR-decomposition  $\Lambda_k \mathbf{V}_k = \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{R}$  and filter.
    Solve  $\mathbf{R} \mathbf{V}_k^\dagger = \mathbf{Q}^\top$ .
    Update  $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_k = \mathbf{W}_k - \hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1} \mathbf{V}_k$  with  $\hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1}$  computed according to the selected restart
    strategy.
    Update  $\hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1} = \mathbf{W}_k - \tilde{\mathbf{W}}_k \mathbf{V}_k^\dagger$ .
    Compute  $\Delta \mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \hat{\mathbf{J}}^{-1} \mathbf{r}_k$ .
    Update  $x_{k+1} = x_k + \Delta x_{k+1}$ .
     $k \leftarrow k + 1$ .
  end while
  if  $(n + 1) \bmod m = 0$  then ▷ Restart condition based on chunk size  $m$ .
    Perform restart according to the selected strategy.
  end if
end for
    
```

3.2 Implementation and configuration of coupling schemes in preCICE

This section provides an overview of the implementation of coupling methods and their integration into preCICE, along with the available configuration options. To better illustrate their role in a partitioned FSI simulation, we place coupling methods within the overall simulation loop and particularly in relation to mapping methods implemented in preCICE and introduced in [Chap. 2](#).

3.2.1 Review of the implementation of coupling methods in preCICE

In this section, the implementation details of the coupling methods in preCICE are presented in a similar fashion to the description of the mapping methods in [Sect. 2.2](#). Most of the content is based on the work of SCHEUFELE [85], who focused on improving quasi-NEWTON acceleration methods, and UEKERMANN [100], who developed the base implementation. The latter builds upon the work of GATZHAMMER [48], who implemented the first iteration of both explicit and implicit coupling schemes in preCICE, together with constant under-relaxation, AITKEN relaxation, and IQN-ILS acceleration methods.

As outlined in [Sect. 2.2](#), the different functionalities of preCICE are organized into *packages*. The coupling schemes (**CSS**, **CPS**, **GS**, and **J**) are implemented in the `cplscheme` package, while the acceleration methods (constant under-relaxation, AITKEN relaxation, **IQN-ILS**, and **IQN-IMVJ**) are contained in the `acceleration` package.

The `cplscheme` package is responsible for managing the coupling workflow between two or more simulation participants. It serves as the central orchestrator for data exchange and synchronization, ensuring that all participants remain consistent during coupled simulations. Within `cplscheme`, the coupling schemes are implemented in an object-oriented manner. The interface `CouplingScheme.[cpp|hpp]` defines the public API⁵ common to all coupling methods, while the abstract class `BaseCouplingScheme` in `BaseCouplingScheme.[cpp|hpp]` provides shared logic and functionality. Specific coupling schemes inherit from these base classes to implement their scheme-specific behavior. This object-oriented design enables modularity and flexibility, allowing different functionalities to be combined with minimal code duplication.

The `cplscheme` package follows the same structural organization as the `mapping` package. The `config` folder contains code for parsing relevant options from the `precice-config.xml` configuration file. The `impl` folder provides implementations of additional functionalities, such as convergence measurements. A dedicated `test` folder contains unit tests to ensure the correctness of the coupling methods. The implementation of the various coupling schemes is located at the

⁵Application Programming Interface.

root of the package.

The base class `BaseCouplingScheme` is further specialized into two derived classes, which are named `BiCouplingScheme` and `MultiCouplingScheme`. The former handles coupling between two participants, while the latter supports coupling among more than two participants. Multi-participant coupling is outside the scope of this thesis, and the reader is referred to Chapter 3 of UEKERMANN’s work [100] for further details. The specific implementations of the parallel and serial schemes are done through the classes `ParallelCouplingScheme` and `SerialCouplingScheme` within their respective `. [cpp|hpp]`. In `CouplingData. [cpp|hpp]`, methods for handling data transfer during coupling steps are implemented.

Since UEKERMANN’s contribution, which introduced the implementation of parallel coupling schemes in preCICE, the overall architecture has evolved, with acceleration methods and related functions being migrated to a dedicated `acceleration` package. This package follows the same structural organization as `cplscheme`. The `impl` folder contains the implementation of several complementary methods, including various preconditioners for the **J** (JACOBI)-type coupling scheme and high-performance parallel matrix operations, which build upon functionality provided by the communication package `com`.

Within the `acceleration` package, the abstract base class `Acceleration` defines the common interface and shared functionality across all acceleration methods. Additional refinements and shared logic for quasi-NEWTON methods are encapsulated in the `BaseQNAcceleration` class. Each acceleration is implemented through a dedicated class: `ConstantUnderRelaxation`, `AitkenAcceleration`, `IQNILSAcceleration`, and `IQNIMVJAcceleration`. Each class inherits its attributes from the base class `Acceleration` to ensure a consistent interface and shared functionality.

Both the `cplscheme` and `acceleration` packages rely on data structures provided by the C++ standard library and the [Eigen library](https://eigen.tuxfamily.org/index.php?title=Main_Page)⁶.

3.2.2 Link between mapping and coupling steps

In **Chap. 2**, the mapping procedure was introduced in detail. It is therefore appropriate to examine the interaction between the mapping and coupling steps in preCICE. From the perspective of both the adapter developer and the end-user, these steps are to a large extent abstracted away.

Mapping and coupling operations are fully encapsulated within the preCICE API, specifically in the *steering* functions. **Fig. 3.3** illustrates the coupling flow between two participants for a serial implicit scheme, without loss of generality. The steering functions comprise `initialize`, `advance`, and `finalize`. Among these, `advance` plays a central role, as it orchestrates the

⁶https://eigen.tuxfamily.org/index.php?title=Main_Page

exchange of data between participants. This includes mesh-to-mesh mapping (as seen in the `map write data` and `map read data` annotations), inter-participant communication, and the execution of acceleration methods alongside coupling algorithm (hidden in the exchange step between `send data` and `receive data`). The mapping operations are performed before and after the coupling and exchange steps have taken place between the participants. The adapter developer is not required to explicitly address either procedures directly, since both are handled transparently by the preCICE API. The end-user merely specifies the desired methods in the `precice-config.xml` configuration file, which is parsed by preCICE at runtime.

Figure 3.3 – Example of FSI coupling between two participants in preCICE. This figure highlights the coupling procedure for a parallel scheme in preCICE. `initialize`, `advance` and `finalize` are methods from the preCICE API. Taken from the preCICE documentation⁷.

3.2.3 User-level configuration options

Most of the information presented in this section is derived from the official preCICE documentation on coupling schemes⁸ and from the XML reference for the `precice-config.xml` file⁹.

In the following, the term *time window* refers to the time interval between two converged states of the coupled system. For all practical purposes, since no subcycling is performed in the examples presented in this thesis, a time window corresponds to a single time step of the coupled simulation.

⁸<https://precice.org/configuration-coupling.html>

⁹<https://precice.org/configuration-xml-reference.html>

From the user's perspective, the configuration of coupling methods in preCICE is specified in the `precice-config.xml` file, located at the root of the simulation setup directory. A simplified outline of the different blocks to be configured is shown below:

```
<precice-configuration>
  <data .../>
  <mesh .../>
  <participant .../>
  <m2n .../>
  <coupling-scheme .../>
</precice-configuration>
```

The configuration options differ between implicit and explicit schemes. However, at the configuration level, no distinction is made between *parallel* and *serial* implementations. The coupling scheme is specified via the `coupling-scheme:{method}` tag, where `{method}` may take one of the following values: `serial-explicit`, `serial-implicit`, `parallel-explicit`, or `parallel-implicit`. Certain configuration parameters are common to both implicit and explicit schemes, while others are specific to one of them (e.g., acceleration methods for implicit schemes). Configuration examples for explicit and implicit coupling schemes are provided in **Lst. 3.1** and **Lst. 3.2**, respectively. The main options common to both types of schemes are:

- `participants` – Defines the participants involved in the coupling. The `first` and `second` attributes determine the execution order of the participants, which has a direct impact on the coupling process for serial schemes. This order is irrelevant for parallel explicit schemes, but significant for parallel implicit schemes, as convergence measurements and acceleration computations are carried out in the environment of the `second` participant.
- `max-time` – Specifies the maximum simulation time.
- `max-time-windows` – Sets the maximum number of time windows. Alternatively, the `max-time` tag may be used to limit the simulation duration.
- `time-window-size` – Defines the size of each time window, i.e., the coupling iterations. Additional options are available to reconcile different timesteps between participants. Specifically, the `time-window-size` can be adjusted as follows:

```
<time-window-size value="..." method="..."/>
```

where `method` can be either `fixed`, allowing each participant to use its own timestep and subcycle with coupling occurring at the end of each time window if it is able to do so, or `first-participant`, where the first participant prescribes the timestep for the other participant (in which case the `value` attribute is ignored). This configuration is described in detail in the [preCICE tutorial](https://precice.org/couple-your-code-time-step-sizes.html)¹⁰ on coupling solvers.

¹⁰<https://precice.org/couple-your-code-time-step-sizes.html>

- `exchange`: Specifies the data exchange settings between participants. This is directly related to the configuration of the mapping method described in **Sect. 2.2**. There must be as many `exchange` tags as there are fields to be transmitted between participants.

The example in **Lst. 3.1** illustrates the configuration of a serial explicit coupling scheme.

```
<coupling-scheme:{type}-explicit>
  <max-time value="{float}"/>
  <max-time-windows value="{integer}"/>
  <time-window-size value="-1" method="fixed"/>
  <participants first="{string}" second="{string}"/>
  <exchange data="{string}" mesh="{string}" from="{string}" to="{
    string}" />
</coupling-scheme:{type}-explicit>
```

Listing 3.1 – Configuration example for explicit coupling schemes from the preCICE documentation. The placeholder `{type}` should be replaced with either `serial` or `parallel`.

In the context of incompressible flow simulations for FSI, explicit schemes are not suitable due to their limitations in handling instabilities arising from the physical problem or the added-mass effect, as discussed in **Sect. 3.1**. Consequently, implicit coupling schemes are typically preferred in such cases.

```
<coupling-scheme:{type}-implicit>
  <max-time value="{float}"/>
  <max-time-windows value="{integer}"/>
  <time-window-size value="-1" method="fixed"/>
  <participants first="{string}" second="{string}"/>
  <exchange data="{string}" mesh="{string}" from="{string}" to="{string}" />
  <acceleration:{string}>
    ...
  </acceleration:{string}>
  <absolute-convergence-measure data="{string}" mesh="{string}" suffices="
    false" strict="false" limit="{float}"/>
  <absolute-or-relative-convergence-measure data="{string}" mesh="{string}"
    suffices="false" strict="false" abs-limit="{float}" rel-limit="{float}"/>
  <relative-convergence-measure data="{string}" mesh="{string}" suffices="
    false" strict="false" limit="{float}"/>
  <residual-relative-convergence-measure data="{string}" mesh="{string}"
    suffices="false" strict="false" limit="{float}"/>
  <min-iterations value="{integer}"/>
  <max-iterations value="{integer}"/>
```

```
</coupling-scheme:{type}-implicit>
```

Listing 3.2 – Configuration example for implicit coupling schemes from the preCICE documentation. No distinction exists between serial and implicit schemes in terms of configuration attributes. The placeholder `{type}` should be replaced with either `serial` or `parallel`.

As shown in **Lst. 3.2**, the configuration of implicit coupling schemes includes additional options related to convergence measures and acceleration methods. The common options with explicit schemes do not change. The `min-iterations` and `max-iterations` tags allow to control the number of coupling iterations. A paragraph will be dedicated to the most important options in implicit coupling schemes as they are quite rich in features and require careful considerations when building the simulation setup.

Configuration of acceleration methods The configuration of the *constant under-relaxation* acceleration method is the simplest, with only the `relaxation` tag being required to set the relaxation factor, as shown in **Lst. 3.3**. Note that this acceleration method is recommended for use with serial coupling schemes.

```
<acceleration:constant>
  <relaxation value="{float}"/>
</acceleration:constant>
```

Listing 3.3 – Configuration example for the constant acceleration method from the preCICE documentation.

The configuration of the AITKEN relaxation method is more complex, requiring additional parameters such as the initial relaxation factor, data scaling, and a preconditioner. An example configuration is shown in **Lst. 3.4**.

```
<acceleration:aitken>
  <initial-relaxation value="{float}"/>
  <data scaling="1" name="{string}" mesh="{string}"/>
  <preconditioner type="{string}" freeze-after="-1"/>
</acceleration:aitken>
```

Listing 3.4 – Configuration example for the AITKEN acceleration method from the preCICE documentation.

Within this configuration block delimited by `acceleration:aitken`, three types of subtags can be specified: `initial-relaxation`, `data`, and `preconditioner`. At least one `data` entry is mandatory, as it defines the field used to compute the acceleration. The `initial-relaxation` tag allows the user to define the starting relaxation factor via the attribute `value`, with a default of 0.5 if omitted. This parameter controls the first iteration before the dynamic Aitken update

adapts the factor as seen in **Sect. 3.1.2.2**.

The `data` tag specifies the data fields that are exchanged during the coupling procedure. Each entry must include a `name` (the identifier of the coupling quantity) and a `mesh` (the mesh containing that data). An optional `scaling` factor can also be provided, with a default of 1, but it is only relevant when the preconditioner type (see below) is set to `constant`. For all other preconditioner types, the `scaling` attribute is ignored. Since several data vectors can be involved in multi-physics *parallel* setups, each of them must be listed through separate `data` entries. For *serial* setups, only one `data` tag per field processed by the `second` participant is necessary. preCICE will raise an error if the `data` tags are not consistent with the current setup specified in the `precice-config.xml` file.

The `preconditioner` tag defines how different data vectors are scaled prior to computing the Aitken step, thus improving numerical stability. This concept is first explained in the present document when describing quasi-NEWTON methods in **Sect. 3.1.2.2**. It was introduced in preCICE mostly thanks to UERKERMANN’s work [100] (see Section 3.6.3 of his dissertation for a theoretical overview). Its attribute `type` may be one of four values. With `constant`, each vector is scaled by the manually provided `scaling` factor from its `data` entry. With a `value` preconditioner, vectors are automatically scaled by the norm of their previous time window values. With `residual`, scaling is based on the current residual, while with `residual-sum`, scaling is based on the rescaled sum of residuals in the current window. This last approach is considered the most robust and effective according to UERKERMANN [100] and SCHEUFELE [85]. This particular scaling procedure is explicitly cited in this report as **Eq. (3.27)**. A second attribute, `freeze-after`, controls when the adaptive behavior stops: after the given number of time windows, the preconditioner “freezes” and behaves like a `constant` preconditioner. The default value of -1 means no freezing is applied. In practice, it is recommended to use a preconditioner for automatic scaling rather than relying solely on manual constants.

The configuration of quasi-NEWTON methods is more complex, as they offer a lot of configuration options. The **IQN-ILS** accelerator is configured with the container tag `acceleration:IQN-ILS`. The layout of the options is presented in **Lst. 3.5**. A root-level attribute `reduced-time-grid` (`boolean`, default `true`) controls how the Jacobian approximation is assembled: when `true`, only the last time step of each time window contributes columns to the least-squares system (reduced grid); when `false`, all time steps in the window may be used (full grid), potentially improving information content at the cost of more memory consumption and ill-conditioning. This option is not mandatory. Inside the container, the valid subtags are: `initial-relaxation` $\in [0, 1]$, `max-used-iterations`, `time-windows-reused`, `data`, `filter`, and `preconditioner`. At least one `data` entry is mandatory, one per coupling field/mesh you wish to accelerate.

The `initial-relaxation value` subtag seeds the first update with a user-chosen relaxation

factor, similar to the `initial-relaxation` tag in the Aitken configuration. If omitted, the initial relaxation defaults to 0.1. The attribute `value` sets this factor, while `enforce` (default `false`) dictates whether this initial value is re-applied at the start of *every* time window (`true`) or only used for the first one (`false`), after which the IQN-ILS update governs the acceleration. Two tags control the size and temporal reach (i.e., the amount of content stored in \mathbf{V}_k and \mathbf{W}_k) of the Jacobian's low-rank history: `max-used-iterations` caps the number of stored columns in the least-squares system (default 100 if the tag is absent), and `time-windows-reused` limits how many past time windows contribute columns (default 10 if absent). Tuning these two parameters balances convergence and robustness against memory and computational cost.

To preserve good conditioning of the least-squares system as the history grows, a filtering strategy can be specified with `filter`. The `type` selects the technique, with options `QR1`, `QR1-absolute`, `QR2`, and `QR3`¹¹. These filters were first introduced in the previous section (see **Sect. 3.1.2.2**). Methods labeled `QR1` are based on a mathematical process called GIVENS rotations, while `QR2` uses a modified GRAM-SCHMIDT QR-decomposition scheme. The choice of filter can have a significant impact on the final results of the simulation. The attribute `limit` supplies the numerical threshold ε used by the test (ε is relative for `QR1` and `QR2` in the forms described, absolute for `QR1-absolute`) as explained when presenting the configuration of convergence measurements. If the entire `filter` tag is omitted, the default is a `QR2` filter with `limit` 1×10^{-2} . If the tag is present but if `limit` is not provided, its default is 1×10^{-16} . Choosing a looser threshold (larger ε) removes more nearly dependent columns, improving conditioning but potentially discarding useful information; a tighter threshold retains more history at the risk of ill-conditioning. SCHEUFELE presented in the Chapter 4 of his thesis [85] a detailed comparison of the influence of the different parameters available for filters on convergence properties.

A preconditioner can be applied with `preconditioner` to scale multiple data vectors before forming the least-squares update with the same options as those already mentioned for AITKEN acceleration. If memory or conditioning issues arise, reducing `max-used-iterations`, tightening the filter via `filter` (e.g., `QR2` with a slightly larger `limit`), or enable `freeze-after` once transients settle are good first steps. Using `enforce=true` (by default, set to `false`, see **Lst. 3.5**) in `initial-relaxation` to force the use of the initial relaxation factor at the beginning of each time window before IQN-ILS adapts the step can be an option.

```
<acceleration:IQN-ILS reduced-time-grid="true">
  <initial-relaxation value="{float}" enforce="false"/>
  <max-used-iterations value="{integer}"/>
  <time-windows-reused value="{integer}"/>
  <data scaling="1" name="{string}" mesh="{string}"/>
  <filter limit="1e-16" type="{string}"/>
```

¹¹No information on the implementation of `QR3` or its specific use was found in the preCICE literature.

```

    <preconditioner type="{string}" update-on-threshold="true" freeze-
      after="-1"/>
</acceleration:IQN-ILS>

```

Listing 3.5 – Configuration example for the **IQN-ILS** acceleration method from the preCICE documentation.

The configuration of the **IQN-IMVJ** method is similar to that of IQN-ILS, with one additional field specific to the IMVJ approach. The full configuration options as specified in the preCICE documentation is given in **Lst. 3.6**.

The `imvj-restart-mode` tag controls how the method restarts after a certain number of time windows to reduce both computational cost and memory requirements. This was introduced in the work of SCHEUFELE [85, 87] and provides an efficient way to represent the Jacobian approximation across multiple time steps. More information on these methods is provided in **Sect. 3.1.2.2**. The `type` attributes specifies the restart strategy with the following options available:

- **no-restart** – Continuous Jacobian accumulation without any resets.
- **RS-0** (RS-0) – Drop all information and the Jacobian approximation is computed from scratch.
- **RS-LS** (RS-LS) – Clear the representation of the Jacobian approximation, but keep the last M time windows to create $\hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1}$.
- **RS-SVD** (RS-SVD) – Clear the representation of the Jacobian approximation, but keep the dominant modes by using a truncated singular value decomposition (SVD) of the Jacobian approximation and construct $\hat{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{prev}}^{-1}$.
- **RS-SLIDE** (RS-SLIDE) – Keep the last M time windows and slide the representation of the Jacobian approximation, i.e., the oldest time window is dropped when a new one is added.

Except for the last restart methods, all others are explained in details in [85, 87] and partially in the present report, especially the **RS-SVD** restart strategies as it requires efficient algorithms to perform the SVD procedure. The tag `imvj-restart-mode` has additional options common to all restart methods: `chunk-size` (integer, default 8), which specifies the number of time windows M before restarting; `reused-time-windows-at-restart` (integer, default 8), relevant only for RS-LS, defining how many past windows are retained; and `truncation-threshold` (float, default 1×10^{-4}), relevant only for RS-SVD, setting the SVD cutoff.

```

<acceleration:IQN-IMVJ reduced-time-grid="true">
  <initial-relaxation value="{float}" enforce="false"/>
  <imvj-restart-mode type="RS-SVD" chunk-size="8" reused-time-windows-
    at-restart="8" truncation-threshold="0.0001"/>

```

```

    <max-used-iterations value="{integer}"/>
    <time-windows-reused value="{integer}"/>
    <data scaling="1" name="{string}" mesh="{string}"/>
    <filter limit="1e-16" type="{string}"/>
    <preconditioner type="{string}" update-on-threshold="true" freeze-
      after="-1"/>
</acceleration:IQN-IMVJ>

```

Listing 3.6 – Configuration example for the **IQN-IMVJ** acceleration method from the preCICE documentation.

Convergence measurements Convergence measurements are a crucial aspect of implicit coupling schemes, as they determine when convergence for a given time window is achieved. They are first presented in the configuration options for implicit schemes in **Lst. 3.2**, and at least one tag related to convergence measurements must be specified. Every method follows a similar configuration structure:

```

<{method} data="{string}" mesh="{string}"
  suffices="false"
  strict="false"
  limit="{float}"
/>

```

where `method` can be one of the following:

- **absolute-convergence-measure** – It requires the norm of the residual to reach below a prescribed bound,

$$\|\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k) - \mathbf{x}_k\|_2 < \text{limit}. \quad (3.28)$$

- **absolute-or-relative-convergence-measure** – It is satisfied either if the norm of the residual is below an absolute tolerance,

$$\|\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k) - \mathbf{x}_k\|_2 < \text{abs_limit}, \quad (3.29)$$

or if the norm of the residual compared to the iterate norm is sufficiently small,

$$\frac{\|\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k) - \mathbf{x}_k\|_2}{\|\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k)\|_2} < \text{rel_limit}. \quad (3.30)$$

In this case, both `abs-limit` and `rel-limit` must be set in the configuration.

- **relative-convergence-measure** – It only considers the latter condition,

$$\frac{\|\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k) - \mathbf{x}_k\|_2}{\|\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k)\|_2} < \text{limit}. \quad (3.31)$$

- `residual-relative-convergence-measure` – It compares the current residual to the initial one at the start of the coupling iterations,

$$\frac{\|\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_k) - \mathbf{x}_k\|_2}{\|\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_0) - \mathbf{x}_0\|_2} < \text{rel_limit}. \quad (3.32)$$

The attributes `data` and `mesh` specify the coupling field and mesh to which the convergence measurement applies. The attribute `suffices` (default `false`) indicates whether the convergence measurement alone is sufficient for overall convergence, while `strict` (default `false`) determines whether the convergence condition must be strictly met (`strict` overrules `suffices`), otherwise the simulation is terminated. Finally, the attribute `limit` sets the numerical threshold for convergence, with the default value depending on the chosen method. It is possible to have more than one convergence measurement to improve robustness and ensure convergence across different aspects of the simulation.

3.3 Validation and performance assessment of coupling methods

This section provides insights on the available acceleration methods for parallel implicit coupling schemes in preCICE. As already stated before, explicit schemes are not suitable for the investigated FSI problems due to stability issues. The analysis is based on two standard FSI benchmarks: the lid-driven cavity with a flexible bottom and the TUREK/HRON (FSI3) benchmark. The section begins with a validation of the simulation setup, followed by an investigation of how different parameters affect the performance of the **IQN-ILS** and **IQN-IMVJ** methods. The section concludes with practical guidance on selecting coupling schemes and acceleration methods alongside some concluding remarks.

Note – All the results presented in this section were obtained using only a backward second-order implicit time discretization (SOFI) for the fluid solver, as described in **Sect. 1.2.1**.

3.3.1 Validation of the simulation setup

Validation of the full FSI simulation setup for both reference benchmarks is essential before conducting further analyses. For the lid-driven cavity benchmark described in **Sect. 1.3.1**, the reference is provided by APOSTOLATOS et al. [6] and SPENKE et al. [93]. For the FSI3 TUREK/HRON benchmark introduced in **Sect. 1.3.2**, the reference solution stems from the original benchmark paper by TUREK and HRON [99] and their second paper with updated values [98]. In the following, key validation metrics are reported to demonstrate the correctness of the numerical setup.

Before presenting the results, it is important to explain how the relevant quantities are presented. To ensure consistency with the reference papers, especially for the FSI3 benchmark,

each quantity is expressed in terms of its mean value and amplitude. The process to obtain these values is directly taken from the reference paper for the FSI3 benchmark [99]. The mean and amplitude of a quantity $q(t)$ are defined as:

$$\text{mean} = \frac{M + m}{2}, \quad \text{amplitude} = \frac{M - m}{2}, \quad \text{with} \quad M = \max_t q(t), \quad m = \min_t q(t), \quad (3.33)$$

where M and m are the maximum and minimum values of the quantity $q(t)$ over a specified time interval. In the FSI3 reference paper [99], TUREK and HRON use the last visible oscillation period in the statistically steady regime to compute these values. The frequency is derived from the last oscillation period of $q(t)$. In the present study, the same approach is adopted for both benchmarks (LDC and FSI3).

3.3.1.1 Lid-driven cavity with flexible bottom

Several variants of the lid-driven cavity benchmark have been reported in the literature. The original configuration was introduced by GHIA [49] for the validation of incompressible flow solvers, and later adapted to fluid-structure interaction by adding a flexible bottom wall, as in WALL [104] and MOK [74]. Unlike the FSI3 benchmark, the lid-driven cavity problem does not have a single standardized definition, and variations are common in the literature. As a result, a direct validation against a unique reference is not possible. Instead, comparisons with two representative studies are presented here.

The first reference is the work of APOSTOLATOS et al. [6]. Their configuration is fully two-dimensional, with an inlet/outlet section height of 0.1 m, compared to 0.09375 m in the present study. The fluid mesh contains 50×50 control volumes, while the structure is discretized with 10 C^1 -continuous B-spline elements. The CFD solver used is OpenFOAM, and the structure is modeled with an isogeometric analysis (IGA) code. The coupling is performed in a partitioned manner using the EMPIRE library [92]. The second reference is the work of SPENKE et al. [93]. Their configuration is also two-dimensional, with an inlet/outlet section height of 0.125 m, compared to 0.09375 m in the present study (see **Fig. 1.8** and figure 2 in [93]). Their mesh discretization consists of 1024 elements for the fluid domain and 64 elements for the structure. The CFD solver used is ANSYS Fluent, coupled in a partitioned manner to the Kratos multi-physics code for the structure via the CoCoNut¹² library.

Contrary to these setups, the present work employs a fully three-dimensional mesh. The choice of the inlet/outlet section height in the present study is dictated by the Cartesian, uniform mesh, where the inlet is constrained by nodal positions. The corresponding length is adjusted to ensure consistent inlet/outlet sizes across different refinement levels. This modification slightly alters the pressure distribution, which in turn modifies the resulting forces acting on the bottom lid. This naturally leads to different displacements, explaining a part of the discrepancy with

¹²<https://pyfsi.github.io/coconut/python.html>

SPENKE et al's results.

Note that the results presented below for both APOSTOLATOS et al. [6] and SPENKE et al. [93] were obtained by extracting data from the plots in their respective publications using [OpenCV](https://opencv.org/)¹³. This approach may introduce minor inaccuracies, but it is deemed acceptable for the purpose of validation.

Figure 3.4 – Total displacement $\|\mathbf{d}\|$ of the center point of the flexible bottom wall in the lid-driven cavity benchmark and comparison with reference results from APOSTOLATOS et al. [6] and SPENKE et al. [93]. **Left** – Comparison of the results obtained with the present setup using two different mesh refinements for both the fluid ($64 \times 64 \times 64$, $128 \times 125 \times 128$) and structure (32×32 , 64×64) domains. The inlet/outlet section height is 0.09375 m. **Right** – Comparison of the results obtained with the present setup using a grid containing $64 \times 64 \times 64$ CVs for the fluid and 32×32 elements for the structure domains. The inlet/outlet section height is increased from 0.09375 m to 0.125 m to match SPENKE et al's configuration. All results presented in this figure and computed using the FSI framework discussed in this report are produced using a second-order implicit time discretization (SOFI) for the fluid solver, alongside IQN-ILS with a parallel implicit coupling scheme and the partition-of-unity approach using the **RBF-TPS** kernel as the mapping method.

Fig. 3.4 shows the total displacement $\|\mathbf{d}\|$ of the center point of the flexible bottom wall over time. The present results are compared to those of APOSTOLATOS et al. [6] and SPENKE et al. [93].

The comparison with APOSTOLATOS et al. is presented on the left side of the figure. Good agreement is observed for both refinements, as confirmed by the quantitative results in **Tab. 3.1**. While the transient responses differ, the quasi-periodic regime (after $t > 13$ s) for the results obtained in the present work converges to a similar waveform as those taken from APOSTOLATOS

¹³<https://opencv.org/>

Table 3.1 – Average displacement $\|\bar{\mathbf{d}}\|_2$ of the center point of the flexible bottom wall in the lid-driven cavity benchmark compared to APOSTOLATOS et al. [6]. The results are presented as *mean* \pm *amplitude*. All results presented in this figure and computed using the FSI framework discussed in this report are produced using a second-order implicit time discretization (SOFI) for the fluid solver, alongside **IQN-ILS** with a parallel implicit coupling scheme and the partition-of-unity approach using the **RBF-TPS** kernel as the mapping method. The relative error on the mean is denoted as ε_m and computed as $\varepsilon_m = 100 \times |\text{mean}_{\text{ref}} - \text{mean}_{\text{sim}}| / \text{mean}_{\text{ref}}$, while the relative error on the amplitude is $\varepsilon_a = 100 \times |\text{amp}_{\text{ref}} - \text{amp}_{\text{sim}}| / \text{amp}_{\text{ref}}$.

Metric	Apostolatos et al. [6]	$64 \times 64 \times 64$	$128 \times 128 \times 18$
$\ \bar{\mathbf{d}}\ $ [m]	0.2665 ± 0.0380	0.2727 ± 0.0399	0.2753 ± 0.0381
Error mean [%]	–	$\varepsilon_m = 2.32$	$\varepsilon_m = 3.30$
Error amplitude [%]	–	$\varepsilon_a = 5.00$	$\varepsilon_a = 0.26$

Table 3.2 – Average displacement $\|\bar{\mathbf{d}}\|_2$ of the center point of the flexible bottom wall in the lid-driven cavity benchmark compared to SPENKE et al. [93]. The results are presented as *mean* \pm *amplitude*. **Note** – *The benchmark definition was modified to increase the inlet/outlet section height from 0.09375 m to 0.125 m to match Spenke’s setup.* The results are presented as *mean* \pm *amplitude*. All results presented in this figure and computed using the FSI framework discussed in this report are produced using a second-order implicit time discretization (SOFI) for the fluid solver, alongside **IQN-ILS** with a parallel implicit coupling scheme and the partition-of-unity approach using the **RBF-TPS** kernel as the mapping method. The mesh parameters are set to $64 \times 64 \times 64$ CVs for the fluid domain and 32×32 elements for the structure. The relative error on the mean is denoted as ε_m and computed as $\varepsilon_m = 100 \times |\text{mean}_{\text{ref}} - \text{mean}_{\text{sim}}| / \text{mean}_{\text{ref}}$, while the relative error on the amplitude is $\varepsilon_a = 100 \times |\text{amp}_{\text{ref}} - \text{amp}_{\text{sim}}| / \text{amp}_{\text{ref}}$.

Metric	Spenke et al. [93]	$h = 0.125$	$h = 0.09375$
$\ \bar{\mathbf{d}}\ $ [m]	0.2468 ± 0.0436	0.2431 ± 0.0467	0.2727 ± 0.0399
Error mean [%]	–	$\varepsilon_m = 1.49$	$\varepsilon_m = 10.5$
Error amplitude [%]	–	$\varepsilon_a = 7.11$	$\varepsilon_a = 8.48$

et al. [6]. In the following sections, only the coarsest mesh refinement for this case will be used, as it is sufficient to obtain meaningful results in a relatively short time.

The comparison with SPENKE et al. is shown on the right side of **Fig. 3.4**. In this figure, the results for the coarsest mesh refinement ($64 \times 64 \times 64$ for the fluid and 32×32 for the structure) and the initial inlet/outlet section height of 0.09375 m are shown again for clarity. The results obtained with the present setup using an increased inlet/outlet section height of 0.125 m to match SPENKE et al’s configuration are also shown. Good agreement is observed with the reference results [93] when the inlet/outlet section height is increased. Quantitative results in **Tab. 3.2** further support this observation. This can be explained by the fact that the outlet height affects the pressure distribution inside the cavity: a larger outlet reduces the overpressure generated by the moving lid, thereby decreasing the forces acting on the flexible wall. Paying attention to the value of this parameter is crucial for comparing results across different studies.

Figure 3.5 – Static pressure field relative to the outlet pressure $p_o = 0$ Pa and streamlines at different time steps for the lid-driven cavity benchmark. All results presented in this figure are produced using a second-order implicit time discretization (SOFI) for the fluid solver, alongside **IQN-ILS** with a parallel implicit coupling scheme and the partition-of-unity approach using the **RBF-TPS** kernel as the mapping method.

To complement these results, **Fig. 3.5** shows the static pressure field (relative to the outlet pressure) and the corresponding streamlines at different time steps. The flow is characterized by a large recirculation zone, clearly visible in the center of the cavity. Owing to the strong spatial variations in the velocity field, visualizations of the velocity magnitude or components were omitted, as they provide limited additional insight. The imposed oscillatory motion on the flow by the top wall with a frequency of 0.2 Hz¹⁴ generates forced oscillations of the flexible bottom wall at the same frequency, in agreement with the reference solution [93] and other comparable studies [74, 104].

3.3.1.2 Turek/Hron FSI3 benchmark

The original study by TUREK and HRON [99] provides reference values for the drag and lift forces acting on the flexible structure, as well as for the displacements of the tip along the x - and y -directions. An updated set of reference values was later published by the same authors [98]. Both of these studies rely on a monolithic approach to solve the coupled FSI problem, as described in detail in the respective papers [98, 99]. The meshes used in these works are comparable to those associated with the **coarse** refinement level introduced in **Sect. 1.3.2**. To complement these references, additional data are considered from the **solid4foam official website**¹⁵ and from the work of FABBRI [40, 41]. Unlike the monolithic studies, these references employ a partitioned approach, similar to the one used in the present work, but with different solvers and coupling libraries. More precisely:

- **solid4foam** — **solid4foam** is a toolbox for solid mechanics and fluid-structure interaction

¹⁴Although not shown in this report, this was confirmed by measurements on the data presented in [6, 93] and the present work.

¹⁵<https://www.solid4foam.com/tutorials/more-tutorials/fluid-solid-interaction/HronTurekPsi3.html>

simulations in OpenFOAM and `foam-extend` [21]. The results reported here are taken from the work of TUKOVIĆ [97]. Both the fluid and solid solvers are based on the finite volume method (FVM) and implemented within the OpenFOAM framework. The fluid mesh contains 21,344 control volumes, while the solid mesh consists of 328 quadrilateral elements.

- FABBRI [40, 41] — The fluid domain is solved using the `YALES2`¹⁶ CFD solver, and the structure is modeled with a custom finite element solver. The coupling is performed with the `CWIPI`¹⁷ library. The data presented in **Tab. 3.4** are extracted from figure 5.6 in [40]. The fluid mesh contains 173,000 triangular control volumes, while the structure is discretized with 70 nine-node quadrilateral elements.

The results obtained with the three mesh refinements introduced in **Sect. 1.3.2** using the present FSI framework are compared in **Tab. 3.3** to the aforementioned references. The updated values of TUREK and HRON [98] are used as the main reference for validation. A comparison based on the relative errors is provided in **Tab. 3.4**.

The present results, obtained with a *partitioned* approach, show good agreement with the reference values from TUREK and HRON, with discrepancies decreasing as the mesh is refined, except for the displacements. This latter discrepancy is most likely due to the measurement procedure as presented in **Eq. (3.33)** and the scale of the reported quantities. Indeed, while the forces are of the order of hundreds of Newtons, the displacements are only a few millimeters. Consequently, small absolute errors in displacement lead to relatively large percentage deviations. Moreover, the evaluation method relies on the last captured oscillation period, which is sensitive to noise and to transient effects that may still be present. These factors could explain the observed discrepancies.

Fig. 3.6 illustrates selected flow features at different time steps for the `coarse` mesh. For clarity, the domain is clipped to approximately half of its full size. The top row shows the static pressure relative to the outlet ($p_o = 0$ Pa), the middle row the vorticity magnitude, and the bottom row the velocity magnitude. Because of the relatively coarse mesh, some flow structures are not fully resolved. In particular, vortex shedding behind the cylinder is barely visible in the vorticity and pressure fields, except in the immediate vicinity of the cylinder, where local mesh refinement has been applied. It is worth noting that oscillations of the lift force at the tip of the flexible structure occur at twice the frequency of the drag force oscillations, as expected from the benchmark geometry.

The results presented in this section validate the numerical setup for both reference benchmarks. The following sections build upon this foundation to investigate the performance of different acceleration methods for parallel implicit coupling schemes in preCICE.

¹⁶<https://www.coria-cfd.fr/index.php/YALES2>

¹⁷<https://github.com/onera/cwipi>

Table 3.3 – Comparison of drag and lift forces acting on the whole structure alongside the displacements of its tip in the FSI3 benchmark. Values are given as *mean ± amplitude [in brackets: frequency]*. All results presented in this table are produced using a second-order implicit time discretization (SOFI) for the fluid solver, alongside **IQN-ILS** with a parallel implicit coupling scheme and the partition-of-unity approach using the **RBF-TPS** kernel as the mapping method.

Source	Drag [N]	Lift [N]
Present work		
coarse	458.08 ± 30.62 [11.24]	3.95 ± 237.85 [5.65]
medium	459.23 ± 32.56 [10.99]	2.61 ± 185.9 [6.0]
fine	459.65 ± 29.36 [10.99]	2.38 ± 163.81 [5.0]
Monolithic approach		
Turek/Hron (2006) [99]	457.3 ± 22.66 [10.9]	2.22 ± 149.78 [5.3]
Turek/Hron (2010) [98]	460.5 ± 27.74 [10.93]	2.30 ± 153.91 [5.46]
Partitioned approach		
solid4foam [97]	459.18 ± 24.86 [11.07]	1.59 ± 155.9 [5.53]
Fabbri [40, 41]	–	–
Source	Disp. X [mm]	Disp. Y [mm]
Present work		
coarse	-2.62 ± 2.46 [11.24]	1.45 ± 33.32 [5.65]
medium	-2.88 ± 2.75 [10.99]	1.48 ± 34.88 [6.0]
fine	-2.97 ± 2.82 [10.99]	1.43 ± 35.54 [5.0]
Monolithic approach		
Turek/Hron (2006) [99]	-2.69 ± 2.53 [10.9]	1.48 ± 34.38 [5.3]
Turek/Hron (2010) [98]	-2.88 ± 2.72 [10.93]	1.50 ± 34.95 [5.46]
Partitioned approach		
solid4foam [97]	-2.72 ± 2.58 [11.07]	1.67 ± 33.84 [5.53]
Fabbri [40, 41]	-3.01 ± 2.77 [10.99]	1.42 ± 35.89 [5.49]

Table 3.4 – Relative error on relevant quantities compared to TUREK and HRON (2010) [98]. The relative error on the mean is denoted as ε_m and computed as $\varepsilon_m = 100 \times |\text{mean}_{\text{ref}} - \text{mean}_{\text{sim}}| / \text{mean}_{\text{ref}}$, while the relative error on the amplitude is $\varepsilon_a = 100 \times |\text{amp}_{\text{ref}} - \text{amp}_{\text{sim}}| / \text{amp}_{\text{ref}}$.

Metric		coarse	medium	fine
Drag [N]	ε_m	0.53	0.28	0.19
	ε_a	10.37	17.39	5.83
Lift [N]	ε_m	57.91	4.39	4.9
	ε_a	54.5	20.83	6.43
Disp. X [mm]	ε_m	9.16	0.13	3.19
	ε_a	9.63	0.93	3.56
Disp. Y [mm]	ε_m	1.67	0.88	2.76
	ε_a	4.65	0.21	1.7

Figure 3.6 – Composite visualization of the FSI3 benchmark on the coarse mesh. *Top row:* static pressure relative to outlet pressure $p_o = 0$ Pa. *Middle row:* vorticity magnitude. *Bottom row:* velocity magnitude. Snapshots correspond to $\Delta t \in \{1.8, 2.8, 3.8\}$ s.

3.3.2 Comparison between constant under-relaxation and IQN variants

The first step in assessing acceleration methods for parallel implicit coupling schemes is to compare the two **IQN** variants available in preCICE (**IQN-ILS** and **IQN-IMVJ**) against a baseline: *constant under-relaxation*. **AITKEN** dynamic under-relaxation is not considered here, as it could not be made to work reliably with the present setup. The root cause could not be identified within the timeframe of this study. Note that constant under-relaxation is paired with a serial implicit scheme, while both quasi-**NEWTON** variants are used with a parallel implicit scheme. This is recommended in the preCICE documentation, as constant under-relaxation is not suitable by construction for a parallel scheme.

The objective of any acceleration method is to reduce the number of coupling iterations required to reach a prescribed tolerance, thereby improving time-to-solution. This is particularly important in partitioned FSI simulations, where each coupling iteration entails solving both the fluid and solid subproblems. As shown in **Fig. 3.7a** and **Fig. 3.7b**, both **IQN-ILS** and **IQN-IMVJ** substantially decrease the number of iterations per time step compared to constant under-relaxation. In both benchmarks, the **IQN** variants typically converge for a relative FSI convergence criterion (specified with a `relative-convergence-measure` tag) of 1×10^{-5} in at most four iterations per time window, whereas constant relaxation requires between 10 and 40 iterations, depending on the case.

Figure 3.7 – Number of coupling iterations per time window for FSI3 and LDC using ■ constant under-relaxation, ■ IQN-ILS, and ■ IQN-IMVJ, with RS-LS as restart method. For FSI3, only a subset of the total time horizon is shown for clarity.

This reduction naturally translates into shorter wall-clock times, as summarized in **Tab. 3.5**. For FSI3, the total simulation time drops from 588 minutes with constant under-relaxation to about 27 minutes with either IQN variant. For the lid-driven cavity, the time decreases from 1895 minutes to about 162 minutes, corresponding to speedups by a factor of approximately 22 (FSI3) and 12 (LDC).

Table 3.5 – Overall simulation time (minutes), including initialization and finalization, reported by the SLURM job manager on MARVIN. Left: FSI3; right: LDC.

Method	Cst. Rlx.	ILS	IMVJ
Time [min]	588	27	26

Method	Cst. Rlx.	ILS	IMVJ
Time [min]	1895	162	162

As seen in **Fig. 3.8**, both IQN variants yield solutions in excellent agreement with those obtained using constant under-relaxation for both test cases. Some mild oscillatory noise appears near extrema in FSI3. With the current parameters this does not degrade significantly the accuracy or stability. Decreasing the FSI relative convergence measurement threshold ε_{rel} helps to mitigate this phenomenon.

Both IQN variants (IQN-ILS and IQN-IMVJ) do not appear to alter the physical outcome of the simulations in a noticeable way compared to constant under-relaxation. However, they significantly reduce the number of coupling iterations and the total runtime. It is important to note that *the choice of acceleration method is problem dependent*. In practice, certain configurations converge rapidly with one variant but prove difficult or even fail to converge with another, and vice versa. Robustness can be sensitive to the coupling physics, discretization choices, time-step size, mapping settings, and restart strategy. Thus, method selection and parameter tuning should be guided by small preliminary runs on the target problem.

(a) FSI3.

(b) LDC.

Figure 3.8 – Comparison of drag and lift forces for FSI3 and of displacements along the x - and y -axes for LDC using **constant under-relaxation**, **IQN-ILS**, and **IQN-IMVJ**, with **RS-LS** as restart method. For FSI3, only a subset of the total time horizon is shown for clarity.

3.3.3 Influence of the filtering parameters on IQN-ILS

For this study, only the FSI3 benchmark is considered due to time constraints. This case is also intrinsically more challenging to stabilize than the lid-driven cavity case. Two parameters of the **IQN-ILS** filtering procedure are investigated: the filter type and the sensitivity threshold s_f . **Fig. 3.9** and **Fig. 3.10** report the number of iterations per time window and key force metrics for different values of these parameters.

By default, preCICE uses a **QR2** filter with a sensitivity of 1×10^{-3} for both **IQN-ILS** and **IQN-IMVJ**. As shown in **Fig. 3.9**, **QR1-abs** and **QR2** yield similar results, whereas **QR1** introduces significantly more noise in the lift and drag signals. Moreover, the number of coupling iterations with **QR1** is also noticeably higher and frequently reaches the maximum allowed (set at 200 sub-iterations), which increases the total runtime (see **Tab. 3.6**). This indicates that **QR1** is not suitable for the present setup, or would require a much stricter sensitivity threshold. Consequently, **QR2** is adopted for the remainder of this work. While the filter choice is case dependent, **QR2** appears more robust here, also under parameter variations, as shown below.

Table 3.6 – Overall simulation time (minutes), including initialization and finalization, reported by SLURM on MARVIN, for different filters (FSI3).

Filter	QR1	QR1-abs	QR2
Time [min]	157	24	27

For the **QR2** filter specifically, decreasing the sensitivity threshold below 1×10^{-3} does not significantly reduce the iteration count but increases noise in the force signals compared to higher thresholds. Raising the threshold to 1×10^{-1} yields a slight increase in iterations, while the force histories remain consistent with other values, as shown in **Fig. 3.10**. The impact on the total runtime is small (see **Tab. 3.7**), except at 1×10^{-1} . Overall, the default value 1×10^{-3} offers a good compromise between stability and performance for this setup.

Table 3.7 – Overall simulation time (minutes), including initialization and finalization, reported by SLURM on MARVIN, for different **QR2** sensitivities (FSI3).

Sensitivity	1×10^{-1}	1×10^{-2}	1×10^{-3}	1×10^{-4}	1×10^{-5}	1×10^{-6}
Time [min]	35	27	27	24	24	27

As with acceleration methods, the filter selection and tuning are problem dependent. Configurations that converge robustly with one filter may be difficult to stabilize with another. Small preliminary studies on the target configuration are recommended to identify robust settings before production runs.

(a) Coupling iterations per time window.

(b) Lift and drag forces.

Figure 3.9 – Effect of the filter choice on coupling iterations and force/displacements measurements with the following choices: ■ QR2, ■ QR1, and ■ QR1-abs.

(a) Coupling iterations per time window.

(b) Lift and drag forces.

Figure 3.10 – FSI3 with **QR2**: Effect of the filter sensitivity $s_f \in \{1 \times 10^{-1}, 1 \times 10^{-2}, 1 \times 10^{-3}, 1 \times 10^{-4}, 1 \times 10^{-5}, 1 \times 10^{-6}\}$ on coupling iterations and force/displacements measurements.

3.3.4 Comparison of different restart alternatives for IQN-IMVJ

For this analysis, only the LDC benchmark is considered, owing to unresolved issues with the **RS-SVD** restart method in the FSI3 setup within the timeframe of this study. The number of coupling iterations per time window and the displacements along the x - and y -axes for different restart methods are shown in **Fig. 3.11a** and **Fig. 3.11b**, respectively.

IQN-IMVJ with the restart method **RS-LS** was already compared to other acceleration method in **Fig. 3.8**. It will serve as reference point. All three restart methods produce results in close agreement with one another. The iteration count is largely insensitive to the restart choice. However, the total runtime differs appreciably (**Tab. 3.8**): **RS-SVD** is substantially more expensive than **RS-0** and **RS-LS**. This overhead is most likely dominated by the singular value decompositions performed at each restart. Further tuning of **RS-SVD**-related parameters might improve the performance. Profiling this case with the available tools in preCICE could help identify bottlenecks. Without any clear stability advantage on this case, **RS-LS** or **RS-0** are preferable for the present setup.

Table 3.8 – Overall simulation time (minutes), including initialization and finalization, reported by the SLURM on MARVIN, for different restart methods (LDC).

Method	RS-0	RS-LS	RS-SVD
Time [min]	164	163	213

3.4 Preliminary conclusions

Across the two benchmarks, **IQN-ILS** and **IQN-IMVJ** consistently reduced the coupling iterations per time window to at most four, while *constant under-relaxation* required 10 to 40 iterations depending on the case (see **Fig. 3.7a** or **Fig. 3.7b**). This translated into substantial wall-clock speedups without noticeably degrading accuracy (**Fig. 3.8**, **Tab. 3.5**). The choice of the filter and restart strategy, however, had an impact on the computational cost and the stability. For FSI3, **QR1** introduced noise in the force histories and triggered near-maximum iteration counts, whereas **QR2** (and **QR1-abs**) delivered stable, low-iteration runs (**Fig. 3.9**, **Tab. 3.6**). An analysis on the influence of the **QR2** filter sensitivity threshold indicated that $s_f = 10^{-3}$ offers a good balance between stability and performance, with limited runtime variation except at the extremes (**Fig. 3.10**, **Tab. 3.7**). For the LDC case, all restart methods produced comparable solution quality, but **RS-SVD** significantly increased the runtime compared to **RS-0** and **RS-LS** (**Fig. 3.11**, **Tab. 3.8**). Notably, AITKEN dynamic relaxation could not be made to work reliably in the present setup, and **RS-SVD** exhibited unresolved issues for FSI3 within the project timeframe.

Based on these findings and the preCICE literature [28, 85], the following guidelines are proposed

(a) Coupling iterations per time window.

(b) Displacements along the x - and y -axes.

Figure 3.11 – LDC: Effect of restart method on coupling iterations and wall displacements. Methods compared: **RS-0**, **RS-LS**, and **RS-SVD**.

for selecting and tuning acceleration methods in preCICE. These recommendations are not exhaustive and should be adapted to the specific problem at hand.

- **Establish a stable baseline** – Begin with *constant under-relaxation* to validate the coupling configuration (physics, discretizations, time step). Once stable, switch to an **IQN** variant to accelerate.
- **Preferred defaults for most cases.** Use **IQN-ILS** or **IQN-IMVJ** with their default values as specified in the [XML reference](#)¹⁸. These settings provide good starting points for most problems. The default setting for the filter appeared sufficient for both benchmarks studied here. This is consistent with recommendations in the literature [28].
- **Filter tuning.** If force/displacement signals exhibit high-frequency noise or iteration counts approach the limit, adjust the specific parameters of the acceleration methods (number of reused iterations, restart methods, etc.) or review the choice of the FSI convergence measurement. **QR2** is generally preferred to **QR1** as it uses the most recent information in priority, when removing columns from the matrices \mathbf{V}_k and \mathbf{W}_k during the filtering steps [28].
- **Restart strategy (IQN-IMVJ).** Favor **RS-LS** as a pragmatic compromise between performance, robustness, and cost. **RS-0** is a simple and effective fallback. Not enough data on **RS-SVD** could be gathered during the project timeframe, so that no definitive conclusions could be drawn. It is also possible to avoid using a restart method at all, but this is not recommended in general as it increases memory consumption and overall computational cost.
- **Expect case-to-case variability.** Convergence behavior is sensitive to the coupled physics, discretization, time step, mapping settings, and restart/filter parameters. Run short preliminary studies on the target configuration to identify robust settings before production runs.

¹⁸<https://precice.org/configuration-xml-reference.html>

Conclusions and perspectives

4.1 General conclusions

During this internship, the main objectives were twofold: first, to provide a comprehensive review of the theoretical and practical aspects of partitioned Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) simulations with the multi-physics coupling library preCICE, and second, to evaluate the performance of two key components: Radial Basis Function (RBF)-based mapping methods with the partition-of-unity (PU) approach, and interface Quasi-NEWTON (**IQN**) acceleration methods for parallel implicit coupling schemes. These methods were expected to provide significant speed-ups and improved robustness compared to the simpler approaches (e.g., constant under-relaxation with serial implicit coupling schemes, global RBF-based mapping methods) previously used at the Department of Fluid Mechanics (Pfs).

The first chapter of this work (see **Chap. 1**) introduced the terminology specific to preCICE and provided an overview of the library together with its main features. It also presented the two solvers coupled through preCICE, namely the finite-volume solver FASTEST-3D with an ALE formulation and the finite-element solver CalculiX. Alongside the presentation of the solvers, the chapter discussed the FSI benchmarks used for validation of the simulation setup: the lid-driven cavity with a flexible bottom (LDC) [6, 93] and the TUREK/HRON FSI3 benchmark [98, 99]. The purpose of this chapter was to establish the terminology and background required for the subsequent chapters, which focused on the practical implementation and evaluation of mapping and coupling methods in preCICE, and to provide a solid foundation for future research within the Department of Fluid Mechanics, particularly for researchers seeking to configure preCICE beyond its default settings.

The investigation of mapping methods, presented in **Chap. 2**, began with a theoretical overview and comparison of projection-based techniques (nearest-neighbor, nearest-projection, etc.) and RBF-based methods. Projection-based methods are computationally efficient and straightforward to use, but they often lack accuracy, especially when dealing with non-conforming meshes.

By contrast, RBF-based methods generally achieve higher accuracy, though their configuration is more demanding due to the need to select suitable kernel functions and associated parameters (e.g., support radius, shape parameter). Although the preCICE team has provided an efficient parallel implementation of RBF methods, their global nature can lead to conditioning issues for large-scale problems and increased computational costs.

To address these limitations, the partition-of-unity (PU) approach was introduced. PU enables the use of parameter-free kernels such as thin-plate splines on larger meshes, which would otherwise be computationally prohibitive. The method subdivides the domain into overlapping subdomains, allowing for localized RBF interpolation and a more balanced distribution of computational costs. The evaluation confirmed the superior accuracy of RBF-based methods compared to projection-based ones. This was demonstrated based on several representative configurations, including meshes extracted from the lid-driven cavity benchmark and from a wind turbine blade geometry. The analysis of convergence orders across all mapping methods confirmed and extended previous results reported by the preCICE team [25].

Based on these findings, practical guidelines were derived for configuring RBF methods. Globally supported kernels, such as multiquadrics, should generally be avoided due to the difficulty of selecting an appropriate shape parameter and the poor conditioning of the kernel matrix. Parameter-free kernels, such as thin-plate splines, are recommended for their robustness and ease of use, particularly when combined with the PU approach. Locally supported kernels also remain a viable option, as the influence of the support radius on the mapping problem is easier to interpret than the abstract shape parameter required by globally supported kernels.

The potential of automated hyperparameter optimization techniques for RBF methods was explored. In particular, leave-one-out cross-validation (LOOCV) was tested as a mean to automatically select a suitable support radius or shape parameter. However, further testing was limited by time constraints. Discussions with the preCICE team during the 2025 preCICE Workshop indicated that such tools are currently under development and represent a promising direction for the continued improvement of RBF-based mapping methods in preCICE.

The third chapter of this work, presented in **Chap. 3**, focused on the evaluation of coupling schemes, with particular emphasis on the introduction of interface quasi-NEWTON (**IQN**) methods for accelerating and stabilizing implicit coupling. The chapter began with a theoretical overview of explicit and implicit coupling schemes, highlighting their respective advantages and limitations, based on the previous work by the preCICE team [28, 48, 85, 100]. Explicit schemes are straightforward to implement, but they are prone to stability issues. This is especially true in FSI applications with incompressible flows and strongly coupled problems, where the added-mass effect can cause severe numerical instabilities. Implicit schemes, by contrast, are more stable and robust, but they require an acceleration method to mitigate the instabilities

inherited from explicit formulations.

On this basis, the chapter introduced the theoretical background of the four acceleration methods currently available in preCICE: constant under-relaxation, dynamic AITKEN under-relaxation, and the two IQN variants, IQN-ILS and IQN-IMVJ. In practice, AITKEN proved unreliable on the two reference benchmarks and was therefore not pursued further, as the root cause of the issue could not be isolated. Comparative testing of the different acceleration methods, together with a parameter study, demonstrated that IQN substantially improves the convergence of implicit coupling schemes and reduces time-to-solution by at least one order of magnitude. Among the two variants, IQN-ILS proved particularly robust and user-friendly, and is recommended as the preferred method for future studies. Nevertheless, coupling configurations remain highly problem-dependent, perhaps even more so than mapping procedures, and typically require preliminary test runs to determine an optimal setup.

A detailed validation of the complete FSI framework on the lid-driven cavity (LDC) and FSI3 benchmarks confirmed both the correctness of the implementation and its consistency with published reference results (see Sect. 3.3.1). The validation setup combined a second-order implicit time discretization (SOFI) for the fluid solver with the partition-of-unity approach using the RBF-TPS kernel as the mapping method, and IQN-ILS as the acceleration technique within a parallel implicit coupling scheme. This configuration proved effective, yielding accurate results across all selected quantities in close agreement with the reference solutions of TUREK and HRON [98, 99] for the FSI3 benchmark and APOSTOLATOS et al. [6] for the LDC benchmark.

Achieving these results required mastering several tools, including the preCICE library, the FASTEST-3D and CalculiX solvers, and the HPC cluster environment. In parallel, a set of scripts was developed to automate the simulation workflow, covering setup, execution, and post-processing. Of particular importance, a Python script was implemented to interface with ASTE, the simulation environment provided by the preCICE team for controlled evaluation of mapping methods. This enabled systematic and automated testing of mapping methods across a wide range of parameter and mesh configurations, and may serve as a valuable resource for future investigations. Finally, although not presented in detail in this report, exploratory work was initiated on GPU-accelerated parameter optimization for RBF-based mapping methods, as a continuation of the efforts on automated hyperparameter optimization.

4.2 Perspectives

To conclude this report, several directions for future research and potential improvements are outlined below:

- **Profiling** – Although preCICE includes a built-in profiling tool, it was not used during this internship. Incorporating it in future studies would help identify performance bottlenecks

and guide targeted optimizations of the coupling process, in particular within the mapping and coupling procedures.

- **Scalability studies** – One of the initial objectives of this internship was to investigate the scalability of the full FSI coupling setup using the LDC benchmark. For this purpose, the benchmark was adapted to a three-dimensional mesh (while boundary conditions enforced two-dimensional flow). Its simple geometry makes it well suited for scalability analysis, but this work could not be completed due to time constraints. Since preCICE is designed for high-performance computing and realistic FSI applications are computationally demanding, a systematic scalability study remains an important next step.
- **Automated parameter optimization** – *Leave-One-Out Cross Validation* (LOOCV) and its variants (e.g., k -fold cross validation) are widely used for hyperparameter tuning in statistics and machine learning. Their application to RBF interpolation was demonstrated by RIPPA [83]. Developing an efficient, possibly GPU-accelerated, implementation of LOOCV or a related approach for RBF-based mapping methods would significantly enhance the preCICE ecosystem.
- **Time interpolation** – The present work used fixed time step sizes for both solvers. In practice, however, fluid and solid solvers often require different step sizes for stability and accuracy: The fluid solvers typically need smaller steps, while imposing such steps on the structure can introduce artificial oscillations. Although preCICE supports time-interpolation schemes to address this mismatch, their performance and impact on accuracy and stability have not yet been evaluated in this context. A systematic study of time interpolation therefore represents a valuable extension of this work.

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